

6G-Path

D2.1 Platform architecture and verticals – initial

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Responsible Author	Qi Wang (UWS) and Jose M. Alcaraz Calero (UWS)		
Contributors	Almudena Díaz Zayas (UMA); Yan Chen, Tarik Taleb, Nora Taleb (ICT-FI); João Fernandes, Luís Cordeiro, Luís Rosa (ONE); Filipe Cabral Pinto, Miguel Mesquita, Carlos Marques (ALB); Pedro Rito, Susana Sargento (IT); Makhoulouf Hadji (ADS); Panayiotis Verrios, Tilemachos Doukoglou, Antonis Georgiou (ACTA); Christina Lessi (OTE); Arturo Torrealba (TID); Andreea Corici, Hemant Zope, Benny Häusler (FOKUS); Nils Lahmann, Simone Kuntz, Mareike-Tabea Jansen (CHAR); Ovidiu Ana, Carmen Lazar (OROF); Sozos Karageorgiou (eBOS); Gregor Liebscher (MCS); Peter Gray (CS); Jorge Gallego, Ana Hermosilla (OdinS); Nicola di Pietro (HPE); Jose M Alcaraz Calero, Pablo Salva Garcia, Qi		

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	Wang (UWS)
Peer reviewer(s)	Panayiotis Verrios (ACTA); João Fernandes, Luís Cordeiro (ONE); Yan Chen, Tarik Taleb (ICT-FI); Andre Tabone, Zak Seridarian, Gregor Liebscher (MCS); Ioannis Chochliouros (OTE)

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	22
1 Introduction	23
1.1 Deliverable Overview	23
1.2 Mapping 6G-PATH Outputs.....	24
1.3 Report Structure	26
2 Initial Reference Architecture	27
2.1 Architecture Overview	27
2.2 Primary Workflows	28
2.2.1 Onboarding Use Case.....	28
2.2.2 Conducting Experiments	31
2.2.3 Monitoring and Reporting Experiment Results	31
3 Architectural Components Description	33
3.1 Portal & Northbound Interface.....	33
3.2 Experiment Lifecycle Manager.....	37
3.3 Monitoring and Analytics	41
3.3.1 Common Monitoring tools.....	41
3.3.2 Additional Monitoring Tools	43
3.3.3 Monitoring Databases.....	44
3.3.4 Analytics	45
3.3.5 Use Case Image Repository.....	46
3.4 Advanced Experimentation Features.....	47
3.4.1 AI as-a-Service.....	47
3.4.2 Security as-a-Service	50
3.4.3 Policy Enforcer	53
3.4.4 Slice Manager.....	55
3.4.5 Closed Loop Coordinator	61
4 Vertical Use Case Blueprints	69
4.1 Farming	69
4.1.1 UC-FARM-1 – Water saving.....	69
4.1.1.1 Motivation.....	70
4.1.1.2 Scenarios Description	70
4.1.1.3 Key components and High-Level Topology	71
4.1.1.4 Requirements	72
4.1.1.5 Validation	73
4.1.1.5.1 Test Cases.....	73
4.1.1.5.2 Validation Tools	73
4.1.1.5.3 KPIs and KVis.....	73
4.1.1.6 Expected Outcomes.....	74
4.1.1.7 Risk Assessment	75
4.1.2 UC-FARM-2 – Smart vineyards.....	76
4.1.2.1 Motivation.....	76
4.1.2.2 Scenarios Description	77
4.1.2.3 Key components and High-Level Topology	77
4.1.2.4 Requirements	79
4.1.2.5 Validation	80
4.1.2.5.1 Test Cases.....	80
4.1.2.5.2 Validation Tools	80
4.1.2.5.3 KPIs and KVis.....	81

4.1.2.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	81
4.1.2.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	82
4.2	Education	84
4.2.1	UC-EDU-1 – XR rural school	84
4.2.1.1	<i>Motivation</i>	85
4.2.1.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	86
4.2.1.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	88
4.2.1.4	<i>Requirements</i>	90
4.2.1.5	<i>Validation</i>	91
4.2.1.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	91
4.2.1.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	91
4.2.1.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVIs</i>	92
4.2.1.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	92
4.2.1.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	93
4.2.2	UC-EDU-2 – Classroom of Future	94
4.2.2.1	<i>Motivation</i>	94
4.2.2.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	94
4.2.2.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	95
4.2.2.4	<i>Requirements</i>	96
4.2.2.5	<i>Validation</i>	97
4.2.2.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	97
4.2.2.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	97
4.2.2.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVIs</i>	98
4.2.2.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	99
4.2.2.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	99
4.2.3	UC-EDU-3 – XR health training.....	100
4.2.3.1	<i>Motivation</i>	100
4.2.3.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	101
4.2.3.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	102
4.2.3.4	<i>Requirements</i>	103
4.2.3.5	<i>Validation</i>	104
4.2.3.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	104
4.2.3.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	105
4.2.3.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVIs</i>	105
4.2.3.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	106
4.2.3.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	106
4.3	Health.....	108
4.3.1	UC-HEALTH-1 – 3D hydrogel patches	108
4.3.1.1	<i>Motivation</i>	108
4.3.1.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	109
4.3.1.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	109
4.3.1.4	<i>Requirements</i>	111
4.3.1.5	<i>Validation</i>	112
4.3.1.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	112
4.3.1.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	113
4.3.1.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVIs</i>	113
4.3.1.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	115
4.3.1.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	115
4.3.2	UC-HEALTH-2 – Elderly monitoring.....	117
4.3.2.1	<i>Motivation</i>	117

4.3.2.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	118
4.3.2.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	118
4.3.2.4	<i>Requirements</i>	121
4.3.2.5	<i>Validation</i>	122
4.3.2.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	122
4.3.2.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	123
4.3.2.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVs</i>	123
4.3.2.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	124
4.3.2.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	125
4.4	<i>Smart Cities</i>	126
4.4.1	<i>UC-CITIES-1 – Connected and sensing city</i>	126
4.4.1.1	<i>Motivation</i>	126
4.4.1.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	127
4.4.1.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	128
4.4.1.4	<i>Requirements</i>	129
4.4.1.5	<i>Validation</i>	131
4.4.1.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	131
4.4.1.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	132
4.4.1.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVs</i>	132
4.4.1.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	134
4.4.1.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	134
4.4.2	<i>UC-CITIES-2 – Automated logistics</i>	135
4.4.2.1	<i>Motivation</i>	135
4.4.2.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	135
4.4.2.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	136
4.4.2.4	<i>Requirements</i>	139
4.4.2.5	<i>Validation</i>	140
4.4.2.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	140
4.4.2.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	140
4.4.2.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVs</i>	142
4.4.2.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	143
4.4.2.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	143
4.4.3	<i>UC-CITIES-3 – Security coordination</i>	144
4.4.3.1	<i>Motivation</i>	144
4.4.3.2	<i>Scenarios Description</i>	145
4.4.3.3	<i>Key components and High-Level Topology</i>	145
4.4.3.4	<i>Requirements</i>	148
4.4.3.5	<i>Validation</i>	149
4.4.3.5.1	<i>Test Cases</i>	149
4.4.3.5.2	<i>Validation Tools</i>	150
4.4.3.5.3	<i>KPIs and KVs</i>	150
4.4.3.6	<i>Expected Outcomes</i>	151
4.4.3.7	<i>Risk Assessment</i>	151
5	<i>Initial Identification of Relevant B5G Technologies and Integration Plan</i>	153
5.1	<i>Identification of Relevant B5G Technologies</i>	153
5.1.1	<i>Wireless Radio and Access Technologies</i>	153
5.1.2	<i>Network Transmission Technologies</i>	155
5.1.3	<i>Network Tiers and Segments</i>	155
5.1.4	<i>Functional Technologies for Enhanced Network Automation</i>	156
5.1.5	<i>Network Security</i>	159

- 5.1.6 Others161
- 5.2 Integration Plan for Relevant B5G Technologies163
- 6 Conclusions165
- Appendices166
 - Appendix 1: ELCM details.....166
 - Workflow.....166
 - Administration interface166
 - Platform Registry167
 - Test case and UE description167
 - Resources and scenarios167
 - Experiment Registry167
 - Grafana dashboard generator168
 - Appendix 2: Security-as-a-Service details169
- References172

List of Figures

Figure 1: Initial reference architecture	27
Figure 2: Use case onboarding workflow	29
Figure 3: Definition of a new experiment to execute the deployment of the Use Case FARM 1	30
Figure 4: Conducting experiments workflow	31
Figure 5: Test case example: Inject measurements in InfluxDB with the Execution ID	32
Figure 6: Positioning of ELCM in 6G-PATH framework	38
Figure 7: ELCM Portal	39
Figure 8: Service and network data analytics function offered as-a-service	49
Figure 9: Closed Loop Coordinator for network slicing (UMA testbed)	66
Figure 10: Management of network slicing [25]	66
Figure 11: Global diagram of the components for the Use Case Farm-1	69
Figure 12: High-level topology of the UC Farm-1	71
Figure 13: Smart Vineyards High Level Topology	79
Figure 14: High Level Diagram of UC-EDU-1	85
Figure 15: High-Level architecture and topology diagram for UC-EDU-1	89
Figure 16: Overall architecture of UC-EDU-2	95
Figure 17: UWS infrastructure topology for UC-EDU-2	96
Figure 18: High-level topology for the remote emergency responder training scenario	103
Figure 19: UC-HEALTH-1 high-level topology	110
Figure 20: UC-HEALTH-2 High-Level Topology	120
Figure 21: UC-CITIES-1 High-Level Topology	129
Figure 22: UC-CITIES-2 High-Level Topology	137
Figure 23: OTE Testbed architecture	138
Figure 24: Autonomous Mobile Robot for transporting loads	139
Figure 25: Indicative probe and monitoring application positions at OTE Lab	141
Figure 26: Application GUI, probe types, measurement results GUI	142
Figure 27: Mission Critical Services: Video, Push-To-Talk and Instant Messaging	146
Figure 28: A high-level view of the Dispatcher in MCX	147
Figure 29: Security coordination scenarios: A high-level view	148
Figure 30: Road-map for technology integration	163
Figure 31: OpenCAPIF architecture	169
Figure 32: OpenCAPIF registration	170

List of Tables

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA deliverable & tasks descriptions	24
Table 2: Overview of 6G-PATH Portal	33
Table 3: Overview of 6G-PATH AAA	34
Table 4: Overview of 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	36
Table 5: Overview of 6G-PATH Test Repository	37
Table 6: Overview of 6G-PATH ELCM	39
Table 7: Overview of 6G-PATH ELCM Portal	40
Table 8: Overview of Monitoring (iPerf Agent for PC component)	41
Table 9: Overview of Monitoring (iPerf Agent for Android component)	42
Table 10: Overview of Monitoring (Ping client for Android component)	43
Table 11: Overview of Monitoring (ACTA/Viavi for UC-CITIES-2-Automated Logistics)	43
Table 12: Overview of Monitoring Database (InfluxDB component)	44
Table 13: Overview of Analytics	46
Table 14: Overview of Use Case Image Repository	47
Table 15: Overview of AI as-a-Service in KAU testbed	48
Table 16: Overview of AI as-a-Service in ALB testbed	49
Table 17: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in UMA Testbed	50
Table 18: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in IT Testbed	52
Table 19: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in FOKUS Testbed	53
Table 20: Overview of Policy Enforcer in ONE Testbed	54
Table 21: Overview of Policy Enforcer in FOKUS Testbed	55
Table 22: Overview of Slice Manager in UWS Testbed	56
Table 23: Overview of Slice Manager in UMA Testbed	57
Table 24: Overview of Slice Manager in OTE Testbed	58
Table 25: Overview of Slice Manager in FOKUS Testbed	59
Table 26: Overview of Slice Manager in ALB Testbed	60
Table 27: Closed Loop Blueprint in FOKUS testbed	62
Table 28: Closed Loop Blueprint in IT/ALB testbed	62
Table 29: Closed Loop Blueprint 01 in ORO testbed	63
Table 30: Closed Loop Blueprint 02 in ORO testbed	64
Table 31: Closed Loop Blueprint in OTE testbed	64
Table 32: Closed Loop Blueprint in UMA testbed	65
Table 33: Overview of Close Loop Coordinator (MIRO)	67

Table 34: Use Case UC-FARM-1 functional requirements	72
Table 35: Use Case UC-FARM-1 performance requirements.....	73
Table 36: Use Case UC-FARM-1 test case description	73
Table 37: Use Case UC-FARM-1 KPIs description.....	74
Table 38: Use Case UC-FARM-1 KVis description.....	74
Table 39: Use Case UC-FARM-1 risk assessment	75
Table 40: Use Case UC-FARM-2 functional requirements	79
Table 41: Use Case UC-FARM-2 performance requirements.....	80
Table 42: Use Case UC-FARM-2 test case description	80
Table 43: Use Case UC-FARM-2 KPIs description.....	81
Table 44: Use Case UC-FARM-2 KVis description.....	81
Table 45: Use Case UC-FARM-2 risk assessment	82
Table 46: Use Case UC-EDU-1 functional requirements	90
Table 47: Use Case UC-EDU-1 performance requirements	91
Table 48: Use Case UC-EDU-1 test case description	91
Table 49: Use Case UC-EDU-1 KPIs description.....	92
Table 50: Use Case UC-EDU-1 KVis description	92
Table 51: Use Case UC-EDU-1 risk assessment	93
Table 52: Use Case UC-EDU-2 functional requirements	96
Table 53: Use Case UC-EDU-2 performance requirements	97
Table 54: Use Case UC-EDU-2 test case description	97
Table 55: Use Case UC-EDU-2 KPIs description.....	98
Table 56: Use Case UC-EDU-2 KVis description	98
Table 57: Use Case UC-EDU-2 risk assessment	99
Table 58: Use Case UC-EDU-3 functional requirements	103
Table 59: Use Case UC-EDU-3 performance requirements	104
Table 60: Use Case UC-EDU-3 test case description	104
Table 61: Use Case UC-EDU-3 KPIs description.....	105
Table 62: Use Case UC-EDU-3 KVis description	105
Table 63: Use Case UC-EDU-3 risk assessment	106
Table 64: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 functional requirements	111
Table 65: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 performance requirements	112
Table 66: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 test case description	112
Table 67: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 KPIs description.....	113
Table 68: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 KVis description	114

Table 69: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 risk assessment	115
Table 70: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 functional requirements	121
Table 71: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 performance requirements	122
Table 72: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 test cases description.....	122
Table 73: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 KPIs description.....	123
Table 74: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 KVis description	124
Table 75: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 risk assessment	125
Table 76: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 functional requirements	130
Table 77: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 performance requirements	130
Table 78: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 test case description	131
Table 79: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 KPIs description.....	132
Table 80: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 KVis description	133
Table 81: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 risk assessment	134
Table 82: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 functional requirements	140
Table 83: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 performance requirements	140
Table 84: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 test case description	140
Table 85: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 KPIs description.....	142
Table 86: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 KVis description	142
Table 87: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 risk assessment	143
Table 88: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 functional requirements	148
Table 89: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 performance requirements	149
Table 90: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 test case description	149
Table 91: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 KPIs description.....	150
Table 92: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 KVis description	151
Table 93: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 risk assessment	151

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description
2D	Two Dimensional
3D	Three Dimensional
3GPP	The 3rd Generation Partnership Project
4G	The Fourth Generation of Mobile Communications
5G	The Fifth Generation of Mobile Communications
5GC	5G Core
5GS	5G System
5GSA	5G Stand-Alone
5QI	5G QoS Identifier
6G	The Sixth Generation of Mobile Communications
AAA	Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting
AAV	Autonomous Aerial Vehicle
AEF	API Exposing Function
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AlaaS	Artificial Intelligence as-a-Service
AMF	Access Management Function
AMF	API Management Function
AMMS	Access and Mobility Management Services
ANCS	Ambulance Nurse Competence Scale
API	Application Programming Interface
App	Application
AR	Augmented Reality
ARPF	Authentication Credential Repository and Processing Function
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
B5G	Beyond 5G
BBU	Baseband Unit
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy

BSS	Business Support System
CA	Carrier Aggregation
CA	Certificate Authority
CaaS	Containers as-a-Service
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CCF	CARIF Core Function
CF	Cell-Free
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CL	Closed Loop
CLC	Closed Loop Coordination
CLG	Closed Loop Governance
CLI	Command Line Interface
CN	Core Network
CPE	Customer Premises Equipment
CPF	Control Plane Function
CN	Collaborative Network
CN	Containerised Network
CNF	Containerised Network Function
CPU	Central Processing Unit
D-MIMO	Distributed MIMO
DaaS	Data as-a-Service
DAF	Data Analytics Function
DB	Database
DCAPBAC	Distributed Capability-Based Access Control
DetNet	Deterministic Network
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DL	Deep Learning
DL	Download
DNN	Data Network Name
DNS	Domain Name System
DoS	Denial of Service

DTN	Digital Twin Network
E2E	End-to-end
EAP	Extensible Authentication Protocol
ECAS	European Commission Authentication System
ECC	Elliptic Curve Cryptography
ELCM	Experiment Lifecycle Manager
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash and Kibana
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
ENI	Experiential Network Intelligence
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
F2F	Face-to-Face
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FL	Federated Learning
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
FR	Functional Requirement
FSO	Free Space Optics
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEO	Geosynchronous Equatorial Orbit
GPS	Global Positioning System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
H2020	Horizon 2020
HALE	High-Altitude Long Endurance
HE	Horizon Europe
HAPS	High Altitude Platform Systems
HMD	Head-Mounted Display
HRV	Heart Rate Variability
HTTP, http	HyperText Transfer Protocol
HTTPS, https	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure

HW	hardware
IaaS	Infrastructure as-a-Service
IBN	Intent-Based Networking
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ID	Identifier
IDN	Intent-Driven Networking
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IHSM	Instituto de Hortofruticultura Subtropical y Mediterránea
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Internet Protocol
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
IRU	Indoor Radio Unit
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communication
JSAC	Joint Sensing and Communication
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JU	Joint Undertaking
KMVaP	KPI Monitoring and Validation Platform
KOPF	Kubernetes Operator
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
LEO	Low-Earth Orbit
LoRa	Long Range
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MaaS	Metal as-a-Service

MAC	Medium Access Control
MAN	Metropolitan Area Network
MANO	(Network) Management and Orchestration
MEC (or Edge)	Mobile/Multi-access Edge Computing
MC	Mission Critical
MCS	Mission Critical Service
MCPTT	Mission Critical Push-To-Talk
MCX	Mission Critical Communications
MDP	Markov Decision Process
MEO	Medium Earth Orbit
MIRO	Multi-domain Infrastructure and Resource Orchestration
ML	Machine Learning
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
mMTC	Massive Machine-Type Communications
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MRTK	Mixed Reality Toolkit
NaC	Network as-a-Code
NCF	Network and Computation Fabric
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Functions Virtualisation
NG	Next Generation
NGAP	Next Generation Application Protocol
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interface
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interface with Linked Data
NITRO	Network Integrated Test, Real-time analytics and Optimisation
NPN	Non-Public Network
NRS	Numerical Rating Scale
NTN	Network and Computation Fabric
NTN	Non Terrestrial Network

NR	New Radio
NRF	Network Repository Function
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NW	Network
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
O-RAN	Open Radio Access Network
OASIS	Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards
OC	Open Call
OCF	OpenCAPIF
OCI	Open Container Initiative
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
OIDC	OpenID Connect
ONEmNEF	OneSource's Microservice-based Network Exposure Function
OS	Operating System
OSM	Open Source MANO
OSS	Operations Support System
OTT	Over The Top
OVS	Open Virtual Switch
OWC	Optical Wireless Communication
PAP	Policy Administration Point
PC	Personal Computer
PCF	Policy Control Function
PDP	Policy Decision Point
PEP	Policy Enforcement Point
PP	Pain Point
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PR	Performance Requirement
PRGS	Paramedic Global Rating Scale
PTT	Push To Talk
QKD	Quantum Key Distribution
QoE	Quality of Experience

QoS	Quality of Service
QR	Quick Response
QRNG	Quantum Random Number Generator
R&D	Research and Development
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
RFC	Request For Comments
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RPE	Rating of Perceived Exertion
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
RTT	Round-Trip Time
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SD	Slice Differentiator
SDG	Software Development Group
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Development Organisation
SECaaS	Security as-a-Service
SFP	Small Form-factor Pluggable
SIM	Subscriber Identity Module
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SNS JU	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
SNWDAF	Service and Network Data Analytical Function
SotA	State of the Art

SRS	Software Radio System
SSH	Secure Shell
SSO	Single Sign-On
SST	Slice/Service Type
SUS	System Usability Scale
SW	Software
TC	Test Case
TC	Traffic Control
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TMF	Tele Management Forum
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TR	Technical Report
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TS	Technical Specification
TSDB	Time Series Database
TSN	Time-Sensitive Networking
TVOS	Terraview OS (Cloud-based operating system)
TWAMP	Two-Way Active Measurement Protocol
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UC	Use Case
UDM	Unified Data Management
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UE	User Equipment
UI	User Interface
UL	Upload
UPF	User Plane Function
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
USB	Universal Serial Bus

USIM	Universal Subscriber Identity Module
UV	Ultraviolet
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
vCPU	virtual Central Processing Unit
VM	Virtual Machine
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VR	Virtual Reality
WAN	Wireless Access Network
WG	Working Group
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity
WOC	Wireless Optical Communication
WP	Work Package
WWW, www	World Wide Web
XaaS	X-as-a-Service
XASML	eXtensible Access Control Markup Language
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XR	Extended Reality
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language
ZSM	Zero touch network & Service Management

Executive Summary

The 6G-PATH project will create a number of geographically distributed 6G-ready testbeds with essential and advanced features for a large variety of vertical use cases (UCs) from the project's vertical partners and prospective third parties interested in deploying and testing their use cases. The main work carried out in this phase of the project has focused on reviewing the 6G-PATH reference architecture and its functional building blocks, defining the vertical use cases within the project consortium and identifying relevant beyond 5G (B5G) technologies.

Accordingly, this deliverable presents the following major outcomes: Firstly, it describes the latest reviewed reference 6G-PATH architecture and its components and interface specifications. The primary workflows for onboarding, testing and evaluating vertical use cases are proposed. Secondly, each of the major components is specified with functions, interfaces, inputs, post conditions etc., identified and further details for specific deployment considerations are provided in the Appendices. Thirdly, it defines the blueprints of all the vertical use cases with refined Key Value Indicators (KVIs) and corresponding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The facilities of each of the use cases are mapped to the reference architecture. Fourthly, it introduces "key" beyond 5G technologies that may be relevant to this project's scope. Moreover, a potential roadmap for integrating selected technologies into the 6G-PATH architecture is proposed.

The purpose of the deliverable is manifold: The reviewed architecture is a reference for the R&D activities in individual components and the subsequent system integration and testing. The defined vertical use case blueprints are a reference for the R&D activities of use case design, implementation, deployment, trials and pilot testing, validation and evaluation. The identified beyond 5G technologies are used as a reference for the subsequent potential integration of selected beyond 5G technologies into the 6G-PATH ecosystem, through collaboration with third-party partners and the wider community.

The main conclusions include the following: A pragmatic approach has been taken in reviewing and refining the 6G-PATH architecture, components and use cases, in line with the schedules of Open Calls for third parties' use cases. The reference architecture builds on the experiences of 5G and beyond projects and standards. The main difference lies in the expected advanced features to be offered in 6G-PATH, such as AI as-a-Service (AlaaS), Security as-a-Service (SECaaS), Closed Loop Coordination and different flavours of Network Slice Management, among others. The vast majority of the functional building blocks identified in the reference architecture can be "mapped" to existing components across the various testbeds within the project consortium. However, further developments are needed to adapt the existing components to the 6G-PATH architecture. Moreover, additional developments are expected to optimise and further evolve these components regarding functionality and performance. The reviewed vertical use cases represent a broad spectrum of real-world businesses that can benefit from the evolution towards 6G, helping test the KPIs and contributing to the KVIs, as defined. There are challenges ahead, e.g. integrating of components from partners and potentially from third parties to enhance the capabilities of the existing use case testbeds. Many potentially related beyond 5G technologies are available for the project to scrutinise further and justify the optimal and feasible choices for building a powerful 6G-ready system as envisioned.

1 Introduction

The EU 6G-PATH project aims to help foster the further development and integration of new and improved tools and products from EU companies with 5G/6G, while also measuring relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs). To this end, seven (-7-) geographically distributed testbeds (FOKUS, IT/ALB, KAU, ORO, OTE, UMA, UWS) from the project consortium will be used by ten (-10-) use cases spread across four (-4-) “key” verticals, that is: Health, Education, Smart Cities and Farming. This is the first deliverable in Work Package (WP) 2 of the project. The main objective of this document is to report all the activities carried out in the context of WP2 since the kick-off of the 6G-PATH project.

1.1 Deliverable Overview

WP2 has successfully kicked off its three tasks:

- *Task 2.1 – Architecture Review*
- *Task 2.2 - Verticals use cases and KVIs/KPIs refinement*
- *Task 2.3 - Identification of relevant B5G technologies and integration plan*

Since the kick-off, during this period, each task has concentrated on different objectives with the main intention of producing the foundations for the 6G-PATH project architecture, vertical use cases and further technologies to be investigated and demonstrated. The present deliverable reports the following activities in the three tasks.

Task 2.1 has focused on providing an initial reference architecture for the 6G-PATH framework. To achieve the reference architecture, the consortium has followed a hybrid approach, combining both a top-down and a bottom-up methodology. The top-down approach has been more focused on identifying the different logical components required for the successful delivery of the 6G-PATH architecture and clarifying the partners' responsibilities for the components. The bottom-up approach has been more focused on pragmatically identifying the different assets available by each of the involved partners and whether they can be reused, adapted, or extended to provide the functionalities of each logical architectural component. This document provides the results of this hybrid methodology and the first release of an agreed and consolidated reference architecture. A component table template has been adopted to offer a coherent overview of each of the key components.

Task 2.2 has focused on providing a homogeneous and concrete definition and description of each of the ten (-10-) different use cases led by the 6G-PATH consortium. These use cases will be deployed and executed in the original 6G-PATH testbeds. To achieve this, the consortium has first developed a common use case blueprint template to describe each of these use cases. The use case blueprints include information on motivation, scenarios, “key” components and high-level topology, requirements, validation, expected outcomes and risks for all the use cases, and collectively such blueprints have defined each use case in detail. This document does not cover a detailed description of the individual testbeds (except identified “key” components in the reference architecture), as this will be “addressed” in the forthcoming deliverables associated with WP3. The task has also clarified the distribution of the advanced experimentation capabilities (features) among individual testbeds.

Task 2.3 has focused on identifying of the different beyond 5G and pre-6G technologies and advanced capabilities to be investigated in 6G-PATH. To this end, it has investigated the state-of-the-art (SotA) including ongoing SNS projects relevant to 6G and provided feedback to the architectural components of the 6G-PATH required to allow the demonstration of such capabilities.

1.2 Mapping 6G-PATH Outputs

This section “maps” 6G-PATH Grant Agreement (GA) commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, to the project’s respective outputs and work performed. The mapping is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Adherence to 6G-PATH GA deliverable & tasks descriptions

6G-PATH GA Component Title	6G-PATH GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			

D2.1 Platform architecture and verticals - initial

Reports on the activities performed in WP2. Focus on the architecture review and use case details.

TASKS			
T2.1 - Architecture review	<p>This task is dedicated to <u>the review of 6G-PATH architecture and the specification of its components and interfaces</u>. Functional blocks of the architecture will be extracted, primarily targeting standalone but loosely coupled software components along with defined interfaces. Beyond the data streams characterised, additional data retrieved and shared across the software components to support the underlying architecture will be specified. The architecture will be used as a reference for all tasks of WP2 and WP3. To trigger WP2 and WP3 early work, an early draft of the reviewed architecture will be internally released at M06 (cf. milestone MS2.2) and successively refined until the formal release of the architecture design and specification (D2.1, scheduled for M10). Following the two-phase approach, a midterm architecture design and specification will be released (D2.2, scheduled for M22), after considering the feedback received from the project first phase experiments. D2.3 will include the final version of the 6G-PATH architecture design and specification, which will address the feedback received from the second phase experiments.</p> <p>Main outcomes: 6G-PATH architecture design and specification (reflected in</p>	<i>Sections: 2 and 3 and all their respective subsections</i>	<i>Section 2 and Section 3 provide the 6G-PATH architectures and the respective interfaces of each of its components.</i>

D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3).

<p>T2.2 - Verticals use cases and KVis/KPIs refinement</p>	<p>This task will refine the <u>reference scenarios and use cases</u>, starting from the relevant descriptions of section 1.3.3 and further <u>tailoring the scenarios to satisfy the needs of the different verticals, business cases and stakeholders</u>. For each vertical use case the <u>KVis and KPIs</u> will be reviewed and improved to incorporate detailed assessment parameters to be used as reference for the 6G trials and pilots' validation and evaluation in WP4. To steer WP2 and WP3 early work, a draft of the vertical use cases, requirements and KVis/KPIs will be internally released at M04 (cf. milestone MS2.1) and successively updated, considering the feedback from the two-phase experiments and evaluation, in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3.</p> <p>Main outcomes: Definition of the verticals use cases and KVis/KPIs (reflected in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3).</p>	<p><i>Section 4 and all its subsections</i></p>	<p><i>Section 4 provides the blueprint of all the 6G-PATH internal use cases and their KPIs and KVis.</i></p>
<p>T2.3 - Identification of relevant B5G technologies and integration plan</p>	<p>This task aims to: 1) <u>identify relevant Beyond 5G (B5G) technologies to integrate in 6G-PATH architecture, platform and use case testbeds to be validated and evaluated in the vertical use case trials, pilots and third-party experiments</u>; 2) establish <u>collaborations with the research projects and research activities responsible for the identified technologies to enable their integration into 6G-PATH</u> through either the open calls or their integration by project partners (technical experts and testbed owners) in the scope of WP3 and WP4 activities. For each identified technology a dedicated 6G-PATH partners team will be defined to be responsible for the communication with the external project/entities, to define the respective integration plan (including roadmap and team roles), and to monitor the integration activities (WP3 and WP4),</p>	<p><i>Section 5 and all its subsections</i></p>	<p><i>Section 5 identifies relevant B5G "key" technologies in all SNS (Smart Networks and Services) JU (Joint Undertaking) projects, and the technology integration plan with 6G-PATH.</i></p>

assessment (WP6) and dissemination (WP7). The preliminary list of “key” relevant groups to monitor are: ongoing SNS JU phase 1 and phase 2 projects; other ongoing Horizon Europe (HE) projects; industry technological innovations; new standards, guidelines or innovation paths; other B5G technologies and innovations worldwide. Initially, these activities will be triggered by consortium partners participation in recent and ongoing projects (SNS JU and Horizon Europe) and standardisation activities, but then complemented by establishing new collaborations and monitoring relevant bodies.

Main outcomes: Plans for the identification and integration of relevant B5G technologies, identification of relevant B5G technologies, description of the partnerships established with other research projects and research activities, and description of the integration and validation outcomes (reflected in D2.1, D2.2 and D2.3).

1.3 Report Structure

The remainder of the deliverable is organised as follows: Section 2 overviews the initial reference architecture, including the building blocks and primary workflows. Section 3 describes the details of the architectural components, including both essential and advanced features. Section 4 presents the blueprints of the vertical use cases. Section 5 identifies the initial investigation of beyond 5G technologies that may be relevant to this project. Finally, Section 6 concludes this document.

2 Initial Reference Architecture

2.1 Architecture Overview

Figure 1: Initial reference architecture

Figure 1 shows the overall architecture overview for the 6G-PATH experimentation framework. The lower part of Figure 1 represents nine (-9-) different 6G testbeds. They correspond to the seven (-7-) testbeds that are initially provided by 6G-PATH project partners, plus two (-2-) additional ones that will be added to the framework via Open Calls. Every testbed is expected to have at least three (-3-) interfaces to enable it to be plugged into the 6G-PATH experimentation framework. Firstly, the *Infrastructure Manager/Orchestrator API/Dashboard* allows local resource management within the scope of every testbed. Secondly, the *Service Manager/Orchestration API/Dashboard* allows local service management in the scope of every testbed. Thirdly, the *Monitoring Northbound API/Dashboard* allows monitoring of both services and resources in the testbed. These are the preconditions in the testbeds. Furthermore, there are several essential building blocks, as shown in the upper layers (above the grey blocks) in Figure 1 to allow the execution of experiments. Moreover, every testbed is expected to provide advanced 6G-ready experiment features. They are depicted in the right-lower part of Figure 1 in darker grey. It is noted that not every testbed will have every advanced functionality. The planned advanced 6G-ready functionalities and their availability in the individual testbeds are presented in more detail in Section 3.4. In the following, the essential functionalities in the 6G-PATH architecture are introduced in the context of the overall operation of the system, whilst more details are provided in Section 3 on a per component basis.

The *6G-PATH Portal and Northbound Interfaces/API* is the entry point for users who plan to experiment in any available 6G-PATH testbeds. User authentication and authorisation will be performed first to ensure that only those authorised users can access the system. To this end, it will interact with the *AAA* (Authentication, Authorisation and Accounting) component of the 6G-PATH architecture. Authenticated and authorised users will then be provided with the set of available testbeds from all the registered testbeds in the *6G-PATH Testbed Repository*, from which the user will use the respective links to get access to the *6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal*. The 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal will allow the users of each of the testbeds to onboard their experiments. Thus, the 6G-PATH Northbound API could be seen as a proxy to allow users to interact graphically with the system.

After a user gains access to a testbed, the *6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELCM)* manages the execution of test cases. The ELCM is a core component of the 6G-PATH experimentation framework, based on ETSI TR 103 761 [1]. Therefore, experiments are formalised in a test, which ELCM will execute. If, a testbed-specific solution needs to be utilised as part of an experiment, a task to launch and configure that solution needs to be included in the test case executed by the ELCM.

As the central point for experimentation, the ELCM is responsible for coordinating the complete lifecycle of the execution of a 6G-PATH experiment. The 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal contains an interface (frontend) to allow configuring the ELCM (backend). When the ELCM receives a request to perform the execution of an experiment, it interacts with other components to carry out its task. Firstly, it retrieves the services/images of the use case from the *6G-PATH Use Case Image Repository* and triggers the deployment of the use case in the indicated testbed, if the experiment requires the deployment of the services and they are not pre-deployed. Then, the 6G-PATH ELCM interacts with the corresponding testbed to execute the use case images. Consequently, it performs the execution of the different test case tools that are executed in order to conduct a concrete evaluation of the performance within the infrastructure, e.g., using a *6G-PATH Monitoring Tool* such as a common monitoring tool like iPerf or a testbed or use case specific tool. After executing both use case images and test case tools, the results generated from the experiment are stored in the *6G-PATH Monitoring Databases* such as InfluxDB. In the test cases, each testbed will include the task of injecting the result data into the Monitoring Databases through a messaging/data streaming mechanism. In the initial release of the 6G-PATH framework, Kafka [2] will be employed. Each testbed needs to include this case and configure it to communicate with each testbed's instance of Kafka. It is noted that each individual testbed will carry out the monitoring using some common and/or testbed or use case-specific monitoring tools. Thus, the 6G-PATH Monitoring Tools should also allow the conversion between the formats available in each testbed to the 6G-PATH monitoring format, common for all the testbeds. Furthermore, the *6G-PATH Analytics* will allow graphical rendering of all the monitoring metrics collected during the execution of an experiment and the results will be visualised and displayed on its dashboard. This Analytics dashboard will utilise the 6G-PATH Testbed Repository to determine how to get access to the different Monitoring Databases populated for the testbed. It will also interact with the 6G-PATH Northbound Interfaces/API to authenticate and authorise the users so that they can only see the results of their experiments in a specific testbed.

It is noted that the 6G-PATH ELCM is instantiated multiple times, one per testbed, to provide experimentation capabilities within the context of the testbed. Moreover, there will be multiple instantiations of the 6G-PATH Monitoring Databases to “keep” the information related to each testbed collected in the same database. Meanwhile, all these databases will have the same data model to allow reusing the same 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal dashboard for all the testbeds at a later stage. Thus, the 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal (also referred to as ELCM Portal hereafter) will also be instantiated per testbed and only the users with permission to access to the testbed will have access the corresponding dashboard.

2.2 Primary Workflows

In the following, the primary workflows for the experimentation are presented.

2.2.1 Onboarding Use Case

The onboarding of the use cases can be handled as an isolated action before the experimentation or demonstration phase, or it included within the experiment/demonstration itself. In the first case, the sequence of actions is shown in Figure 2. The experimenter – or use case provider – briefly accesses the 6G-PATH Portal and queries the available platforms. After verifying the experimenter's identity in the AAA module, the links to the available platforms are sent to the experimenter. The experimenter selects one of them and accesses the

6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal, where the available test cases for that user will be listed. The numbers in Figure 2 indicate this sequence.

Figure 2: Use case onboarding workflow

Figure 3 shows an example of a test case for deployment. Once this test is selected, the ELCM will download the necessary artefacts from the use case image repository to deploy the selected testbed’s infrastructure.

To this end, it will communicate with the local orchestrator available in that infrastructure. The deployment will be monitored by the Monitoring Tools available on that testbed, and the obtained metrics will be stored in the Monitoring Databases with the corresponding Execution ID generated by the ELCM to identify the experiment uniquely.

CREATE EXPERIMENT

Name

Type

Test Cases

- DEPLOY UC FARM 1
- DEPLOY UC FARM 2
- TC01 UC FARM 1
- TC02 UC FARM 1
- TC01 UC FARM 2
- TC02 UC FARM 2

UEs

- UE_S0_IN
- UE_S0_OUT
- UE_local

Scenarios

Figure 3: Definition of a new experiment to execute the deployment of the Use Case FARM 1

The onboarding of the use cases will be implemented as a test case executed via the ELCM. The first step is to define a new experiment in the local 6G-PATH Portal available at each testbed as shown in Figure 2, and the test operator conducts this. The Portal sends an experiment descriptor to the ELCM for the test case to be executed to run the deployment. In the ELCM, the implementation of the deployment test case should include a task or several tasks, which incorporate the commands used for executing the deployment in the respective testbed.

The list of general tasks available is documented in [3]. Three tasks can be used, including the “*Run.CliExecute*”, “*Run.DeployExperiment*” and “*Run.RestAPI*” tasks.

The “*Run.CliExecute*” enables the execution of an application with a CLI (Command Line Interface) or the execution of different types of scripts, in which the deployment steps can be included.

The “*Run.RestAPI*” enables direct invoking of the RESTful API¹ exposed by the orchestrator of the testbed.

The “*Run.DeployExperiment*” is capable of performing deployments based on Helm Charts [4]. The test case for the deployment can include additional tasks to perform some actions such as configuration or activation of the use case or the collection of results. In this case the workflow is similar to that shown in Figure 3.

¹ A RESTful API is an architectural style for an application programming interface that uses HTTP requests to access and use data. For further related information also see, among others: <https://www.techtarget.com/searchapparchitecture/definition/RESTful-API>

2.2.2 Conducting Experiments

Figure 4: Conducting experiments workflow

Figure 4 shows an indicative workflow to execute an experiment. Firstly, the experimenter visits the 6G-PATH Portal and inserts a username and a password. The 6G-PATH Northbound interface receives this authentication request and redirects it to the AAA server. The authentication result indicates whether the user is authenticated and which testbed they are authorised to access. The 6G-PATH Northbound interface will retrieve from the 6G-PATH Testbed Repository all the links necessary for the user to get access to the testbed. The ELCM will retrieve all the images of the use case, if the experiment requires the dynamic deployment of the images as part of the experiment. Subsequently, the experiment will be triggered at the testbed ELCM Portal. After the experiment has begun, the metrics will flow from the testbed and then be stored in the associated Monitoring Database. The numbers in Figure 4 indicate this sequence.

2.2.3 Monitoring and Reporting Experiment Results

In most cases, the monitoring is part of the experiment/demonstration. This means that the test case includes the activation and collection of the measurements as shown in the workflows defined in Figure 4. This does not preclude the definition of a test case that solely collects the available measurements, in which case the workflow would follow the one shown in Figure 2.

The 6G-PATH framework enables aggregating the measurements available in the testbeds in a very simple and flexible way in the Monitoring Databases such as InfluxDB (as this approach links all of them through the same unique Execution ID). The measurements collected by the different monitoring tools deployed in the testbeds will be collected using the definitions of specific tasks in the test case. For example, Figure 5 shows a simple test case that includes a task of the type “*Run.CliExecute*”, which connects via an SSH (Secure Shell) transaction to a VM (Virtual Machine) located in the Edge and executes a script (pingm.sh) that contains a ping from the Edge to the IP address of the UPF and stores the results in a file called “edgeping.csv”. After this task, the test case includes a new task that retrieves the file with the results via an SSH. Finally, the test case includes a task, “*Run.CsvtoInflux*”, which injects results stored in the file into the Monitoring Databases with the Experiment ID of the experiment under execution.

```

Version: 2
Name: EDGEPING
Sequence:
- Order: 20
  Task: Run.CliExecute
  Config:
    Parameters: plink -ssh 10.11.32.XXX -l admin -pw hello -batch -t "sh pingm.sh 10.11.32.1 TESTTEST"
    CWD: C:/ELCM/Experiment
- Order: 21
  Task: Run.CliExecute
  Config:
    Parameters: plink -ssh 10.11.32.XXX -l admin -pw hello -batch -t "cat edgeping_ping.csv" > edgeping.csv
    #Parameters: 'echo'
    CWD: C:/ELCM/Experiment
- Order: 30
  Task: Run.CsvToInflux
  Config:
    ExecutionId: "#{ExecutionId}"
    CSV: "C:/ELCM/Experiment/TESTTESTping.csv" # Replace with the location of the file
    Measurement: ADB_Ping_Agent
    Delimiter: ','
    Timestamp: 'Timestamp'
    Convert: True

```

Figure 5: Test case example: Inject measurements in InfluxDB with the Execution ID

The general tasks documented in [3] can be used to retrieve the available measurements from different sources in the testbed. For example, a “*Run.CliExecute*” task can be used to query a Monitoring Database such as Prometheus [5] for the CPU consumption during a specific interval time (start, end):

```

curl -G 'http://<PROMETHEUS_SERVER>:9090/api/v1/query_range' --data-urlencode
'query=sum(rate(container_cpu_usage_seconds_total[5m])) by (namespace, pod)' --data-urlencode 'start=2024-
07-01T00:00:00Z' --data-urlencode 'end=2024-07-01T01:00:00Z' --data-urlencode 'step=60s'

```

Specific tasks to retrieve measurements from Prometheus, Kafka, and MQTT [6] will be implemented in WP3.

3 Architectural Components Description

This section provides a detailed description of the major components in the 6G-PATH architecture defined in Section 2. A component table is presented to summarise the “key” design aspects of each component, highlighting its expected functions, interfaces with other components (or actors, such as Experimenters), management protocol (if applicable), input and output, and optional information on open source projects, standardisation and related former/ongoing projects for component reuse/adaption (the base version for this component). Further details are described in the corresponding text.

3.1 Portal & Northbound Interface

The **6G-PATH Portal** is the primary entry point for users who want to interact with the 6G-PATH testbeds. It is a front-end interface that enables users to authenticate, select and manage testbed experiments. Once users log in using their credentials, the portal communicates with the backend (interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface) to verify the user’s identity (interface with AAA) and fetch the testbeds (interface with 6G-PATH Testbed Repository) they are authorised to access. The portal displays this information graphically, providing users with URLs to the relevant testbeds and allowing them to initiate and monitor their experiments. The portal offers a user-friendly way to interact with the complex backend infrastructure. Table 2 summarises the 6G-PATH Portal.

Table 2: Overview of 6G-PATH Portal

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	6G-PATH Portal
Functions	Serves as the primary entry point for users who want to interact with the 6G-PATH testbeds.
Interface for the experimenters	Front-end component, Web application
Interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	REST API (GET) /authenticate – this request is redirected to the AAA to authenticate users and returns an access token for subsequent API requests. Subsequently, the 6G-PATH Northbound Interface communicates with the 6G-PATH Testbed Repository to retrieve list of testbeds (URLs) the authenticated user can access.
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	Username, Password
Output/postcondition	Access Token; List of testbeds (URLs) the user has access to
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for	5GMediaHUB ²

² 5GMediaHUB (5G Experimentation Environment for 3rd Party Media Services) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.1010116714, <https://www.5gmediahub.eu/>

component reuse/adaption	
---------------------------------	--

The **AAA (Authentication, Authorisation, and Accounting)** component, implemented with Keycloak³, will be the solution for managing user access and security within the 6G-PATH architecture. Keycloak will handle the authentication process by verifying user credentials when they log into the portal, ensuring secure access. Additionally, it will enforce role-based authorisation, determining which testbeds users can access based on their assigned roles. This guarantees that only authorised users can run experiments on specific testbeds. Beyond access control, Keycloak's accounting functionality will log user activity and track experiment usage, supporting auditing and efficient resource management across the platform. Table 3 summarises the 6G-PATH AAA.

Table 3: Overview of 6G-PATH AAA

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	AAA
Functions	<p>Managing user access and security within the 6G-PATH architecture. Main functions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication: Supports various methods like OAuth2⁴, OpenID Connect⁵, SAML⁶, and social logins (Google, GitHub, etc.) for user authentication. • Authorisation: Implements role-based access control⁷ (RBAC) to manage what users or groups can access within the platform. • Single Sign-On⁸ (SSO): Enables users to authenticate once and access multiple services within the experimentation platform.

³ Keycloak is an open source identity and access management solution. More informative details can be found at: <https://www.keycloak.org/>

⁴ OAuth 2.0 is the industry-standard protocol for authorisation. OAuth 2.0 focuses on client developer simplicity while providing specific authorisation flows for web applications, desktop applications, mobile phones and living room devices. For more details also see: <https://oauth.net/2/>

⁵ OpenID Connect (OIDC) is an identity layer built on top of the OAuth 2.0 framework. It allows third-party applications to verify the identity of the end-user and to obtain basic user profile information. For further details also see: <https://openid.net/>

OpenID verifies the end-user identity but provides no other user information. Its scope is restricted to authentication only. OAuth verifies and grants specific access to protected resources, with customizable scopes. The access is restricted to the delegated scope.

⁶ Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) is an open standard for exchanging authentication and authorisation data between parties, in particular, between an identity provider and a service provider. SAML is an XML-based markup language for security assertions (statements that service providers use to make access-control decisions). For further information also see, *inter-alia*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Security_Assertion_Markup_Language

⁷ Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) refers to the idea of assigning permissions to users based on their role within an organisation. It offers a simple, manageable approach to access management that is less prone to error than assigning permissions to users individually. RBAC is a method of restricting network access based on the roles of individual users within an enterprise. For further information also see, *for example*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Role-based_access_control

⁸ Single Sign-On (SSO) is an identification method that enables users to log in to multiple applications and websites with one set of credentials. SSO streamlines the authentication process for users. SSO allows a user to use a single set of login

- Token Management: Issues, manages, and revokes OAuth2 and OpenID Connect tokens.

Interface for the experimenters	N/A
Interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	REST API
Interface with 6G-PATH Testbed Repository	REST API
Management protocol	REST APIs to handle user management, access tokens, client registration and service configuration. It also supports OAuth2, OpenID Connect, and SAML protocols for authentication and authorisation across integrated services.
Input data for action	User credentials (username/password, social login tokens) Authentication tokens (OAuth2 or OpenID Connect tokens)
Output/postcondition	Access Tokens: OAuth2 or OpenID Connect tokens for authorised sessions. Authentication Status: Whether a user is authenticated or not. User Role and Permission Assignments: Returned to the 6G-PATH portal and other services to enforce access controls.
Applicability of open source projects	Keycloak is an open-source project developed by Red Hat and part of the larger JBoss project ⁹ . It can be freely integrated into any platform and offers a high degree of customisation.
Relation to SDOs	Keycloak adheres to standards defined by OAuth2, OpenID Connect, and SAML specifications, which are supported and governed by standardisation bodies like the IETF ¹⁰ and OASIS ¹¹ .
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

credentials – such as a username and password, or even multi-factor authentication – to access multiple applications. This is a Federated Identity Management architecture, sometimes called as identity federation. Also see, *among others*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Single_sign-on

⁹ For further details also see, *among others*: <https://developers.redhat.com/products/eap/overview>

¹⁰ The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), founded in 1986, is the premier standards development organisation (SDO) for the Internet. The IETF makes voluntary standards that are often adopted by Internet users, network operators and equipment vendors, and it thus helps shape the trajectory of the development of the Internet. For further information see: <https://www.ietf.org/>

¹¹ OASIS (Organization for the Advancement of Structured Information Standards) is a nonprofit consortium that works on developing open standards for the global information society. It has more than 5 000 participants representing over 600 organisations and individual members in more than 65 countries. For further information also see: www.oasis-open.org

The **6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API** is a “key” intermediary in the architecture, acting as a backend service that connects the 6G-PATH Portal, the AAA component and the testbeds. It handles requests from the portal and forwards user authentication requests to the AAA component. Once the authentication and authorisation are validated, the Northbound Interface retrieves the URLs of the testbeds the user can access from the Testbed Repository and presents them via the portal. Additionally, the Northbound Interface handles experiment execution requests, routing them to the appropriate lifecycle engines that manage the actual deployment and execution of experiments on the testbeds. Table 4 summarises the 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API.

Table 4: Overview of 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API
Functions	Backend service that connects the 6G-PATH Portal, the AAA component and the testbeds
Interface for the experimenters	N/A
Interface with AAA	REST API (See AAA component)
Interface with 6G-PATH Testbed Repository	REST API (See 6G-PATH Testbed Repository component)
Interface with 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal	REST API (See 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal component)
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User credentials for authentication (redirected to AAA) • Requests for list of testbeds (redirected to 6G-PATH Testbed Repository) • Experiment execution parameters such as testbed selection and deployment settings (redirected to 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Portal component)
Output/postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Testbed URLs provided via the portal (post-authentication) • Experiment execution request forwarded to lifecycle engines • Experiment initiated on testbeds, or error messages if execution fails
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

The **Testbed Repository** maintains the URLs and metadata centralised storage system that contains information about all the registered testbeds within the 6G-PATH architecture. This component ensures that the Northbound

Interface can retrieve the correct details when a user is authorised to access a testbed. The repository also holds the locations of the monitoring databases linked to each testbed, enabling the system to collect and visualise experiment metrics. Its role is to ensure that the system knows which testbeds are available, their URLs and how to access their monitoring services. Table 5 summarises the 6G-PATH Test Repository.

Table 5: Overview of 6G-PATH Test Repository

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	6G-PATH Testbed Repository
Functions	A centralised storage system that contains information about all the registered testbeds within the 6G-PATH architecture.
Interface for the experimenters	N/A
Interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	REST API (GET) /testbeds/{id} – retrieves list of testbeds authenticated user has access to
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	User ID
Output/postcondition	Testbed list and details (URLs)
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

These components work seamlessly to allow users to securely access and experiment on 6G-PATH testbeds while ensuring proper authentication, authorisation and resource management.

3.2 Experiment Lifecycle Manager

The ELCM (Experiment Life Cycle Manager) is a “key” component of the experimentation framework designed to manage the life cycle of experiments conducted on the 5G network infrastructure. It handles experiments’ orchestration, deployment, monitoring and termination, ensuring efficient and automated processes. The ELCM provides users with tools to define and execute experiments, collect and analyse results, and iterate on experimental setups, facilitating advanced research and testing in 5G and beyond technologies. Figure 6 shows the positioning of ELCM in the 6G-PATH deployment, and Table 6 and Table 7 summarise the ELCM and its portal respectively. Further details are provided in Appendix 1.

Figure 6: Positioning of ELCM in 6G-PATH framework

The ELCM provides a RESTful API to initiate, cancel and retrieve the experiment's status, among other actions. The complete list of end-points available is described in [7]. However, this interface is more oriented to automation or integration with other tools. Experimenters can use a Web Portal to define the experiments.

The ELCM is oriented to the execution of Test Cases, in different scenarios, and may involve the usage of different user equipment. The ELCM Portal, as shown in Figure 7, provides a straightforward interface to choose the test case or the test cases.

The Portal lists the test cases available, the scenarios, and the User Equipment (UE). The user chooses a combination of these and the Portal sends an Experiment Descriptor to the ELCM which contains the selected parameters. In the ELCM, the test cases will be associated with a [.yaml] file that implements the selected test case with the general task available and a description in [3].

If the selection includes more than one test case, they will be executed one after the other. If the selection also includes more than one scenario the ELCM will execute all the possible combinations of the test cases and the scenarios.

Figure 7: ELCM Portal

Ultimately, the tasks involve communication with the resources available in the trial network. For example, the monitoring probes available in the testbed must be initiated, so the test case should include tasks that configure and start each of the probes required in the test case. For this, an associated plugin that exposes the configuration and control interface of the resources is needed.

Table 6: Overview of 6G-PATH ELCM

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	ELCM
Functions	<p>(POST) /api/v0/Run: Experiment descriptor in JSON¹² format. Return the ID of the experiment</p> <p>(GET) /execution/<id>/cancel: Cancel the experiment <id></p> <p>(GET) /execution/<id>/descriptor: Retrieve the experiment descriptor in JSON format of the experiment <id></p> <p>(GET) /execution/<id>/logs: Retrieve the logs of the experiment with <id></p> <p>(GET) /facility/testcases: Retrieve the list of Test Cases available for a particular user</p> <p>(GET) /facility/eus: Retrieve the list of devices available for a particular user</p> <p>(GET) /facility/scenarios: Retrieve the lists of scenarios available for a particular user</p>

¹² JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) is a standard text-based format for representing structured data based on JavaScript object syntax. It is commonly used for transmitting data in web applications (e.g., sending some data from the server to the client, so it can be displayed on a web page or vice versa). For further information also see: <https://www.json.org/json-en.html>

Interface with the Portal	REST interface for the Portal
Interface with testbed components	Specific task developed for the communication with the components of the testbed
Management protocol	Web management interface
Input data for action	Experiment descriptor, Experiment ID
Output/postcondition	Control of the execution of the experiments
Applicability of open source projects	Open Source: https://gitlab.com/morse-uma/elcm
Relation to SDOs	Implementation based on ETSI TR 103 761
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5GENESIS ¹³

Table 7: Overview of 6G-PATH ELCM Portal

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	ELCM Portal
Functions	Definition of experiments, access to raw results and Grafana dashboard
Interface for the experimenters	Web
Interface with ELCM	REST API
Management protocol	Local configuration
Input data for action	Web interface
Output/postcondition	
Applicability of open source projects	Open Source: https://gitlab.com/morse-uma/elcm-portal
Relation to SDOs	Implementation based on ETSI TR 103 761
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5GENESIS

¹³ 5GENESIS (5th Generation End-to-end Network, Experimentation, System Integration and Showcasing) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.815178, <https://5genesis.eu/>

3.3 Monitoring and Analytics

This section presents key sensors/probes for monitoring purposes in the architecture.

3.3.1 Common Monitoring tools

The 6G-PATH framework includes measurement agents based on iPerf and Ping. Tables 8, 9 and 10 summarise the iPerf for different devices.

iPerf is a widely-used network testing tool that measures bandwidth, jitter and packet loss between two end-points. The iPerf agents included in the 6G-PATH framework enable assessing the performance of the 5G configuration used during the testing and trial of the use cases. The iPerf agent is typically implemented as a client-server architecture. The iPerf client initiates the tests and the iPerf server responds to these tests. The agent can be deployed on various nodes within the 5G infrastructure to measure performance between different points in the network. The “key” features of the iPerf agent include: 1) automated performance testing: the iPerf agent automates the execution of iPerf tests across the 5G infrastructure, allowing consistent and repeatable performance measurements; 2) supporting iPerf2; 3) allowing automated customisation of various iPerf parameters, such as the duration of the test, the number of parallel connections, the protocol (TCP or UDP) and the bandwidth limits; 4) the automated collection of a wide range of network performance metrics, including throughput, packet loss, jitter and latency; 5) providing detailed logs and results that can be analysed to evaluate the performance of the network under different conditions. There are two versions of the iPerf agent, one for Android (<https://github.com/6G-SANDBOX/OpenTAP.AdbAgents>) and one for Windows (https://github.com/5genesis/Remote_iPerf_agent). The agents expose a control interface (potentially RESTful APIs or command-line interfaces) that allows the 5GENESIS Experimentation Suite to start, stop and configure iPerf tests. Documentation of the agents’ usage is included in the GitHub repositories. **Ping** is based on the ping network diagnostic tool that enables the testing of round-trip time. Two versions are also provided, for Linux [8] and for Android [9].

Table 8: Overview of Monitoring (iPerf Agent for PC component)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Monitoring (iPerf Agent for PC)
Functions	<p>/lperf (POST): Executes the iPerf process with the specific parameters in the request body in JSON format. Returns a JSON reporting the success of execution and a message.</p> <p>/lperf/<pathParameters>: Executes the iPerf process with the specific parameters. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the command execution and a message.</p> <p>/Close: Closes iPerf process. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the process closure and a message.</p> <p>/LastRawResult: Retrieve the results of the previous execution. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the retrieval, a message and a list of Results (full line).</p> <p>/LastJsonResult: Retrieve the results of the previous execution. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the retrieval, a message and a list of Results (dictionary)</p>

with parsed results).

/LastError: Retrieve the errors of the last execution. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the retrieval and a message informing of the error.

/StartDateTime: Retrieve the date and time of the last execution. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the retrieval, a message and a list of Errors.

/IsRunning: Check if there is another execution running. Returns a JSON reporting the success of the check and a message informing if is running or not.

Interface with ELCM	REST API
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	IPerf2 tool parameters
Output/postcondition	Measurements and traffic generation
Applicability of open source projects	Base on iPerf2
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5GENESIS

Table 9: Overview of Monitoring (iPerf Agent for Android component)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Monitoring (iPerf Agent Android)
Functions	com.uma.iperf.CLIENTSTART(Requires iperf client configuration parameters) com.uma.iperf.SERVERSTART(Requires iperf server configuration parameters) com.uma.iperf.CLIENTSTOP com.uma.iperf.SERVERSTOP
Interface with ELCM	OpenTAP ¹⁴ (Test Automation Interface) plugin
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	IPerf2 tool parameters
Output/postcondition	Measurements and traffic generation
Applicability of open source projects	Base on iPerf2

¹⁴ OpenTAP is an open source project for test automation. Further details can be found at: <https://opentap.io/>

Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5GENESIS

Table 10: Overview of Monitoring (Ping client for Android component)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Monitoring (Ping Agent Android)
Functions	com.uma.ping.START (Requires parameters) com.uma.ping.STOP
Interface with ELCM	OpenTAP (Test Automation Interface) plugin
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	ping tool parameters
Output/postcondition	Measurements and traffic generation
Applicability of open source projects	Base on the Ping tool
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5GENESIS

3.3.2 Additional Monitoring Tools

In addition to the common monitoring tools, individual testbeds may deploy use case-specific monitoring tools. Table 11 shows a representative example of such a monitoring tool for the use case of Smart Cities – Automated Logistics.

Table 11: Overview of Monitoring (ACTA/Viavi for UC-CITIES-2-Automated Logistics)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Monitoring (Viavi NITRO SW platform ¹⁵ (FUSION application ¹⁶))
Functions	Fusion Controller Fusion ESAM to manage Smart SFPs: JMEPs Fusion Analytics vPMA for TWAMP initiation

¹⁵ The VIAVI Network Integrated Test, Real-time analytics and Optimisation (NITRO) solution is the first real-time intelligence platform that connects testing and service activation data from instruments with software-based planning, provisioning, assurance and optimisation probes and applications, working seamlessly across mobile, fiber, cable, cloud and enterprise networks. For further information also see: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/solutions/nitro>

¹⁶ For further information also see: <https://www.oracle.com/applications/>

	Hardware probes JMEP Smart SFP ¹⁷
Interface with ELCM	KAFKA
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	via application GUI
Output/postcondition	Measurements and traffic generation
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	5G-TOURS ¹⁸ , 5G-HEART ¹⁹

3.3.3 Monitoring Databases

The measurements collected during the testing are stored in an Influx database with the same Execution ID. InfluxDB²⁰ is one of the most popular solutions for a purpose-built time series database. The content of the database is not predefined, as it depends on the use case under test. The data is organised into measurements, tags and fields. A measurement is a collection of related data points. Tags are indexed key-value pairs that are used to store metadata. Fields are key-value pairs that store the actual data values. Fields are not indexed and are typically used for storing metrics. Each data point in InfluxDB includes a timestamp, which is used to track when the data was collected. Timestamps are automatically indexed. There is only a mandatory tag, the Execution ID. Table 12 summarises the Monitoring Database using InfluxDB as a representative implementation example.

Table 12: Overview of Monitoring Database (InfluxDB component)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Monitoring Database (InfluxDB)
Functions	InfluxDB HTTP API
Interface with ELCM	OpenTAP (Test Automation Platform) plugin Task CsvToInflux Task Prometheus

¹⁷ For further information also see, *inter-alia*: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/products/fusion-jmep>

¹⁸ 5G-TOURS (SmarT mObility, media and e-health for toURists and citizenS) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.856950, <http://5gtours.eu/>

¹⁹ 5G-HEART (5G Health, Aquaculture and Transport validation trials) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.857034, <https://5gheart.org/>

²⁰ InfluxDB is an open-source time series database (TSDB) developed by the company InfluxData. It is used for storage and retrieval of time series data in fields such as operations monitoring, application metrics, Internet of Things sensor data and real-time analytics. More details can be found at: <https://www.influxdata.com/>

	Task Kafka Task MQTT
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	Field (data) and tags (metadata)
Output/postcondition	Time-series database
Applicability of open source projects	InfluxDB is an open-source time series database (TSDB) developed by the company InfluxData.
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.3.4 Analytics

The **Analytics** will follow a decentralised approach, where each testbed is responsible for independent deploying the required dashboard modules. To ensure consistency, each testbed owner must follow the detailed deployment instructions. The Analytics collects data and calculates KPIs (and/or KVIs if applicable). The Analytics will retrieve data from each testbed's 6G-PATH Monitoring Database (e.g., InfluxDB), calculating KPIs/KVIs based on the Experiment ID provided by the ELCM. The Experiment ID, supplied by the ELCM, allows users to select KPIs associated with specific testbed experiments they are authorised to access.

The front-end of the Analytics is a dashboard for data visualisation, which will graphically render the KPIs/KVIs and experiment metrics. This dashboard will allow users to interactively select KPIs/KVIs and visualise data from the experiments they conducted. The Analytics dashboard will be seamlessly integrated with the 6G-PATH Northbound Interface, ensuring that users can only access and visualise data from the testbeds they are authorised to use, as verified by the AAA component.

Each testbed will maintain its own Monitoring Database for storing the experiment data, which will be retrieved by the Analytics for KPI/KVI calculation and visualisation purposes. While the data collected will vary across testbeds, the information will follow a standardised structure, ensuring consistency and interoperability in storing and visualising the data. Although certain testbeds will offer unique metrics based on their specific infrastructure, there will also be a set of common KPIs/KVIs across all testbeds. This unified data structure will be formalised to streamline the querying, calculation and visualisation processes, enabling a coherent user experience across the 6G-PATH testbed ecosystem. Table 13 summarises the Analytics component.

Table 13: Overview of Analytics

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Analytics
Functions	Data visualisation and analytics. Graphically render the KPIs/KVIs and experiment metrics.
Interface for the experimenters	Front-end component, Web
Interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	REST API
Interface with Analytics Module Middleware	REST API
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	Username, password, Experiment ID
Output/postcondition	Experiment KPIs/KVIs
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.3.5 Use Case Image Repository

The Use Case Image Repository, as summarised in Table 14, is a “key” component in the 6G-PATH experimentation framework, designed to manage and store use case images required for experiments across various 6G testbeds. This repository ensures that the required use case images (such as services, applications or tools) are available to the 6G-PATH Experiment Lifecycle Manager (ELCM) for deployment on the testbeds. Each testbed will have a different configuration and set of features, making the repository central to ensuring a seamless, standardised deployment across diverse environments.

GitLab²¹ serves as the central platform for managing the lifecycle of the use case images and experiments. Users can interact with GitLab via the UI and the Git CLI for direct version control. GitLab’s CI/CD pipeline facilitates image deployment automation. Once changes are pushed to the repository, the pipeline automatically builds the

²¹ GitLab is a web-based Git repository that provides free open and private repositories, issue-following capabilities, and wikis. It is a complete DevOps platform that enables professionals to perform all the tasks in a project, from project planning and source code management to monitoring and security. For further information also see: <https://about.gitlab.com/>

images, runs validation checks, and, if successful, pushes them to the centralised 6G-PATH Use Case Image Repository. From here, the ELCM can be triggered to deploy the images onto the appropriate testbed for further experimentation. GitLab’s pipeline can also be configured to run specific test scripts, allowing the evaluation of image performance and functionality before deployment.

Table 14: Overview of Use Case Image Repository

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Use Case Image Repository
Functions	Central project repository for storing development images
Interface for the experimenters	Gitlab, Front-end UI + Git CLI
Interface with 6G-PATH Northbound Interface/API	N/A
Management protocol	Git
Input data for action	Username/email, password/SSH
Output/postcondition	N/A
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4 Advanced Experimentation Features

In addition to the above essential features for the 6G-PATH platform, several advanced experimentation features have been identified and specified below.

3.4.1 AI as-a-Service

The 6G-PATH project will build Artificial Intelligence (AI) as-a-Service (AlaaS) to help “meet” the diverse needs of different business application scenarios, including smart cities, education, health and farming use cases. Networks produce data that can be provided to external entities or consumed internally, enabling insights for triggering actions. The relationship between network and service can go beyond using over-the-top (OTT) resources. The interaction can be gained from sharing data that can be used to manage each domain better. Predictive infrastructure management allows mechanisms to be implemented to enable closed-loop (CL) network automation and the evolution of services that require infrastructure statistics and predictions to support dynamic-based high-quality demands. Artificial Intelligence functionalities can be offered as-a-service to support enhanced analytics.

3.4.1.1 KAU Testbed

As part of the advanced experimentation features of the 6G-PATH reference architecture, the project plans to design, implement and test AlaaS capabilities in the KAU testbed. This component will make it possible to leverage Machine Learning (ML) and AI-based analytics, such as outlier/anomaly detection and Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE) modelling, prediction and forecasting, which can be used for network planning, (re-)configuration, troubleshooting and in-depth performance analysis. Table 15 summarises the AlaaS in the KAU testbed.

By considering the trade-off between the availability of computational resources in the Cloud-Edge continuum and service latency requirements, we are designing a microservice-based AlaaS component where several microservices (i.e., Python-based code encapsulated in Docker containers) are interconnected and can be deployed in a distributed manner over the Cloud-Edge continuum, ultimately providing self-contained functionalities (e.g., one microservice for data processing deployed at the Edge, one microservice for KPI modelling deployed in the Cloud and so on). Such a microservice-based architecture adds further flexibility, since AlaaS functions can be instantiated across the underlying infrastructure and can be initiated, reconfigured, moved and terminated on demand.

Table 15: Overview of AI as-a-Service in KAU testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	AI as-a-Service (KAU)
Functions	<p>Post-experiment descriptive, diagnostic and predictive functionalities, including:</p> <p>Measurement post-processing (e.g., time series synchronisation and outlier/anomaly detection)</p> <p>Experiment statistics</p> <p>Feature correlation and feature importance analyses (e.g, via linear correlation matrix and ML-based feature selection algorithms)</p> <p>QoS/QoE modelling (e.g., via neural network training)</p> <p>QoS/QoE classification and prediction (e.g., via Random Forest²² classifier/regressor)</p> <p>QoS/QoE time-series forecasting (e.g., via LSTM²³)</p>
Interface with Monitoring Databases	Interfaces with InfluxDB via REST APIs
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	Experimental data as collected by the monitoring probes (instructed by the ELCM) and stored in InfluxDB

²² Random Forest is a famous machine learning algorithm that uses supervised learning methods. It can be applied it to both classification and regression problems. It is based on ensemble learning, which integrates multiple classifiers to solve a complex issue and increases the model's performance. For further information also see, *inter-alia*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Random_forest

²³ A Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM) is a type of deep neural network that is designed to capture historical information of time series data and is suitable for predicting long-term nonlinear series. Also see, *for example*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Long_short-term_memory

Output/postcondition	Presentation of the results from the analyses carried out via the methods listed in “Functions” (e.g., report / visualisation in a web interface through REST API calls.)
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.1.2 ALB Testbed

The AlaaS advanced feature will also be available in the ALB testbed, based on the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) as the functional entity standardised in the 3GPP TS 29.520 specification [10]. 3GPP proposes that the NWDAF provide analytical information to authorised entities.

The “key” concept is to share descriptive statistics of past events and prediction information of future states. NWDAF gathers data from different infrastructure entities and provides analytics in subscription & notification mode to interested applications and network functions. Although the interfaces are getting normalised, the algorithms and models are scenario-dependent. *Figure 8* shows this NWDAF-based AlaaS approach.

NWDAF can also be extended to support analytics functions for third-party services. A Service and Network Data Analytical Function (SNWDAF) capability can be available in a Cloud-based model. Under the 6G-PATH project, we aim to build AI-based models to create top-level services, answering the need for the proposed scenarios. Table 16 summarises the AlaaS in the ALB testbed.

Figure 8: Service and network data analytics function offered as-a-service

Table 16: Overview of AI as-a-Service in ALB testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	AI as Service
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • POST: create prediction action

- PUT: update prediction action
- DELETE: delete prediction action

Interface with Monitoring	Elasticsearch API, Prometheus API, Kafka API
Interface with Slice Manager	REST API
Management protocol	REST API
Input data for action	Monitoring data
Output/postcondition	Prediction of network issues
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.2 Security as-a-Service

3.4.2.1 UMA Testbed

The UMA testbed includes a CAPIF (Common API Framework for Telco) [11] Core Function instance to manage the exposure of APIs for Security as-a-Service, as summarised in Table 17. CAPIF is the API Framework defined by 3GPP SA6 in TS 29.222, TS 23.222 and TS 33.122. This API framework defines the capabilities to manage API exposure from 5G Networks as deployed in the UMA testbed. The CAPIF implementation used is based on OpenCAPIF [12], a new ETSI Software Development Group (SDG) created in 2024. The CAPIF standardises and simplifies the integration of telecommunications services through a unified and secure API framework. It provides a consistent interface for accessing various network resources, reducing complexity for developers and accelerating the deployment of new applications. CAPIF fosters innovation and collaboration within the telecommunications industry by promoting interoperability between network operators and service providers. This initiative supports the sector's digital transformation, enabling the delivery of more advanced and reliable services to consumers and businesses. More details of this approach can be found in Appendix 2.

Table 17: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in UMA Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Security-as-a-Service (CAPIF)

Functions	Integration of telecommunications services through a unified and secure API framework, including the following API framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Invoker management API - Provider management API - Discover API - Publish API - Events API - Security API - Logging/Auditing API - Access control policy API - Routing Info API
Interfaces with third parties	Interfaces with third parties exposing or consuming services through REST APIs
Management protocol	REST APIs
Input data for action	Onboarding as an invoker/service provider
Output/postcondition	Access to requested API/ Service
Applicability of open source projects	Integrated with Open5GS
Relation to SDOs	ETSI OpenCAPIF SDG, 3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	EU EVOLVED-5G ²⁴ , EU 6G-SANDBOX ²⁵ , EU IMAGINE B5G ²⁶ , EU 6G-PATH ²⁷ , EU FIDAL ²⁸

3.4.2.2 IT Testbed

In the IT testbed, the Security-as-a-Service is implanted via the S&P Platform, as summarised in Table 18. It is based on the EU FiWARE proposal [13] of information integration and secure data management for applications in Smart Cities. The security-by-design mechanisms of the S&P Platform provide different features to guarantee that the data of IoT objects/devices are accessed only by those ICT services having the proper authorisation. In particular, the integrated security-by-design mechanisms include a privacy-preserving identity management

²⁴ EVOLVED-5G (Experimentation and Validation Openness for Long-term evolution of Vertical inDustries in 5G era and beyond) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.101016608, <https://evolved-5g.eu/>

²⁵ 6G-SANDBOX (Supporting Architectural and technological Network evolutions through an intelligent, Secured and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation facility) HE SNS-JU project, Grant Agreement No.101096328, <https://6g-sandbox.eu/>

²⁶ Imagine B5G (Imagine Beyond 5G) HE SNS-JU project, Grant Agreement No.101096452, <https://imagineb5g.eu/>

²⁷ 6G-PATH (6G Pilots and Trials Through Europe) HE SNS-JU project, Grant Agreement No.101139172, <https://6gpath.eu/>

²⁸ FIDAL (Field Trials beyond 5G) HE SNS-JU project, Grant Agreement No.101096146, <https://fidal-he.eu/>

solution based on the KeyRock approach [14] for the Identity Manager framework and EAP²⁹ authentication; a modelling language based on XACML (eXtensible Access Control Markup Language) is used to specify access control policies to the S&P Platform using the properties of Data providers or consumers; a distributed access control model based on capabilities tokens (DCapBAC³⁰) is provided to manage the authorisation access, mainly composed by Policy Administration Point (PAP), Policy Decision Point (PDP), Policy Enforcement Point (PEP), and an optimised Elliptic Curve Cryptography (ECC) for signing and validating distributed tokens between the S&P Platform and external entities (i.e., constrained IoT devices and ICT services).

Table 18: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in IT Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Security-as-a-Service (S&P Platform)
Functions	Security and privacy to data, anonymised identity management, authentication and entity registration, security policies management, authorisation and access control.
Interface with ELCM	REST API
Management protocol	Definition of Data providers/consumers and access policies by the S&P Platform Administrator
Input data for action	XACML Policies
Output/postcondition	Post/access data, protect data
Applicability of open source projects	Based on FIWARE
Relation to SDOs	ETSI NGSI-LD APIs (REST/JSON-LD)
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	PRECEPT (https://www.precept-project.eu/)

²⁹ Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP) is an authentication framework frequently used in network and internet connections. It is defined in RFC 3748, which made RFC 2284 obsolete, and is updated by RFC 5247. EAP is an authentication framework for providing the transport and usage of material and parameters generated by EAP methods. Also see, among others: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Extensible_Authentication_Protocol

³⁰ For further details also see, for example: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/271202925_DCapBAC_Embedding_Authorization_logic_into_Smart_Things_through_ECC_optimizations

3.4.2.3 FOKUS Testbed

In the FOKUS testbed, Security-as-a-Service is implemented in a Security Gateway, as summarised in Table 19. The Security Gateway enables the integration of Edge nodes and central components of a distributed 5G system, having the Edge node deployed at the use case premise and the centralised node deployed in Fraunhofer FOKUS premises. This enables centralised management of the users and policies for all the edges. This allows scalability and upgrades without being onsite.

Table 19: Overview of Security-as-a-Service in FOKUS Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Security-as-a-Service (Security Gateway)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add – Add new configuration for an Edge node to be connected • List – List the already connected Node • Remove – Remove a given Edge node
Interface	N/A
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	Edge Name, IP (Optional)
Output/postcondition	Establishment of secure connectivity between Edge components and the centralised components of the 5G System
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	FUDGE-5G ³¹ , 5G-VINNI ³²

3.4.3 Policy Enforcer

3.4.3.1 IT Testbed

In the IT testbed, the Policy Enforcer summarised in Table 20 is implemented through the ONEmNEF (OneSource's Microservice-based Network Exposure Function), which is a critical component designed to enable secure and efficient interaction between external AFs (Application Functions) and the 5GC (5G Core). Built on a microservice-based architecture, ONEmNEF provides a scalable, flexible and modular solution that aligns with 3GPP standards, particularly Releases 16 and 17. This architecture allows seamless integration into Cloud-native

³¹ FUDGE-5G (Fully Disintegrated private nEtworks for 5G verticals) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.957242, <https://fudge-5g.eu/en>

³² 5G-VINNI (5G Verticals Innovation Infrastructure) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.815279, <https://www.5g-vinni.eu/>

environments, supporting dynamic orchestration and ensuring that various network services and data are securely exposed to authorised third-party applications.

In addition to its network exposure capabilities, ONEmNEF is a policy enforcer, ensuring that AFs adhere to the network's predefined policies during their interactions with the 5GC. Its advanced features, including Event Monitoring, QoS Control, Traffic Influence and Analytics Exposure, allow AFs to subscribe to network events, manage QoS settings, influence traffic routing and receive analytics-based notifications, all while enforcing policy compliance. These features make ONEmNEF a crucial component in the IT testbed, enhancing its capabilities for secure, policy-driven and intelligent network experimentation across layers.

Table 20: Overview of Policy Enforcer in ONE Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Policy Enforcer (ONEmNEF)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event Monitoring: Facilitates subscription to network events. • QoS Control: Manages AF requests for session creation with specified QoS parameters. • Traffic Influence: Allows AFs to influence traffic based on specific criteria. • Analytics Exposure: Enables AFs to subscribe to analytic events.
Interface with external AFs	Interfaces with external AFs (e.g. ELCM) through its northbound APIs (based on 3GPP NEF standards) Protocol: JSON over HTTP2 ³³
Interface with 5G Core	Interfaces with the 5GC through its southbound APIs Protocol: JSON over HTTP2
Interface with Security-as-a-Service	Interfaces with the CAPIF through its APIs Protocol: JSON over HTTP2
Management protocol	NA
Input data for action	(based on 3GPP NEF standards) Event Monitoring: AF requests containing event subscription details. QoS Control: AF requests with QoS parameters for session management. Traffic Influence: Payloads specifying traffic conditions or user data. Analytics Exposure: AF requests specifying analytic events of interest.
Output/postcondition	(based on 3GPP NEF standards) Event Monitoring: Monitoring event notifications sent to the AF. QoS Control: Response with session creation details or error messages. Traffic Influence: Created or modified traffic influence subscriptions. Analytics Exposure: Notifications containing analytics data.
Applicability of open	Integrated with OpenCAPIF and Open5GS.

³³ HTTP/2 is a major revision of the HTTP network protocol used by the World Wide Web. Also see, *among others*: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/HTTP/2>

source projects	
Relation to SDOs	3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	FUDGE-5G

3.4.3.2 FOKUS Testbed

The Policy Enforcer is a network-side component responsible for controlling the data path end point of a UE. The Policy Enforcer in the FOKUS testbed is summarised in Table 21. The actions are performed by using the Traffic Influence API [15] defined by 3GPP/ETSI as northbound API for NEF (Network Exposure Function). The action from the Policy Enforcer will push new data path rules to UPF for changing the gateway UPF when the creation subscription is called.

Table 21: Overview of Policy Enforcer in FOKUS Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Policy Enforcer
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create subscription -> Create a subscription to request path change for a given UE by specifying its IP address, data network access identifier and ID • Delete subscription -> Delete a subscription based on the subscription ID • List subscription -> Get a list of subscriptions
Interface with ELCM	JSON-RPC interface exposing northbound API to ELCM for initiating actions
Management protocol	HTTP-JSON
Input data for action	UE IP, Data network access identifier, ID for the request
Output/postcondition	Data-path change in the UPF topology
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	3GPP/ETSI Traffic Influence API to be reused
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.4 Slice Manager

3.4.4.1 UWS Testbed

The Slice Manager at UWS focuses on network slicing over the data plane of a beyond 5G (towards 6G network) infrastructure. It largely leverages and adapts the network slicing approach from the EU 6G BRAINS project [16].

Work is ongoing to adapt the 6G BRAINS solution to the architecture defined in 6G-PATH, especially the interfacing with ELCM (for triggering network slicing operations) and the Monitoring (for being aware of the network data plane topology) components. The overview of this component is presented in Table 22.

The Slice Manager is centred on a Slice Control Agent architecture, which supports intent-based network slice control and management in the northbound interface, and technology-agnostic enforcement of network slicing operations in the southbound interface. The southbound interface further facilitates the integration of heterogeneous technology-specific controllers over the various network segments along the End-to-End (E2E) data plane. Example controllers may include Radio Access Network (RAN) controllers such as FlexRAN or FlexRIC from the OpenAirInterface [17] and Mosaic5G [18] projects, and non-RAN (Edge, Transport network and Core network) controllers such as Traffic Control (TC) in Linux, Open Virtual Switch (OVS) based on the OVS project [19] or other mechanisms exploring programmable data plane technologies. Such controllers typically need to employ advanced 6G network traffic-aware packet inspection for classifying the traffic and corresponding advanced actuation capabilities to allow traffic engineering to create network slices (including assigning the classified flows to the created slices) on demand to meet the diverse QoS requirements of different applications.

Table 22: Overview of Slice Manager in UWS Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Slice Manager (Data Plane Programmability)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <code>bool createe2eslice()</code> -> Enforce the flow priority along the different network segments to achieve an E2E network slice definition. Each segment will return True or False when the segment slice is created. • <code>bool assignFlowToe2eslice()</code> -> Attach a flow to a given network slice that has already been created. Each segment will return True or False when the flow is attached. • <code>bool removeFlowToe2eslice()</code> -> Detach a flow from a given network slice that has already been created and attached. Each segment will return True or False when the flow is detached.
Interface with ELCM	ELCM to trigger slice control functions (slicing creation, attachment and detachment) Protocol: JSON over RabbitMQ ³⁴
Interface with Monitoring	Monitoring Databases to receive topologies Protocol: JSON over RabbitMQ
Management protocol	Management protocol performed through the exposed functions in the interface with component A
Input data for action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slice requirements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Min Warrantied Bandwidth ○ Max Available Bandwidth ○ Priority • Flow(s) specifications:

³⁴ RabbitMQ is a reliable and mature messaging and streaming broker, which is easy to deploy on cloud environments, on-premises, and on a local machine. It is currently used by millions worldwide. For further relevant information also see: <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

- FlowId (it can be a composition of flows)
- Flow network fields (IP, MAC, port, etc.)
- SliceId

Output/postcondition	Topology-aware network slicing over the data plane
Applicability of open source projects	OpenAirInterface, Mosaic5G, TC, OVS
Relation to SDOs	ITU-T etc.
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	EU 6G BRAINS ³⁵

3.4.4.2 UMA Testbed

UMA is developing a Slice Manager, as defined in Table 23, based on the NaC (Network as-a-Code) tool from Nokia, which also uses the slicing aware feature offered by the RAN from Nokia. The slicing aware feature enables configuring the weight of the slices. This feature will dynamically change the resources assigned to the different slices configured in the network.

Table 23: Overview of Slice Manager in UMA Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Slice Manager (NaC)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Api.Slices.get: List the created slices for the indicated site. • Api.Imsis_get: List of recorded individual IMSIs (among the ranges assigned to the user) • Api.Imsis_list: List of IMSIs assigned to slice (among the ranges assigned to the user) • Api.QoS_profiles(imsi): Get QoS profiles configured for the user • Api.Imsis_deregister: Deregister IMSI from the slice • Api.Imsis_register_qos: Register IMSIs to QoS profiles (slice sessions) • Api.Radio_status: Radio status
Interface with ELCM	The task in the ELCM to configure the slice
Management protocol	Management protocol performed through the exposed functions in the interface with component A
Input data for action	IMSIs, DNN, QoSProfiles

³⁵ 6G BRAINS (Bring Reinforcement-learning Into Radio Light Network for Massive Connections) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.101017226, <https://6g-brains.eu/>

Output/postcondition	Slices configuration
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.4.3 OTE Testbed

OTE's Slice Manager, as defined in Table 24, is a component designed to manage 5G Core's pre-defined slices. With the absence of the NEF, the challenge of providing a reliable slicing mechanism had to be met. Therefore, the Slice Manager component was designed, to play the role of both the translator and a security node.

As a translator, Slice Manager allows an external component, such as 6G-PATH platform, to communicate with the Packet Core, exchanging messages and fulfilling requests. At the same time, it increases the security level as a security note, since it does not allow an external component to be interconnected directly to the network.

Table 24: Overview of Slice Manager in OTE Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Slice Manager (B5G Network Slicing)
Functions	<p>Methods supported are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • POST: create slices • PUT: update slices • DELETE: delete slices
Interface with other components	JSON
Management protocol	N/A
Input data for action	<p>Methods (post, put, delete) are configured in Slice Manager, so that it can communicate with 5GC. Slices ID is sent back to the slice manager with the following format:</p> <pre> "slicId": "EMBB", "expDataRateUL": 65, "expDataRateDL": 1000, "userDensity": 10, "userSpeed": 80, </pre>

	<pre> "sliceId": "URLLC", "latency": 5, "jitter": 1, "expDataRateUL": 65, "expDataRateDL": 70 </pre>
Output/postcondition	HTTP messages of successful action operation
Applicability of open source projects	N/A
Relation to SDOs	3GPP, ETSI
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	VITAL-5G ³⁶ , 5G-INDUCE ³⁷

3.4.4.4 FOKUS Testbed

The Slice Manager at the FOKUS testbed is a pivotal component of 5G Core deployment, enabling redirection of the UEs to specify network slices without the involvement of user equipment, as defined in Table 25. The user-based control provides the granularity of selecting and assigning users to a required network slice.

Table 25: Overview of Slice Manager in FOKUS Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Slice Manager (Slice Assignment to UE)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • assign - > Assign a given UE to a requested slice • unassign - > Unassign a given UE from the assigned slice
Interface with ELCM	ELCM triggers an action to set UE to an already deployed slice of the 5G network.
Management protocol	HTTP-JSON
Input data for action	IMSI, network slice details: SST (Slice/Service Type), SD (Slice Differentiator)
Output/postcondition	UE will be redirected to a new slice when it re-registers in the network
Applicability of open source projects	N/A

³⁶ VITAL-5G (Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.101016567, <https://www.vital5g.eu/>

³⁷ 5G-INDUCE (Open cooperative 5G experimentation platforms for the industrial sector Network Applications) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.101016941, <https://www.5g-induce.eu/>

Relation to SDOs	N/A
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.4.5 ALB Testbed

The Slice Manager at the ALB testbed is the component responsible for managing the 5G end-to-end network slicing in the network, as defined in Table 26. This component receives data with requirements from the ELCM and creates/updates/deletes the slices in the RAN and the CORE on demand. This component can also receive information from monitoring tools or the AlaaS, which will trigger reconfigurations of the slices in the network.

Table 26: Overview of Slice Manager in ALB Testbed

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Slice Manager (B5G Network Slicing)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • POST: create slices • PUT: update slices • DELETE: delete slices
Interface with ELCM	ELCM API/Kafka
Interface with AlaaS	REST API
Interface with srsRAN	srsRAN API
Interface with Open5GS	Open5GS API
Management protocol	REST API
Input data for action	Service Owner, IMSIs, DNN, QoSProfiles, Location
Output/postcondition	Slices configuration
Applicability of open source projects	srsRAN, Open5GS
Relation to SDOs	3GPP
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	N/A

3.4.5 Closed Loop Coordinator

Closed Loops refer to automated processes/systems where data is continuously collected, analysed and acted upon in near-real-time to optimise processes, decisions or outcomes. In the context of the 6G-PATH project, closed loops may involve automated decision-making systems, feedback control mechanisms or machine learning algorithms that adjust parameters dynamically based on monitored data. Closed-loop mechanisms are essential across various domains, such as telecommunications, industrial automation and intelligent infrastructure, to maintain performance, prevent failures and optimise resource allocation in volatile environments. The rise of AI-driven technologies has further raised the notion of closed-loop systems for replacing human intervention in (error-prone) complex tasks which require timely intervention, enabling more intelligent predictions and faster responses to changes [20], [21]. Indeed, in 6G, closed-loop systems are typically referred to as a cornerstone in network autonomy. Closed-loop systems are expected to enable close-to real-time orchestration of network resources, dynamically adjusting to service demands, network conditions and environmental factors [20], [22]. Several 6G features can benefit from such automation. For instance, in network slicing, where virtual network slices are dynamically allocated for different services, each with unique performance requirements, closed loops can be leveraged to manage these slices, ensuring timely resource optimisation and real-time adjustments based on ongoing performance metrics like latency, bandwidth and throughput. For example, a slice dedicated to autonomous vehicles must respond instantly to any network performance degradation to ensure safety. In contrast, slices for enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB) may prioritise bandwidth allocation during periods of high demand. Similarly, Edge computing might rely on closed-loop systems in 6G to manage the Edge-to-Cloud interaction, balancing workloads between the Edge and Core networks to optimise service delivery for latency-sensitive applications such as smart cities or remote surgery ([23]).

Nevertheless, coordinating closed loops remains an open challenge due to the complexities inherent in dynamic systems, data management issues, conflict resolution requirements, algorithm limitations, security concerns and regulatory constraints.

Firstly, there is no “one-size-fits-all” approach for efficient closed loop coordination. Closed loops might assume different shapes, including: 1) simple feedback control models where sensors collect data, a controller processes the information, and actuators adjust, used in areas like network traffic management and dynamic resource scaling in Cloud environments; 2) Markov Decision Processes (MDPs) used for modelling decision-making probabilistic processes [24]; 3) Reinforcement Learning (RL) for learning optimal actions over time-based on feedback from the environment (e.g., use in dynamic resource allocation, network optimisation and energy management); 4) Digital Twin-based to simulate a digital replica of the physical system operating in parallel and to support the decision-making process.

Then, the underlying idea of coordinating closed loops predates their characterisation (i.e., ways to define their role, objectives, priorities, actuation capabilities, etc.) and the ability to resolve conflict. For example, one closed loop might prioritise bandwidth allocation for real-time applications, while another focuses on energy efficiency. Resolving these conflicting goals requires negotiation and additional decision-making mechanisms. This also means that the behaviour of one closed loop can impact others, resulting in another layer of interdependencies (and complexity). For instance, competing closed loops with differing objectives cannot fully achieve autonomy without risking a lack of coordination. This intricate negotiation process becomes even more challenging in multi-stakeholder environments, where different interests must be considered. Closed-loop coordination also faces challenges due to security and privacy concerns, including the need to protect sensitive, regulatory and standardisation issues from a lack of interoperability standards across diverse networks.

As part of our efforts in 6G-PATH to explore and achieve closed-loop coordination, the initial phase focused on characterising available closed loops (and automation tasks). The project gathered information on the closed loops deployed across multiple 6G-PATH testbeds. These represent various operational scenarios which require orchestration. We have identified three testbeds (FOKUS, ORO and IT) using closed loop-based processes as presented in Tables 27 to 30. Two testbeds (UMU and OTE) plan to have this feature, as presented in Tables 31

and 32, and two testbeds (UWS and KAU) do not use such capabilities. In the next stage, the project will work closely with testbed owners to better understand and discuss their requirements and the coordination aspects of such capabilities.

Table 27: Closed Loop Blueprint in FOKUS testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s) (FOKUS testbed)	
ID	CL-FRA-01
Description	<p>Monitoring and updating backhaul used for data path communication between Edge and central node in a multi-backhaul scenario.</p>
Data Sources and Types	<p>The data source for monitoring is the link status (with fping). Link break is detected by fping which triggers a request to SMF for path change. The path preferences are predefined in the monitoring script. When the broken link is fixed, the script triggers another path change to return to the previous/low weight link. The preference is Terrestrial, LEO and GEO in this order.</p>
Algorithms or Models Used	<p>A simple detection mechanism where a request is triggered upon fping failure.</p>
Policies or Actions	<p>Send a request to SMF to update the link used for data path communication.</p>

Table 28: Closed Loop Blueprint in IT/ALB testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s) (IT/ALB testbed)	
ID	CL-IT-01
Description	<p>A closed-loop system is used in a networking environment where the network parameters can be dynamically adjusted. The purpose is to prevent loss of connectivity, detect intrusions and maintain service quality.</p>

Data Sources and Types	<p>The closed loop utilises data sources provided by Suricata and from srsRAN and CableFree + Open5GS, such as the number of UEs by cell, bandwidth per Cell/UE, error rates during transmission, signal-to-noise ratio, network flows, protocols details, full Pcap captures and parser.</p> <p>Open5GS Core network function metrics are scraped via an HTTP server and stored in a Prometheus time-series database to be later accessed for complex analytics and processing by other software applications.</p> <p>The data is collected at frequent intervals (e.g., near real-time) through filebeat/logstash and stored in Elasticsearch. CableFree and srsRAN metrics are collected with Python scripts capable of interacting with each RAN technology and persisted in a Kafka Broker for real-time analysis and in a Mongo Database for historical processing.</p> <p>Additionally, on-board unit devices using cellular networks, contain services that generate metrics such as packet loss, jitter and bitrate, which are gathered with scripts and then published on the previously mentioned Kafka Broker and Mongo Database.</p>
Algorithms or Models Used	<p>The closed loop employs decision-making algorithms like threshold-based rules and predictive analytics models that detect anomalies.</p> <p>Machine learning techniques such as regression analysis or reinforcement learning may also predict future resource demands and trigger proactive migration.</p>
Policies or Actions	<p>When anomalies are detected, policies are triggered to mitigate the problems detected. Actions include changing the slice, applying/changing QoS profile parameters for UEs, influencing traffic routing, triggering handovers, controlling the antenna's power according to usage and isolating/detaching the UEs under attack.</p> <p>Additionally, when considering a 5G-Edge-enabled deployment, these metrics can be used to influence service orchestration on the Edge platform, by dynamically managing service instances according to the 5G platform usage (e.g., avoiding instances in the nodes that have their cellular interfaces completely overloaded).</p>

Table 29: Closed Loop Blueprint 01 in ORO testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s) (ORO testbed)	
ID	CL-ORO-01
Description	Automatic Scaling of Edge/Cloud Resources: ORO's testbed uses automated scaling of computing and network resources in the Cloud and Edge environments. The testbed also provides an Infrastructure as-a-Code approach, capable of network and application software development and implementation related to building, testing, and deploying, as well as continuous integration and continuous delivery (Jenkins and Ansible tool ³⁸).

³⁸ Jenkins is a continuous integration (CI) tool primarily used for building and testing software projects. Ansible is a configuration management and orchestration tool for automating infrastructure and application deployment, setup and administration. For further informative elements also see: <https://plugins.jenkins.io/ansible/>

	On top of the infrastructure, orchestration is enabled based on the OSM (Open Source MANO) v12/13 open-source tool, connected to the IaaS ³⁹ /CaaS ⁴⁰ managers, for VNFs and CNFs instantiation and further NF healing for VMs or CNs.
Data Sources and Types	OpenStack monitoring data includes resource usage data (vCPU, RAM, Disk, Network) and Instance-specific data (bandwidth utilisation, requests etc.).
Algorithms or Models Used	Autoscaling based on thresholds.
Policies or Actions	Resources scaling based on demand dynamics; Spinning-up of new nodes to server additional application instances or services instances.

Table 30: Closed Loop Blueprint 02 in ORO testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s) (ORO testbed)	
ID	CL-ORO-02
Description	<p>Dynamic Services Lifecycle Loop: AI driven network, the testbed implements 5G services and orchestration for slicing with conflict resolution based on 5QI (5G QoS Identifier) and QoS mapping in the end-to-end network, network orchestration, automation and proper Cloud services instantiation and placement, through the distributed and decentralised computing environments, compute continuum readiness.</p> <p>Through the dynamic services instantiation, the system places the compute resources at optimal processing in the distributed 5G Lab system to the proper Edge computing. Instantiation is supported through TMF (Tele Management Forum) APIs and interface implementation.</p>
Data Sources and Types	Monitoring data includes resource usage data (vCPU, RAM, Disk, Network) and Instance-specific data (bandwidth utilisation, requests etc.).
Algorithms or Models Used	Services instantiation, migration and deletion based on threshold and predictive forecasting.
Policies or Actions	VNFs/CNFs lifecycle is managed according to services and use case requirements; Services-specific/use case specific playbooks.

Table 31: Closed Loop Blueprint in OTE testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s) (OTE testbed)	
ID	CL-OTE-01

³⁹ Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) delivers on-demand infrastructure resources to organisations via the cloud, such as compute, storage, networking and virtualisation. Customers do not have to manage, maintain or update their own data center infrastructure, but are responsible for the operating system, middleware, virtual machines and any apps or data.

⁴⁰ Containers as a service (CaaS) delivers and manages all the hardware and software resources to develop and deploy applications using containers. Sometimes viewed as a subset or an extension of IaaS, CaaS uses containers rather than VMs as its main resource. Developers and IT operations teams can use CaaS to develop, run and manage applications without having to build and maintain the infrastructure or platform to run and manage containers. Customers still have to write the code and manage their data and applications, but the environment to build and deploy containerised apps is managed and maintained by the cloud service provider.

Description	(Planned) Closed loop system that detects poor network performance by analysing the collected network performance data (latency, throughput, packet loss) and requests slice change.
Data Sources and Types	The closed loop utilises data sources such as latency, throughput and packet loss. These data are collected from the probes installed at different points in the end-to-end infrastructure.
Algorithms or Models Used	The closed loop will use decision-making algorithms or/and AI tools (based on the final development) to identify the poor performance and request the slice change from the slice manager.
Policies or Actions	When the closed loop identifies the need for slice change, a delete and a create message will be sent to the Slice Manager. These messages will delete the user from the default slice and re-register it in a new one.

Table 32: Closed Loop Blueprint in UMA testbed

Closed Loop Blueprint(s)	
ID	CL-UMA-01
Description	(Planned) UMA plans to implement a Closed Loop Coordinator to support the Slice Manager in managing the resources assigned to the slices, as shown in Figure 9.
Data Sources and Types	The closed loop utilises data from the monitoring of the network slices.
Algorithms or Models Used	The solution focuses on implementing of a supervision module to modify the configuration of the slices in Nokia RAN equipment using the Slice-aware scheduler feature included in Nokia equipment.
Policies or Actions	The Slice Manager provides an interface for the configuration of the quality parameters of the slices and for retrieving radio status. The Closed Loop Coordinator (CLC) will use this interface to check the status and trigger dynamic reconfiguration of the parameters of the slices (Figure 10). In the ELCM, UMA plans to have a task to activate/deactivate the Closed Loop Coordinator and a task for the manual control and configuration of the slices via the Slice Manager during the execution of the experiments and trials.

Figure 9: Closed Loop Coordinator for network slicing (UMA testbed)

Figure 10: Management of network slicing [25]

Considering the above closed loops across the various testbeds, the project plans to devise a Closed Loop Coordinator in the format of a Multi-domain Infrastructure and Resource Orchestration (MIRO), as defined in Table 33.

The MIRO is a Cloud-Native framework for enhancing the management of the Edge-to-Cloud continuum. MIRO facilitates the dynamic creation and peering of Kubernetes clusters across multiple Cloud providers and automates the deployment and management of applications within these complex, multi-cluster ecosystems within an innovative solution.

MIRO lays the groundwork for effective lifecycle management, including essential service migration operations, while providing comprehensive monitoring capabilities for a multi-domain Kubernetes infrastructure.

For that, MIRO incorporates the concept of closed loops, allowing for continuous feedback and adjustment for various tasks, including the idea of more intelligent and optimised resource management.

MIRO leverages multiple algorithms to optimise application component deployment, ensuring efficiency and responsiveness. In 6G-PATH, MIRO is considered a resource management solution targeting distributed and multi-domain scenarios, capable of delivering experimentation insights (KPIs and KVs).

Table 33: Overview of Close Loop Coordinator (MIRO)

Functions and Interfaces etc.	Description
Component name	Close Loop Coordinator (MIRO)
Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamically create and peer Kubernetes clusters on top of various Cloud Providers. • Automate the deployment of applications in those multi-cluster environments. • Provide the means to optimise the application component deployment based on AI. • Provide the building blocks for enabling their lifecycle management (e.g., service migration operations) through automated closed-Loops. • Monitor a multi-domain K8s based infrastructure.
Interface for Users (Experimenters/ Infrastructure Providers)	Custom Web UI
Interface for Third-Party Integrations	HTTP REST Interfaces (documented via OpenAPI) Thanos/Prometheus (for metrics subscription)

Interface with Cloud	Cluster API (via providers)
Interface between Domains	WireGuard Links Ligo ⁴¹)
Input data for action	Applications descriptions (experiments) using TOSCA ⁴² standard and WebUI ⁴³
Output/postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application & Infrastructure deployments across multi-domain • KPI Metrics (resource-related, cluster-related, link-related, etc.)
Applicability of open source projects	Kubernetes, KOPF (Kubernetes Operator), Cluster API, Ligo, TOSCA, Prometheus/Thanos ⁴⁴ , Metallb ⁴⁵ , NGINX ⁴⁶ , Flannel ⁴⁷ , FastAPI ⁴⁸ and Grafana.
Relation to SDOs	ETSI ZSM ⁴⁹ , ETSI ENI ⁵⁰ , OASIS TOSCA
Related projects for component reuse/adaption	EU CHARITY ⁵¹

⁴¹ Ligo is an open-source project that enables dynamic and seamless Kubernetes multi-cluster topologies, supporting heterogeneous on-premise, cloud and edge infrastructures. For more informative details also see: <https://liqo.io/>

⁴² Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) is an OASIS standard language to describe a topology of cloud based web services, their components, relationships and the processes that manage them. For more informative details also see, *among others*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OASIS_TOSCA

⁴³ For more details also see: <https://webui.me/>

⁴⁴ For more details also see: <https://thanos.io/v0.10/thanos/getting-started.md/>

⁴⁵ MetallLB is a load-balancer implementation for bare metal Kubernetes clusters, using standard routing protocols. For more details also see: <https://metallb.universe.tf/>

⁴⁶ NGINX is open-source web server software used for reverse proxy, load balancing, and caching. It provides HTTPS server capabilities and is mainly designed for maximum performance and stability. For more details also see: <https://nginx.org/en/>

⁴⁷ Flannel is a basic overlay network that works by assigning a range of subnet addresses (usually IPv4 with a /24 or /16 subnet mask). An overlay network is a computer network that is built on top of another network. Also see, *among others*: <https://www.velotio.com/engineering-blog/flannel-a-network-fabric-for-containers>

⁴⁸ FastAPI is a modern, fast (high-performance), web framework for building APIs with Python based on standard Python type hints. For more details also see: <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>

⁴⁹ The ETSI ZSM (Zero-touch network and Service Management) group was formed in December 2017 with the goal to accelerate the definition of the required end-to-end architecture and solutions. More informative details can be found at: <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/zero-touch-network-service-management>

⁵⁰ ETSI ENI (Experiential Network Intelligence) focuses on improving the operator experience, using closed-loop AI mechanisms based on context-aware, metadata-driven policies. This enables the ENI system recognize and incorporate new and changed knowledge, and hence make actionable decisions. More informative details can be found at: <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/experiential-networked-intelligence>

⁵¹ CHARITY (Cloud for Holography and Augmented Reality) H2020 project, Grant Agreement No.101016509, <https://www.charity-project.eu/en>

4 Vertical Use Case Blueprints

This section contains the blueprints for the ten (-10-) Use Cases (UCs) of the 4 6G-PATH verticals. These blueprints include a detailed description of the UCs, including scenarios, key components, high-level topology, validation methodologies, expected outcomes and risk assessment. Regarding validation, an initial set of KPIs and KVI is defined, which will be refined alongside WP6 and reported in future deliverables.

4.1 Farming

4.1.1 UC-FARM-1 – Water saving

The use case aims to automate the decision-making process for irrigation by monitoring and controlling the phenology of an open avocado fruit orchard. This is located at the experimental station of La Mayora in Algarrobo Costa Malaga (Spain), using the advantages of 5G/6G technology, which means instantaneous treatment of large volumes of data to automate decision-making and diagnostic processes in real time. Thus, the main objective of the use case is to acquire and store data and monitor and control the plot of fruit trees to create a real-time information database that allows us to make decisions regarding parameters of efficient crop irrigation management. Combining plant knowledge (CSIC) with data processing (UMA) becomes essential for project's success. Figure 11 shows the overview diagram for the Use Case Farm 1.

The “Water saving” use case pursues three main goals:

1. Creating a network of (battery-powered) sensors and actuators to acquire the necessary data on the water content of the soil-plant-atmosphere continuum.
2. Test the water demands of avocado crops in situ by comparing stressed and unstressed plants, and improve the precision of irrigation.
3. Periodically monitoring the phenological state of the crop through images and videos transmitted in real-time by a drone adapted with different types of artificial vision cameras designed for agriculture.

Figure 11: Global diagram of the components for the Use Case Farm-1

4.1.1.1 Motivation

The ongoing climate changes are as a “driver” for improving overall farming actions, not only by their direct impact on crops, but also through the increasing regulations imposed on farmers. As such, bringing innovation and intelligence to crop management will increase its effectiveness, reduce the consumed resources and increase operations’ cost effectiveness.

The Mediterranean basin is highly susceptible to the harmful effects of climate change, such as water scarcity. In particular, the coastal regions of Málaga and Granada are the main producers of subtropical fruit crops, such as avocados, which are the most important in terms of productivity. The lack of available water for irrigation is threatening this production and a handful of studies have explored the effects of climate change on this crop.

The use case objective is to focus on the development and provision of guaranteed products and services for the agricultural sector, in this case, ensuring water saving according to the phenological stages of the crop and taking advantage of the pilot facilities to optimise and validate the final product. All this will lead to efficient and intelligent irrigation. Large volumes of video and real-time images require 6G technology with lower latency and reliability.

Key Pain Points

1. Irrigation of crops uses approximately 70% of available freshwater worldwide. Real-time decisions to optimise water use are limited by the difficulty in quickly obtaining and analysing sufficient data.
2. The access of producers to tools that improve decisions on irrigation would result in significant savings in the amount of water used for fruticulture
3. Decisions on irrigation are usually made at the orchard level from a qualitative perspective since data collection and analysis at the single tree/plant level is limited. The combination of a significant amount of data at the single tree level together with its rapid flow and analysis, may enable preventive actions to optimise irrigation thus responding to the needs of each plant.
4. Irrigation needs by the phenology of plants is a novel approach for fruit trees, given the lack of seasonal information on most crops. Combining irrigation experiments with phenophases at the orchard level will be crucial in optimising product quality and more efficient use of resources.

4.1.1.2 Scenarios Description

Scenario 1. Avocado irrigated

Several sensors powered by solar energy and batteries will be installed to check for the trees’ physiological parameters related to water consumption. Sensors measuring water in the soil, water potential in the tree trunk, turgor in the leaves and humidity in the environment will be combined. Information from multiple sensors will be uploaded to the Cloud in real-time to generate parameters that serve to understand the hydric status of avocado crops.

Scenario 2. Avocado water scarcity

With the sensors mentioned above, irrigation deficit will be applied to a set of fruits in the orchard to evaluate changes associated with the lack of water, and identify critical points of water use. All data will be sent through a 6G network to the UMA repository and the NPN (Non-Public Network) of CSIC. Then, a feedback process is expected to provide more efficient irrigation and ameliorate drought effects in situ using dedicated software based on decision algorithms.

Scenario 3. Monitoring avocado phenology

Periodically, a drone will send images and videos in real time to the server, which will automatically process these images to obtain parameters to control the hydric status of the plants. The photos will be uploaded to the Cloud using 5G/6G technologies. From there, using image processing software, the phenological status will be inferred first and then the effects of drought will be identified at the tree level. This is a milestone in tree plantations in open plots, enabling detailed diagnoses by tree.

4.1.1.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

Following the requirements of the agriculture use case Farm 1, the usage of three concurrent slices has been identified, following the different needs. An eMBB slice, providing greater bandwidth, will be used to transmit the drone captures, e.g., images and videos. The control of drones and other agricultural machinery needs a reliable link and low latency, requiring a URLLC slice. On the other hand, because the sensors are battery-powered and require an energy-efficient connection, this will be provided by an mMTC slice.

The Application Functions (AF) for controlling the agriculture drone will be deployed in the Edge to reduce latency. The AF for smart irrigation can be deployed in the Edge to reduce the traffic load in the network, as the data collected will be used locally. The high-level topology of the UC is depicted in *Figure 12*.

Figure 12: High-level topology of the UC Farm-1

The use case owner is the experimental station of La Mayora. They operate the farm and deploy the sensors. The University of Málaga is in charge of operating the 5G deployment in La Mayora. They are responsible for coordinating the demonstration of the cases. HPE provides the Core network and Telefónica manages the Edge servers.

The following list shows the key components:

- **Drones Equipped with Multispectral Cameras:** These drones fly over the crops, capturing images in various wavelengths. This imagery can reveal a wealth of plant information, including their health, water

stress levels and growth patterns. Multispectral cameras can see beyond the visible spectrum, detecting issues not visible to the human eye.

- **Sensors:** Alongside or independently from the drones, various sensors are deployed in the field. These include soil moisture sensors, which measure the water content in the soil and can also include temperature, light and nutrient sensors. These sensors provide ground-level data that complements the aerial imagery, giving a fuller picture of the crops' needs.
- **5G Network with an HPE 5GCore and Edge Computing:** The entire system is interconnected via a 5G network, known for its high speed and low latency, making it ideal for transmitting large amounts of data in real-time. The network uses the HPE 5GCore. Edge computing capabilities are also a critical component, where servers located at the Edge of the network (closer to where data is collected) process the images and sensor data. This setup reduces latency further and allows for rapid analysis and response.
- **Data Analytics on Edge Servers:** The servers at the Edge of the network employ data analytics algorithms to interpret the images and sensor data. By analysing this data, the system can identify patterns, detect issues and accurately predict the crops' water needs. This information optimises irrigation plans, ensuring water is used efficiently and only applied where and when needed.

4.1.1.4 Requirements

Table 34 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 35 contains the performance requirements.

Table 34: Use Case UC-FARM-1 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	The high density of sensors	Usage of a massive number of IoT sensors to calculate the precise requirements of water.
FR2	Drones	The system must support their remote control and the streaming of high-resolution videos and images for scanning the status of crops.
FR3	Edge deployment	Servers at the Edge of the network employ data analytics algorithms to interpret the images and sensor data.
FR4	Real time data collection	The system must be capable of continuously collecting real-time data from various sources, including soil moisture sensors, weather stations, and multispectral imaging from drones, to accurately assess the current water needs of crops and the soil's moisture levels.
FR5	High-speed Data Transmission	Utilise the capabilities of 5G networks for high-speed data transmission to ensure that the vast amounts of data collected from sensors and drones are quickly transmitted to the processing servers without significant delays.
FR6	Data Processing and Analytics	The system must efficiently process and analyse the collected data to determine the optimal watering schedules and amounts for each crop type and field section, considering current soil moisture levels, weather forecasts,

and crop water requirements.

Table 35: Use Case UC-FARM-1 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Smart irrigation	Connection density: > 100/km ² ; Battery life: > 1 year
PR2	Drones	Reliability: > 99,999%; Latency: < 5ms
PR3	Multispectral camera	High uplink capacity for transmitting high resolution photos.

4.1.1.5 Validation

4.1.1.5.1 Test Cases

Table 36 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 36: Use Case UC-FARM-1 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Data transmission latency	Test the latency in transmitting data from sensors and drones to the processing servers over the 5G network, ensuring it falls within acceptable thresholds for real-time analysis.
TC2: Data transmission throughput	Test the throughput when transmitting data from sensors and drones to the processing servers over the 5G network, ensuring it provides enough throughput for sending high-resolution images.
TC3: Battery life of sensors and drones	Test the battery duration of sensors and drones in different scenarios to ensure they meet expected life spans under typical usage patterns.
TC4: Connection density	To verify that the 5G NR network can support the target number of simultaneous connections per square kilometre specified by the use case requirements, ensuring stable connectivity and acceptable performance for each connection.

4.1.1.5.2 Validation Tools

UMA will validate the evolved version of the testbed and the performance of vertical solutions via experimentation with the internal use cases and will perform additional validation with the use cases coming from the open calls. UMA is the WP3 leader, and will coordinate the 6G-PATH experimentation environment upgrade and extensions. UMA will also lead task T3.3, developing the southbound and northbound APIs. Validation will be further advanced in these contexts.

4.1.1.5.3 KPIs and KVI

Tables 37 and 38 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 37: Use Case UC-FARM-1 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Video Resolution	Resolution of the video delivered by the multispectral camera using a 5G connection.	4K image resolution and video transmissions
Data transmission latency	Maximum latency in transmitting data from sensors and drones to the processing servers over the 5G network.	20-30 ms
Video transmission throughput	Minimum throughput is needed to transmit high-resolution videos.	15-30 Mbps
Remote control throughput	Minimum throughput needed to transmit control commands and telemetry.	1 Mbps
Inferencing accuracy and interpretability	AI-models accuracy (and additional AI metrics).	Predicting the correct irrigation decisions and the usage of explainable AI techniques; to achieve >5% improvement compared with state-of-the-art algorithms and the no AI benchmark

Table 38: Use Case UC-FARM-1 KVis description

KVI	Description	Objective
Cost Savings	Reduction in water use and resource inputs.	(>10%) compared to the previous period or baseline.
Increase in yield	Crop yield quality increases resulting from timely interventions.	(>20 indicators) collected and processed at the single tree/plant level (baseline: qualitative analysis at the orchard level).
Energy intensity of agriculture	Increases in Agricultural production but reduction in energy consumption.	Delta between costs saved from intelligent water-saving processes and the overhead in compute and network costs in operating such processes (>5%).

4.1.1.6 Expected Outcomes

In sustainable food production, the KVI Environmental water footprint of agriculture activities is a “key” indicator for assessing environmental sustainability. The activities associated with this project will activate the dialogue between farmers, agricultural cooperatives, network operators and the administration to implement these types of initiatives massively; as a result, the project will influence the agricultural sector and society, since implementing the proposed solutions will contribute to the well-being of citizens, ensuring the sustainability of crops.

This project will impact the short/medium term due to the deployment of a pilot plot at the experimentation farm La Mayora, which will predictably accelerate the knowledge of fruit tree performance under different irrigation scenarios, providing invaluable information to the farmers.

This use case will make open access to the following datasets: training data for the AF for smart irrigation; two (-2-) irrigation monitoring AF data, one of the control datasets and the second of the experiments; at least two (-2-) experiments trials or pilots network traces.

CSIC will use this project to continue its history as a reference for the most innovative techniques for studying fruit crop performance. Thus, the pilot plot will expand the current efforts of exploring the 5G technology in monitoring fruit crop water use toward 6G. First, the information generated will be transferred to stakeholders and growers. The innovative approach that combines data from images and sensors through time will be important for the scientific community. In particular, this project will create an attractive environment for the students of this generation, and several graduate, MSc, and PhD research students will be involved in the research activities of IHSM (Instituto de Hortofruticultura Subtropical y Mediterránea), aligned with the project activities, thus helping to train the next generation of plant physiologists. The project results will also be reported in the most relevant journals of plant physiology and technological advancements in agriculture. The predicted results will enable the establishment of new collaborative consortiums of a transdisciplinary nature, opening the possibility of applying for funds from the EU, such as the PRIMA projects⁵² for agricultural solutions. Finally, the new paradigm of the virtual solutions of this project will allow collaboration with developers of applications in agriculture, thus expanding the results to final users and extending the research applications of 6G systems to society.

4.1.1.7 Risk Assessment

Table 39 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 39: Use Case UC-FARM-1 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Failure to integrate 5G connectivity into the sensors and multispectral camera	L	H	Identification of dataloggers and multispectral cameras with support for Ethernet connection so the integration with 5G routers is easier.
R2	Delay of the readiness of the 5G deployment in La Mayora	M	H	A commercial 5G network can be used.

⁵² The PRIMA is an EU program for Research and Innovation solutions in the Mediterranean region. For more details see: <https://prima-med.org/>

4.1.2 UC-FARM-2 – Smart vineyards

The “Smart Vineyards” use case aims to elevate vineyard management by integrating advanced technologies such as Edge computing, satellite imaging (remote observation), private 5G/6G networks and AI/ML algorithms. By leveraging these technologies, the use case seeks to optimise resource usage, improve productivity and minimise environmental impact.

4.1.2.1 Motivation

The motivation behind the Smart Vineyards use case is to “address” the key pain points in traditional vineyard management, including limited visibility and control over operations, inefficient resource utilisation and reliance on manual intervention. By deploying satellite, Edge computing technologies equipped with private 5G/6G networks, the use case aims to enable real-time monitoring and automated interventions, thereby enhancing operational efficiency and productivity.

Key Pain Points

1. **Limited Visibility and Control over Vineyard Operations:** Vineyard operators often “face” challenges in gaining comprehensive visibility into their operations due to the vastness of vineyard landscapes and the complexity of grape cultivation. Traditional monitoring and management methods rely heavily on manual observation and periodic inspections, which may not provide real-time insights into crop health, environmental conditions or operational efficiency. This limited visibility can lead to inefficiencies, such as delayed response to emerging issues like pest infestations, disease outbreaks or adverse weather conditions. Without timely and accurate data on vineyard conditions, operators may struggle to make informed decisions regarding irrigation scheduling, pest control measures, or harvest planning, impacting overall productivity and grape quality.
2. **Inefficient Resource Utilisation:** Inefficient resource utilisation is a common challenge in vineyard management, particularly concerning water, fertilisers and labour. Traditional irrigation practices often rely on fixed schedules or manual soil moisture assessments, leading to overwatering or under-watering of vines and wastage of water resources. Similarly, the indiscriminate use of fertilisers without precise monitoring of soil nutrient levels can result in nutrient runoff and environmental pollution. Moreover, manual labour-intensive tasks, such as pruning, canopy management and harvesting, may be inefficiently allocated due to limited visibility into vineyard conditions and labour availability. These inefficiencies can increase production costs, reduce profitability and have negative environmental impacts, such as soil degradation and water contamination.
3. **Reliance on Manual Intervention for Monitoring and Management Tasks:** Traditionally, vineyard management relies heavily on manual intervention for monitoring and managing various tasks, including pest and disease monitoring, irrigation management and harvest planning. This reliance on manual labour can be time-consuming, labour-intensive and prone to human error. For example, visual inspection for pest infestations or disease symptoms may not be comprehensive or timely enough to prevent significant crop damage. Similarly, manual irrigation scheduling based on visual soil moisture assessments may result in suboptimal water use efficiency and uneven vineyard irrigation. Moreover, the availability and cost of labour for manual tasks may vary seasonally, leading to operational challenges and delays in critical vineyard activities. The reliance on manual intervention limits operational efficiency, scalability and adaptability to changing environmental conditions, affecting vineyard productivity and profitability.

4.1.2.2 Scenarios Description

The Smart Vineyards use case encompasses multiple scenarios tailored to different vineyard conditions and requirements. These scenarios include:

Scenario 1: Off-grid Deployment:

In an off-grid deployment scenario, the vineyard operates in a completely isolated environment without consistent access to external networks or Cloud services. This could occur in remote rural areas where traditional network infrastructure is unavailable or unreliable. In this scenario, all processing and storage occur locally within the vineyard premises. The Edge computing nodes deployed within the vineyard can autonomously handle data collection, analysis and storage. This setup provides vineyard operators with complete privacy and control over their data. It also ensures continuous operation even in the absence of external connectivity. However, it requires a robust local infrastructure and may limit access to real-time updates or Cloud-based services.

Scenario 2: Intermittent Connectivity:

In the intermittent connectivity scenario, the vineyard has periodic access to Cloud services and external networks for data backup and updates. This scenario is common in partially covered regions where network connectivity is available but may be unreliable or intermittent. It could also apply to vineyards located in areas with limited network infrastructure or where network connectivity is established temporarily for specific purposes. In this setup, data collected by the Edge computing nodes is periodically synchronised with Cloud-based storage and processing platforms during periods of connectivity. This allows for the backup of critical data and updates to algorithms or software without requiring constant network connectivity. However, it may result in delays in data processing and analysis during periods of disconnection.

Scenario 3: Interconnected Deployment:

The vineyard has constant backhaul connectivity to local and Cloud-based processing resources, in an interconnected deployment scenario. This scenario suits vineyards in well-connected regions with reliable network infrastructure. It provides continuous access to Cloud services for real-time data analysis, updates and seamless integration with external systems. The Edge computing nodes within the vineyard leverage local processing capabilities and Cloud resources to optimise performance and scalability. This setup enables vineyard operators to leverage the full potential of Edge computing and Cloud services, ensuring high efficiency and optimisation in vineyard operations. However, it may require higher investment in network infrastructure and ongoing maintenance to ensure uninterrupted connectivity.

4.1.2.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

Terraview plays a central role by deploying Crates within the vineyard environment. These Crates enable connectivity to Terraview's Cloud-based management platform, facilitating seamless integration of Edge and Cloud functionalities. With Crates equipped with Edge TVOS, vineyard operators gain access to advanced data processing, analytics and decision-making capabilities at the Edge of the network, enabling real-time monitoring, analysis and control of vineyard operations.

ONE contributes to the ecosystem by providing a solution for managing and coordinating Autonomous Aerial Vehicles (AAVs) and Autonomous Ground Vehicles (AGVs) deployed within the vineyard environment. The solution provided by ONE enables seamless integration of AAVs and AGVs into vineyard operations, facilitating crop monitoring, pest control and infrastructure inspection. By connecting Crates to on-site-deployed AAVs and AGVs managed by ONE's solution, the smart vineyard ecosystem enhances operational efficiency, reduces manual labour requirements and enables precision agriculture practices.

The deployment architecture consists of one or more Crates distributed across the vineyard, each equipped with compute and storage nodes, and additional connectivity options like LoRa. Kubernetes enables scalability. Figure 13 depicts the high-level topology of the Smart Vineyards UC.

Furthermore, the Smart Vineyards use case will utilise the following key components:

Key component 1 - Crates: Edge Ingestion Nodes with Private 5G/6G Networks

- Crates refer to specialised Edge computing nodes deployed within the vineyard premises. These nodes serve as localised data ingestion nodes with processing power and storage capabilities.
- Crates can be equipped with private 5G/6G network connectivity technology (amongst others), enabling seamless connectivity and communication between various sensors, devices and machinery deployed within the vineyard.

Key component 2 - Aquaview: Cloud-Based Vineyard Management Platform

- Aquaview is a Cloud-based decision support system around water use efficiency platform developed by Terraview and complimenting TerraviewOS; it is designed to provide comprehensive tools and functionalities for water-related vineyard management and optimisation.
- It serves as a centralised hub for data aggregation, analysis and visualisation, allowing vineyard operators to monitor and remotely manage aspects related to irrigation.
- It leverages advanced analytics, machine learning algorithms and historical data to provide actionable insights and recommendations to vineyard operators, enabling them to make informed decisions and optimise vineyard irrigation performance.
- It leverages other components of the smart vineyard ecosystem, such as Crates and TerraviewOS.

Key component 3 - AAVs and AGVs: Autonomous Aerial and Ground Vehicles for Operations

- AAVs (Autonomous Aerial Vehicles) and AGVs (Autonomous Ground Vehicles) are unmanned vehicles with sensors, cameras and other monitoring devices.
- AAVs, such as drones, are used for aerial surveillance, imaging, and monitoring of vineyard conditions from above. They can capture high-resolution imagery and provide further imagery data to Aquaview.

Figure 13: Smart Vineyards High Level Topology

Key component 4 - Awareness Solution: Machinery Tracking Solution Bridging Decisions Between Systems and Operations

- The Awareness Solution provided by ONE is a specialised machinery tracking solution designed to bridge the gap between decision-making processes in the Terraview OS platform and on-the-ground vineyard operations.
- It can integrate seamlessly with Terraview products to track the vineyard machinery’s location, status and activities, including AAVs and AGVs.
- The Awareness Solution provides vineyard operators with actionable insights into machinery utilisation, performance and efficiency, enabling them to optimise resource allocation, task scheduling and operational workflows. By leveraging data from both Terraview OS and on-the-ground sensors, the Awareness Solution facilitates informed decision-making and coordination between centralised management systems and autonomous operational units within the vineyard.
- It enhances operational efficiency, reduces downtime, and improves overall vineyard management effectiveness by giving operators real-time visibility and control over machinery operations and activities.

4.1.2.4 Requirements

Table 40 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 41 contains the performance requirements.

Table 40: Use Case UC-FARM-2 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Autonomous Operation	Crates operate independently without an external connection to Terraview systems.
FR2	Over-the-air updates	The software stack can be updated remotely (when a connection is available).

FR3	In-crate data ingestion	Data from on-the-ground sensors can be ingested locally.
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Table 41: Use Case UC-FARM-2 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Data Transfer Efficiency	Reduce data transfer from property to central Cloud.
PR2	Low latency	Enable real-time decision-making.
PR3	Minimal overhead	The processing time of data remains the same. No increase.

4.1.2.5 Validation

4.1.2.5.1 Test Cases

Table 42 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 42: Use Case UC-FARM-2 test case description

Title	Description
TC1	Validate functionality.
TC2	Evaluate the reliability of software upgrade strategies.
TC3	Validate internal connectivity throughput.
TC4	Validate internal connectivity latency.
TC5	Validate external connectivity throughput.
TC6	Validate external connectivity latency.

4.1.2.5.2 Validation Tools

Validation tools include automated testing frameworks, simulation environments and real-world field tests. Terraview will comprehensively validate the deployed solution in a real-world test site environment to ensure its effectiveness, reliability and scalability. The validation process will involve rigorous testing of the end-to-end functionality of the solution across various scenarios and use cases relevant to smart vineyard operations.

The validation activities can include, depending on needs:

- **End-to-End Testing:** Terraview will perform extensive end-to-end testing to verify all components' seamless integration and interoperability within the smart vineyard ecosystem. This testing will encompass data transmission, processing and decision-making workflows to validate the solution stack.
- **Scenario-Based Testing:** Terraview will simulate and execute multiple scenarios representative of typical vineyard irrigation operations, including different environmental conditions, crop management tasks and operational challenges. This scenario-based testing will validate the solution's ability to adapt and perform optimally under varying circumstances.

- Performance Testing: Terraview will evaluate speed, efficiency and resource utilisation performance. This testing will assess data processing latency, network throughput and scalability to ensure the solution “meets” performance requirements under different load conditions.
- Reliability and Robustness Testing: Terraview will assess the reliability and robustness of the solution by subjecting it to stress tests, fault injection and failure scenarios. This testing will validate the solution’s resilience to failures, ability to recover from disruptions and overall reliability in mission-critical vineyard irrigation operations.

4.1.2.5.3 KPIs and KVIs

Tables 43 and 44 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 43: Use Case UC-FARM-2 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Data processing	Increase in data processing time on-site (Edge) compared to Cloud.	<5%
Resource dependency	Reduction from Cloud resources dependency.	10%
Coverage	Vineyard coverage by additionally using AGVs and/or AAVs to automate and minimise the processing time.	>95%
Accuracy	Predictive model accuracy	5%

Table 44: Use Case UC-FARM-2 KVIs description

KVI	Description	Objective
Energy efficiency	Energy and Resource Efficiency and OPEX cost reduction in day-to-day operations and usage of natural resources compared to Cloud-based solutions.	5%
Cost Reduction	Reduction in cost for Terraview. Terraview’s resource cost reductions.	10%
Water usage reduction	Potential water usage reductions are enabled by early threat detection and prevention.	10%

4.1.2.6 Expected Outcomes

The expected outcomes of the Smart Vineyards use case include:

Enhanced Vineyard Irrigation Management Capabilities through the Deployment of Crates:

- The deployment of Crates within the vineyard environment is expected to elevate vineyard irrigation management practices through Aquaview by providing real-time data processing, analysis and decision-making capabilities at the Edge of the network.

- Crates facilitate the integration of diverse data sources, including environmental sensors, machinery telemetry and crop health monitoring systems, enabling vineyard irrigation management and optimisation strategies.
- By leveraging Edge computing capabilities offered by Crates, vineyard operators can streamline operations, optimise resource allocation and mitigate risks such as water leaching, poorly designed irrigation placement and schedules, pest infestations, crop diseases and adverse weather conditions on time.

Improved Productivity and Efficiency in Vineyard Operations:

- The implementation of smart vineyard solutions is expected to “drive” significant improvements in productivity and efficiency across vineyard operations.
- Automation of routine tasks such as irrigation scheduling, pest control and harvest planning through AI-driven algorithms and autonomous vehicle deployment reduces reliance on manual labour and minimises operational bottlenecks.
- Enhanced data-driven decision-making facilitated by smart vineyard solutions leads to optimised resource utilisation, reduced input wastage and increased operational agility, ultimately resulting in higher productivity and profitability for vineyard operators.

Advancements in 5G/6G Deployment Approaches and Service Placement Optimisation:

- The Smart Vineyards use case is a testbed for exploring innovative deployment approaches and service placement optimisation strategies for 5G/6G networks in agricultural settings.
- By integrating private 5G/6G networks into the vineyard ecosystem, the use case demonstrates the feasibility and benefits of localised, Edge-centric network architectures tailored to specific agricultural use cases.
- Through experimentation and validation within the vineyard environment, the use case aims to identify best practices, performance metrics and deployment models for optimising network services, resources and communication infrastructure placement to maximise operational efficiency and user experience.
- Insights gained from the Smart Vineyards use case contribute to advancing 5G/6G technology deployment paradigms, fostering innovation and collaboration between stakeholders in the agriculture and telecommunications sectors to accelerate digital transformation in rural and remote environments.

4.1.2.7 Risk Assessment

Table 45 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 45: Use Case UC-FARM-2 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Delay in readiness of internal 5G network deployment.	L	M	Use commercially available 5G network.
R2	Problems with automated data transfers from sensors, AAVs and AGVs to Crate.	M	M	Availability of manual interventions.

R3	Crate device HW limiting processing capabilities.	M	M	Reduce data volumes processed.
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4.2 Education

4.2.1 UC-EDU-1 – XR rural school

The implementation of the project in two rural schools in Romania aims to create captivating and interactive learning experiences that will help students improve their academic performance and reduce the discrepancies between students' learning in rural and urban environments, respectively.

The support for this use case will essentially rely on the infrastructure of the ORO's networks. ORO will provide data connectivity through the commercially deployed network (5GSA) and access to a fully-fledged 5G/6G Experimentation Platform ("testbed") equipped with the latest generation of software and hardware solution. The VR (Virtual Reality) Caravan, operated from Iasi, Romania, and both rural schools will have the necessary coverage to ensure a good quality experience for students and teachers. Besides the necessary XR (Extended Reality) equipment, the schools will receive tablet computers and laptops to support their teaching experiences and ensure appropriate access to the Digitaliada platform⁵³ and content creation processes. Figure 14 shows a high-level overview of this use case.

This use case also considers the possibility of increasing the teaching experience and materials through "Track C" of the Open Calls, where external entities may contribute developing and integrating new content. The use case will also drive, together with the Digitaliada program, the necessary training so that teachers and other faculty staff can contribute. In short, the trials for this user case will include:

- Interactive multimedia content: Various multimedia resources, such as videos, animations and 3D models allow students to explore learning subjects in a captivating and interactive way.
- Personalised learning experiences: The platform could be designed to adapt the learning experience to each student's knowledge level and skills. This could help improve students' academic performance and reduce disparities between rural and urban students.
- Use of VR/AR (Augmented Reality) devices: The platform will be compatible with various virtual and augmented reality devices, such as VR glasses or AR-supported mobile phones, to allow students to experience learning subjects more practically and interactively.
- Collaboration and interaction: The platform will allow students to collaborate and interact with each other and their teachers more innovatively and engagingly.
- Evaluation and monitoring: The platform will allow teachers to evaluate students' performance and monitor their progress during the learning process. This could help identify areas for improvement and adapt the teaching material accordingly.

⁵³ More details can be found at: <https://www.digitaliada.ro/platforma-digitaliada>

Figure 14: High Level Diagram of UC-EDU-1

4.2.1.1 Motivation

In Romania, digital education is still a privilege, as almost 38% [26] of children under 16 years old and 37.5% of young people aged 16-24 are at risk of poverty or social exclusion, a situation that is particularly widespread among those with a low level of education: almost 55% of people who have only completed primary school are exposed to poverty or social exclusion, with a significant proportion in rural areas, according to data from EUROSTAT. 45% of Romania's kids come from rural areas and almost 30% of them are unable to get a passing grade [26] at the National Evaluation, which prevents them from accessing high school and university studies. This means that several generations of kids' chances of employment will be either in dirty, dull and dangerous jobs or in domains which will provide fewer chances of making a decent wage. At the same time, some of these jobs will be subject to extinction within the next 20 years, due to automation and machine learning. All studies on the future of labour predict (from Oxford to World Economic Forum) that IT and technology skills will be in high demand.

Studies [28] within the Digitaliada programme show that there is an important category of teachers who have an open attitude towards the use of new technologies and digital content in the classroom, across all types of schools, regardless of the level of technology.

It is our use case motivation to "drive" this attitude towards exploitable results in improving the students' academic performance and to "reduce the gap" in the adoption and utilisation of technologies in urban and rural schools, respectively.

An equally important motivation is ORO's and OROF's commitment to "drive" the usage of technologies in education and to improve the existing methods and processes using sustainable new technologies such as beyond-5G networks and Extended Reality technology.

Key Pain Points

1. **Low availability of XR-enabled educational content tailored to the Romanian primary and secondary education curriculum:** There is a lack of developed and distributed content mapped to the national

curriculum for primary and secondary schools. While technological advances are steadfastly making XR available to many new regions in rural areas, content availability is lagging. This Pain Point should be addressed in 6G-PATH through the Open Calls for developers to construct XR-enabled platforms and services that allow content to be adapted to XR-world.

2. **Low availability of equipment and IT resources in the rural schools of Romania:** The rural areas of Romania lack the funding and infrastructure required to adopt significant IT resources, including equipment, to enable the utilisation of XR/VR/AR technologies. We aim to address this Pain Point in 6G-PATH, by acquiring and deploying a functional set-up of portable computers – laptops, tablet computers and XR-enabled interfaces – VR headsets, actuators and control surfaces/control devices – to two (-2-) rural schools and one (-1-) mobile “VR Caravan”, to pilot the usage of beyond-5G-enabled technologies in education.
3. **Low adaptation of XR-enabled technologies in Education in the rural schools of Romania:** We aim to address this pain point in 6G-PATH, through “teach the teacher” engagement, co-ordinated by OROF through the Digitaliada platform, to enable easy and replicable adaptation of their teaching tools and methods, to the usage of XR-enabled content.

4.2.1.2 Scenarios Description

UC-EDU-1 relies on 2 distinct scenarios of implementing immersive education in two (-2-) target rural schools and deploying a similarly equipped “VR Caravan”.

Both scenarios will leverage the utilisation of ORO’s beyond-5G capabilities in the 5G Lab testbeds and extend to ORO’s commercial networks and will enable OROF and ORO to deploy “Digitaliada”, the educational platform developed by OROF through the 6G-PATH experimentation framework.

Digitaliada will be deployed as a Network-aware application, with components and services in the ORO 5GSA Edge, and will be improved with additional capabilities including:

- 5G readiness
- XR-class devices management
- XR content management
- 5G-enabled content delivery.

Furthermore, third-party network applications will be able to interact with Digitaliada to enable the creation and deployment of XR content, such as interactive and personalised learning experiences and simulations. The 6G-PATH Open Calls will support these third party network applications’ selection and integration activities.

During the Testbeds Upgrades and Extensions phase, ORO’s testbed will be updated to support the functional and operational requirements of UC-EDU-1 and to enable integration with the 6G-PATH platform’s components.

During the integration phase of the two scenarios, the various 6G-PATH components will be deployed to ORO’s Testbeds (1.3) and tested for interoperability with the 5GC and Edge components of ORO’s testbed.

During the internal trials and pilots for the Education Vertical, the principal activities targeting the two scenarios of UC-EDU-1 will be:

- **Composition of ORO’s testbed and UC-EDU-1 to the 6G-PATH Platform** – This activity will use several experiments enabling components to onboard the required assets of the UC components.
- **Deployment of the UC components to the 6G-PATH platform** – This activity will encompass the creation of the Use Case Repository assets for UC-EDU-1, such as the Use Case images for the Network Applications to be deployed - Digitaliada and third-party applications through the 6G-PATH Open Calls.

- **Testing and validation of UC-EDU-1** – This activity will fall forward to the two test cases (“scenarios”) to validate the overall use case ambitions and expected outcomes, supported through the KPIs and KVI to be collected during the piloting.

Scenario A – “XR in rural schools”

This scenario targets deploying of an XR-enabled platform to two primary schools in rural areas of Romania. The two schools will be selected through an internal evaluation process of OROF’s, building on top of their demonstrable experience in working with primary education institutions, on several other projects and opportunities.

The principal actors of this scenario will be:

- **Testbed Operators** – Will interact with the 6G-PATH platform to deploy the UC components, select the KPIs and Metrics for monitoring, choose the testbed features required for the piloting and initiate the piloting of Scenario 1.
- **End-Users 1** – A selected group of teachers, from the two schools will be able to use “Digitaliada” to choose and deploy XR-enabled content to end-users to schedule and create interactive learning experiences and simulations from pre-defined primitives.
- **End-Users 2** – Primary School pupils, in the two schools to be selected, will use “Digitaliada” through XR-enabled interactions with UE to be deployed in the schools.

The pre-requisites for running Scenario A are:

- The 6G-PATH platform and platform components are available and integrated into ORO’s Testbed Infrastructure.
- The 6G-PATH Open Calls have yielded at least one successful integration of a third-party application, to Digitaliada, to allow the end-user creation and management of XR-rich content from existing primitives.
- XR-enabled User Equipment, such as VR-headsets, touch-based interactive surfaces and controllers, exists and is integrated and managed through Digitaliada.
- 5GSA exists between the two schools in Scenario A piloting.
- The end-users have received the required training to operate the testbed interfaces and the Digitaliada Platform.

Scenario B – “XR Caravan”

This second scenario targets the deployment of an XR-enabled platform to a purpose-equipped vehicle (for this purpose, a Caravan-class automobile) which will transit between rural areas near Iași, Romania and support the dissemination of XR-enabled learning to the teachers, students and pupils in these rural areas. The principal purpose of this scenario is to demonstrate the mobility capabilities and features of the 6G-PATH platform.

The principal actors of this scenario will be:

- **Testbed Operators** – Will interact with the 6G-PATH platform to deploy the UC components, select the KPIs and Metrics for monitoring, choose the testbed features required for the piloting and initiate the piloting of Scenario 1.
- **End-Users 1** – A selected group of teachers use “Digitaliada” to choose and deploy XR-enabled content to a demonstration set-up, available in the XR-Caravan.

- **End-Users 2** – Primary school students and pupils will interact with the XR-enabled platform, Digitaliada, during the Caravan’s visits to their localities.

The pre-requisites for running Scenario B are:

- The 6G-PATH platform and platform components are available and integrated into ORO’s Testbed Infrastructure.
- The 6G-PATH open calls have yielded at least one successful integration of a third-party application, to Digitaliada, to allow the end-user creation and management of XR-rich content from existing primitives.
- XR-enabled User Equipment, such as VR-headsets, touch-based interactive surfaces and controllers, exists and is integrated and managed through Digitaliada; these are available and ready for use in the Caravan and are supported through that vehicle’s electronics.
- 5GSA connectivity exists in the areas through which the Caravan will travel through.
- The end-users have received the required training to operate the testbed interfaces and the Digitaliada Platform.

4.2.1.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

Integration in the scope of EC-EDU-1 will “run” in three distinct domains, comprising of the 6G-PATH Platform, ORO testbed infrastructure and the ORO 5GSA MEC deployment (and, if available at runtime, the 5GSA Commercial MEC deployment).

The 6G-PATH platform and components should be deployed in ORO’s testbed to support experimentation for third-party apps selected in the Open Calls process and should support the feature set selected by the third-party application developer/experimenter.

The 6G-PATH platform should consist of all components required for the running of experiments across the testbeds, all interfaces, all frontend/backend services and applications, and should be available in instances deployed to the experimentation testbeds. During the project’s lifecycle, the 6G-PATH project consortium will support the deployment of components to target testbeds and/or to a centralised platform interfacing with the federated components in the testbeds.

ORO Testbed facility is in University Politehnica of Bucharest in a “5G Lab” and remotely extended to a 5G Lab in Iași, a large city in the North-Eastern region of Romania; it implements a complete 5G SA 3GPP Release 16 compatible infrastructure.

The testbed infrastructure comprises a series of software and hardware components, including open software tools, integrated into an end-to-end functionality scenario. The testbed is equipped with the latest generation of software and hardware solutions for 5GSA RAN, 5G Core elements including but not limited to AMF, SMF, UPF, NSSF, NRF, advanced programmable network solution based on next-generation Data Centre IPFABRIC concepts⁵⁴, MANO functions (OSMv12/13⁵⁵) orchestrating OpenStack clusters⁵⁶ (controllers, deployment servers, shared storage and pool of servers for computing) or Kubernetes clusters (master nodes and workers) running as a Cloud Native infrastructure. The testbed is also enabled with Security functions, including Fortinet 1000D

⁵⁴ IP fabric is an overlay tunneling technology that is based on IP networks.

⁵⁵ More details regarding Open Source MANO (OSM) documentation can be found at: <https://osm.etsi.org/docs/user-guide/latest/>

⁵⁶ For more details also see, *inter-alia*: <https://static.openstack.org/docs/senlin/3.0.1/developer/cluster.html>

Firewalls⁵⁷ and BIG-IP F5 Load balancers⁵⁸; through this, different applications, services or multi-domain or multi-federation testbeds and architecture implementation can be secured, implemented and monitored.

The testbed also provides considerable computing resources (12TB RAM, 1000vCPU, 48TB storage RAID 1, high-speed network interfaces (10/25Gbps), GPUs and external storage. Different virtualised functions can be instantiated in the testbed, such as VNFs or CNFs (VMS or CNs), through orchestration. The testbed also ensures the orchestration of the network functions, dynamic slice implementation for end-customers, and **5GSA network services dynamically connected to Edge computing**. The 5G LAB functionality in Bucharest is extended to 5G LAB in Iasi, infrastructures interconnected through high-speed broadband (100Gbps interfaces), having similar technical approach and features in terms of 5GSA network capabilities, computing, monitoring, orchestration and analytics functionality, enabling the path for Compute Continuum.

A high-level depiction of the overall Use Case Topology is presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15: High-Level architecture and topology diagram for UC-EDU-1

The system also provides network slice capabilities, such as eMBB (1500Mbps/150Mbps DL/UL) or URLLC <3ms one-way delay (average 5ms end-to-end RTT from device to Edge). The 5G SA spectrum available for the

⁵⁷ For further details also see, among others: <https://www.avfirewalls.com/FortiGate-1000D.asp>

⁵⁸ A BIG-IP F5 Load Balancer uses various algorithms to distribute traffic across multiple servers. These algorithms include round-robin, least connections, IP hash and more. The solution also has advanced features such as SSL offloading, TCP optimisation and caching to improve performance and security further.

experiments and tests is up to 100MHz in N78 bands, with different radio CA for DL and UL being also available, based on 3GPP carrier aggregation characteristics for improved performance. The ORO testbed has integrated a series of 5G devices and hardware components, for example Cradlepoint R1900⁵⁹, Siemens MUM856⁶⁰, Quectel RM500Q-GL⁶¹, Inhand ER805⁶² and Nokia FastMile 5G⁶³. The setup is suitable use cases requiring intensive high-capacity transmissions (VR/AR, Digital Twin, V2X, etc.) and experimentation is available in indoor, outdoor and mobile scenarios.

Furthermore, the high-level process for each experimenter, either internal to the project (OROF, as a champion of UC-EDU-1) or external, coming from the Open Calls, should permit the experimenter to interact via the 6G-PATH platform's frontend to access the experimentation dashboards which, in turn will allow them to select assets from the composition repositories:

- Testbed features: Topology features will determine the target testbed for the desired experimentation activity.
- Metrics and KPIs features: These will determine the baseline and benchmark characteristics for the desired experimentation measurement of outcomes.
- Use Case Composition features: Aiming to determine the overall scope and main flows of the experimentation.
- Control the experimentation lifecycle to start or stop the experiment's main flows.

4.2.1.4 Requirements

Table 46 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 47 contains the performance requirements.

Table 46: Use Case UC-EDU-1 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Beyond-5G Network Connectivity	The 5GSA network infrastructure is available, offering connectivity in the geographical areas where the rural schools are localised.
FR2	Availability of third-party "XR" apps	Availability of third-party apps to develop XR-enabled content from existing curriculum Integration of device management functionality for the XR devices into the Digitaliada Platform or as a third-party application running on the Edge.
FR3	Availability of XR-enabled equipment	XR-enabled equipment includes VR-headsets, control surfaces and interactive control devices and the IT infrastructure required to support the equipment operation, such as laptop computers, tablet computers and Wi-Fi Networks.

⁵⁹ For more details see: <https://cradlepoint.com/product/endpoints/r1900-series/>

⁶⁰ For more details also see, among others: <https://mall.industry.siemens.com/mall/en/WW/Catalog/Products/10400849?tree=CatalogTree>

⁶¹ For more details see: <https://www.quectel.com/product/5g-rm500u-series/>

⁶² Also see, among others: <https://poweris.inhandnetworks.com/api/plm/offical/files?category=Specifications&subcategory=General&series=ER800>

⁶³ For more details see: <https://www.nokia.com/networks/fixed-networks/fastmile/5g-gateway-32-2/>

Table 47: Use Case UC-EDU-1 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Ultra-high bandwidth	>50Gbps bandwidth available to the XR platform and UE.
PR2	Ultra-low latency	<3ms available to UE XR devices.
PR3	Near-zero Packet Loss	Minimal E2E packet loss.

4.2.1.5 Validation

4.2.1.5.1 Test Cases

UC-EDU-1 envisions 2 test cases, described as Scenario A and Scenario B. The two scenarios target similar actors, end-users and operators as well as similar utilisation of XR technologies, but in vastly different 6G domains – delivery and management of XR-enabled functionalities and content, over 6G networks to stationary building, in Scenario A) and delivery and management of XR-enabled functionalities and content, over 6G networks to a moving vehicle, in-field. The test cases proposed for validation will cover both scenarios. Table 48 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 48: Use Case UC-EDU-1 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Validate 6G connectivity to target areas in UC-EDU-1	Test and validate the availability of 6G network access in the two rural areas and in-field in the projected itinerary of the XR-Caravan.
TC2: Validate the Use Case composition on ORO's testbed	Test and verify if the software components, services and interfaces access required to deliver and manage XR-enabled functionalities and content over 6G to the end-users of UC-EDU-1 are available, including the availability of Digitaliada and the third-party applications and modules that plug-in to Digitaliada to extend its functionality with XR-enabled features.
TC3: Validate UE availability, connectivity and management capabilities	Test and validate if the XR-supporting User-Equipment is available in the two rural schools and the XR-Caravan, test and validate if the equipment can be connected to the 6G networks, test and validate if the device management functions are available and onboarded in the Digitaliada Platform.

4.2.1.5.2 Validation Tools

The outcomes of UC-EDU-1 will be validated using industry-standard tools. Open-source, and commercial-off-the-shelves to support the end-to-end methodology for measurements of KPIs. After field trials, questionnaires will collect stakeholder feedback, using opinionated questions on a 5-point Likert Scale, for Economic KIVs and Service Quality KIVs. Similarly, the same style of the survey will also be extended to validate the Social KIVs selected for the Use Case.

4.2.1.5.3 KPIs and KVIs

Tables 49 and 50 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 49: Use Case UC-EDU-1 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Ultra-high bandwidth	XR Enabled Content required very high bandwidth capabilities in the 6G network transport.	More than 50 Gbps available bandwidth to the XR platform and the XR UE.
Ultra-low latency	XR Enabled interactions require ultra-low latency.	Less than 3ms available to UE XR devices.
Near-zero packet loss	Achieve extremely low loss of data packets during transmission, ensuring high reliability and data integrity in network communication.	<0.01%

Table 50: Use Case UC-EDU-1 KVIs description

KVI	Description	Objective
Increase in QoE	Increase the perceived QoE and impact of XR-enabled and content-rich training experiences.	>20%
Engagement and student satisfaction	Increase the students' engagement and satisfaction compared to baseline (traditional teaching).	>20%
Academic achievement	Increase the students' academic achievements compared to baseline (traditional teaching).	>20%
Student retention	Improve student retention compared to baseline (traditional teaching).	>10%

4.2.1.6 Expected Outcomes

A successful implementation of “Digitaliada” as an XR-enabled learning platform in two rural schools in Romania and one mobile deployment (“XR Caravan”), achieving the KPIs set forward in this proposal and leading to the validation of the Use Case. **Improve learning outcomes of schools in rural areas** – Through the provisioning of a digitalised, alternative content-rich platform with 6G XR-based immersive and interactive engaging experiences, Digitaliada can significantly improve the attrition rates in sparsely-populated rural areas of Romania and visibly add to the learning experiences and performance results of the pupils. **Improve teacher attrition in schools in rural areas** – Digitaliada will focus on providing a teach-the-teacher medium, rich in XR-based experiences thus achieving a slower slope for new hires and incumbent teachers, to gain knowledge in using of new technologies for teaching their current curricula. In turn, this can improve the retention of teachers in schools in rural areas. **Enhance awareness, availability, and accessibility of 6G XR-enabled learning tools** - by deploying Digitaliada’s XR-enabled learning experiences to a caravan through the North-Eastern parts of Romania, teachers and pupils in areas not covered through the fixed deployments, will experience the XR-enabled, improved teaching and learning methods and tools.

4.2.1.7 Risk Assessment

Table 51 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 51: Use Case UC-EDU-1 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Failure to integrate the Digitaliada Platform's Device Management with the B5G Infrastructure	L	H	Requirements for integration will be set forward at an early stage of the project, giving ORO and OROF ample time to seek alternative means of assuring XR device management, such as out-of-band management.
R2	Failure to integrate XR content management capabilities to the Digitaliada Platform	M	M	Alternative means of deploying XR content to the two rural schools are being considered, such as using a third-party platform for the content management – ClassVR.
R3	Failure to meet Use Case mobility requirements for the XR-Caravan Scenario	L	M	The XR-Caravan vehicle will be positioned near a vantage point relative to ORO's 5GSA Coverage, in the areas of the demonstrations where school pupils will engage with the XR platform.

4.2.2 UC-EDU-2 – Classroom of Future

This use case in the UK targets the creation of a highly immersive and interactive teaching and learning environment for students to receive and enjoy high-quality learning experiences, comparable to physical reality and, in some cases, superior than the physical reality.

This use case will be implemented based on the experimental infrastructure at UWS. UWS will provide access to its customised 5G XR (VR/AR) platform, i.e. UWS testbed equipped with proper software and hardware solution for this use case.

4.2.2.1 Motivation

With the increasing complexity of the wireless/mobile networking scenarios in 5G and beyond networks, it has become growingly challenging for university lecturers to effectively explain the complicated networking technologies, such as virtualisation, softwarisation, multitenancy, etc. to students in the computer networking discipline. These students struggle to understand such new concepts coupled with the conventional telecommunication infrastructure. Moreover, hybrid teaching and learning have become a norm in universities since the pandemic and thus, innovative approaches have been required to manage such new educational settings whilst keeping comparable quality for higher education.

Key Pain Points

- Lack of XR-ready platform for teaching and learning in the 5G and beyond networking discipline.
- Lack of cutting-edge XR-enabled higher education materials for the computer networking curriculum.
- Lack of experience in applying XR-based classrooms of the future, especially in hybrid module delivery settings.

4.2.2.2 Scenarios Description

UC-EDU-2 focuses on a primary scenario of teaching and learning of complicated 5G/6G virtualised, softwarised and multitenant infrastructure.

The main actors of this scenario will be:

- **Testbed Operator** – The UWS team in this project will act as the Testbed Operator to manage the 6G-PATH platform to deploy, operate and maintain the UWS testbed and support users including third parties to access the testbed and onboard the use cases.
- **Teaching staff as End-User** – The lecturers at UWS will help generate and deliver the required teaching and learning materials for this use case.
- **Students as End-Users** – University students at UWS will help test the use case deployed and provide feedback.

The pre-requisites for running this use case:

- The essential 6G-PATH components are developed and integrated with the UWS testbed, especially the Portal and the ELCM in the first step, followed by other northbound components and the components in the southbound interface.
- XR-enabled teaching and learning materials are developed and integrated with the UWS testbed.

- XR-enabled User Equipment is tested to be compatible with the UWS testbed and are in place for students to use.
- Reliable 5G connectivity for the RAN is required, and ideally, beyond 5G RAN, it would be desired to test towards 6G capabilities truly.
- Internet connectivity is tested to be sufficient for remote access and operating XR.
- End-users consent to participate in the experimentation and provide feedback, after ethical approval.

4.2.2.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

Figure 16 shows the overall architecture of this use case. In this layered architecture, lecturers and professors in the delivery team employ wearable devices and haptic controllers to manipulate a virtual world where a complete 6G network topology is represented, allowing them to control the delivery of the class being able to provide immersive, adaptive 3D realistic representation of the entire infrastructure. This is achieved by creating advanced applications for that particular purpose based on several toolkits, such as MRTK⁶⁴ and Unity⁶⁵, to create the virtual world. This information will be distributed to those remote attending classes. The use case may include multi-campus delivery, where some students physically attend the class in a classroom while others attend remotely from home.

It is noted that the challenges associated with this educational environment where there will be heterogeneous networks for each of the students and quality of services which is a significant challenge and combining this with the ultrahigh requirements in terms of latency, bandwidth, jittering and packet losses required by the holographic and haptic communications. The use case will be complemented with an application that allows performing the digital twin to be performed over the same testbed used to this use case. It will enable lecturers and professors to monitor the complete infrastructure and deliver such operational capabilities to the students to deliver hands-on experience over the actual infrastructure.

Figure 16: Overall architecture of UC-EDU-2

⁶⁴ Mixed Reality Toolkit (MRTK) is an open source software development kit (SDK) developed by Microsoft in 2016 for the development of mixed reality (MR) and augmented reality (AR) software applications. For more informative details also see, among others: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Mixed_Reality_Toolkit

⁶⁵ More relevant information can be found at: <https://unity.com/features/ui-toolkit>

Figure 17: UWS infrastructure topology for UC-EDU-2

Figure 17 shows the topology for the UWS infrastructure, consisting of several layers including cloud-managed infrastructure (Edge and Core), transport, management and control, and interdomain (Access layer) for Internet access outside of the university. It is noted that Edge nodes are deployed in the infrastructure, which will be further developed to support the demanding XR application in this use case. RAN capabilities are subject to upgrades to yield more reliable and capable performance in line with beyond 5G (towards 6G) expectations.

4.2.2.4 Requirements

Table 52 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 53 contains the performance requirements.

Table 52: Use Case UC-EDU-2 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Reliable and higher performance (beyond) 5G RAN	Upgrade the testbed to have a more reliable and supportive RAN for the testing, especially for 3rd parties.
FR2	Edge computing	Edge computing is required to process massive amounts of data and run the XR service applications closer to the students, reducing latency and improving the user experience.
FR3	XR infrastructure and UE	Achieve the essence of the vision presented in Figure 16 in

		terms of both network XR components and user XR equipment.
FR4	6G-PATH platform	Northbound and southbound components in the 6G-PATH reference architecture.

Table 53: Use Case UC-EDU-2 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Ultra-high bandwidth	Perceived high bandwidth for the XR application
PR2	Ultra-low latency	Perceived low latency for the XR application
PR3	Ultra-low packet Loss	Minimal E2E packet loss

4.2.2.5 Validation

4.2.2.5.1 Test Cases

Table 48 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 54: Use Case UC-EDU-2 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Validate the local communication infrastructure	Test and validate the local communication quality in the UWS lab, with upgraded RAN/Edge capabilities for the XR application.
TC2: Validate the remote communication infrastructure	Test and validate the remote connectivity and communication quality for remote users and 3rd parties.
TC3: Validate the 6G-PATH platform	Test and validate the components integrated from the project, and the existing UWS components.
TC4: Validate the XR user equipment	Test and validate the XR hardware and software required to deliver and manage the XR application.
TC5: E2E UC-level testing	Test and validate if the E2E XR application works as expected, and apply mitigation if needed.

4.2.2.5.2 Validation Tools

The outcomes of UC-EDU-2 will be validated empirically using objective or subjective methods. The measurements of KPIs will leverage the lab-based monitoring tools available in the testbed and may be enhanced by additional monitoring tools described in the reference architecture. The measurement of KVI will be based on questionnaires to collect feedback from stakeholders such as students, using Mean Opinion Scores on a 5-point Scale.

4.2.2.5.3 KPIs and KVIs

Tables 55 and 56 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 55: Use Case UC-EDU-2 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Perceived usefulness	High perceived usefulness ratio for teaching and learning experience.	>70%
Newly developed XR application	Develop new XR teaching and learning materials.	≥ 2
Visualised devices	Number of supported networked devices to be visualised in the same topology in the subject domain (5G and beyond).	≥ 1000
Visualised connections	Number of supported connections among devices to be visualised in the same topology in the subject domain (5G and beyond).	≥ 2000
Key technological concept visualisation	Number of visualised key technological concepts (visual representation) in the subject domain (5G and beyond).	≥ 3 (e.g., virtual machines, multitenancy, virtual equipment and interfaces, which would be difficult to explain without XR-based visualisation).
Key business scenario visualisation	Number of visualised key business roles and scenarios (visual representation) in the subject domain (5G and beyond).	≥ 2 (e.g., Infrastructure Service Provider and Infrastructure Service Consumer and their business scenarios, which would be difficult to explain without XR-based visualisation).

Table 56: Use Case UC-EDU-2 KVIs description

KVI	Description	Objective
Student satisfaction	High satisfaction rate from the students.	$\geq 70\%$
Academic performance	High student performance vs. the performance in a control group (understanding the complicated 5G and beyond topology).	$\geq 20\%$ (compared with a control group)

4.2.2.6 Expected Outcomes

Driving 6G Development: The deployment of 6G technology from 6G-PATH for “Classroom of Future” can provide an ideal testbed for the development and optimisation of 6G considering the multi-level requirements posed by 6G infrastructure including Edge computing, XR devices, network and application performance as well as user experience. Testing this 6G use case in a realistic environment, can accelerate deriving various related KPIs from these different perspectives to drive further development of new 6G technologies and applications.

Improving Learning Outcomes: By providing an immersive and engaging learning experience based on XR and 6G, this Classroom of Future can significantly enhance students’ learning effectiveness. Using XR technologies can create a more interactive and stimulating learning environment, presenting a new world of 5G/6G technological insights to the students in a visualised fashion not existing in the real world, which can increase student engagement and retention.

Enhancing Collaborative Learning: Such a Classroom of the Future will support highly collaborative learning, an essential feature of the modern education environment. By facilitating real-time collaboration and group discussions, students can work together to solve problems and learn from each other, nurturing the culture of being a team player, an essential personal merit to handle complex issues in real-world projects.

Enhancing Accessibility: The use of such a Classroom of the Future can boost the accessibility of education, especially for students who are unable to attend physical classes due to distance or other factors (e.g., financial difficulties). By providing a highly realistic virtual learning environment with capabilities to visualise the world behind the hardware and other 5G/6G elements, students can access high-quality education from anywhere at an affordable cost.

4.2.2.7 Risk Assessment

Table 57 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified of likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 57: Use Case UC-EDU-2 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	RAN capacity/performance is not sufficient	M	H	Try to upgrade RAN; explore Edge computing.
R2	XR application is too demanding in terms of resources	M	H	Try to increase the resources through smarter MANO etc.; explore Edge computing and network slicing.
R3	Multiple 3rd parties would like to run their testing simultaneously	L	M	Try to schedule appropriately to distribute the workload for the testbed.
R4	3rd party use cases require deploying components that are not compatible with the testbed	M	H	Try to convert the components into a compatible form.

4.2.3 UC-EDU-3 – XR health training

In this use case, we plan to showcase how immersive technologies (AR/VR/XR), Beyond-5G (B5G) and 6G communication systems, Edge and Cloud computing platforms, machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) can be used to support high-quality education and training for healthcare, ultimately enabling advanced healthcare education systems.

4.2.3.1 Motivation

Healthcare education involves many practical medical tasks that students need to practice. These practical components are vital for the well-rounded education of our healthcare professionals. The practical training is typically acquired in two ways: working in simulated environments with manikins and taking part in real medical scenarios.

Manikins simulate human anatomy and physiology, allowing learners to extend their knowledge by experiencing lifelike situations. Advanced manikins incorporate cutting-edge computer technology and provide a realistic patient representation to simulate various physical conditions and reactions. When training on manikins the teacher is usually situated in the room next door and provides the voice response of the manikin and also controls specific reactions in response to the actions taken by the students (such as the change in breathing when the students move the head of the manikin to clear its airways). The more authentic the scenarios simulated with the manikins are, the better the learning experience.

Examples of training in real medical scenarios include accompanying senior physicians on hospital rounds, observing complex surgeries first-hand by acting as an assistant to the chief surgeon and accompanying emergency medical responders on their cases as observers. Since these components involve patients, often under considerable pain and stress, only a small batch of students can be accommodated within each training session. The time spent by students/trainees in such practical scenarios greatly enhances their confidence and competence as they start their careers as doctors, nurses and emergency responders.

Incorporating AR, VR and Extended Reality (XR) into medical training creates an immersive learning experience that can prepare nurses and medical professionals for the challenges they may encounter in their future practice with greater efficiency and efficacy. Most of the current use of immersive learning for healthcare revolves around an offline virtual learning environment. Several commercial tools, such as *Cassette*⁶⁶ and *Holopatient*⁶⁷, use AR/VR/XR to provide repeatable training experiences across various use cases. These tools can replicate emergency scenarios, and facilitates patient role-playing surgical training. With offline immersive learning, the students learn without real-world repercussions by working within a virtual scene. The feedback is also virtual and pre-designed. We propose to extend such immersive environments to allow for learning in interaction with live, real-world learning environments – with real implications and feedback. We propose developing a methodology that allows paramedic nursing students virtually to participate in remote (simulated or real) acute/ambulance scenarios in an immersive yet unobtrusive manner.

⁶⁶ Airbus Secure Land Communications. (2024, October 17). SmarTWISP ecosystem. Retrieved from <https://www.securelandcommunications.com/smartwisp/>

⁶⁷ Holomedicine Association. (2024, October 17). Hyperrealistic holographic simulated patients. Retrieved from <https://www.gigxr.com/holopatient/>

Key Pain Points

Authenticity is a “key” pain point in the simulated medical scenario with a manikin. Creating realistic scenarios is limited by the scenario being staged in a classroom with the teachers and observing students being next door. Allowing the manikin to be remotely controlled over greater distances and the observing students to remotely take part in the scenario in an interactive and immersive way opens up the possibility of staging the simulation in realistic environments, for instance placing the manikin in an ambulance or at a staged accident scene.

For the training in real medical scenarios, scalability and the associated costs are the main pain points. As only a small number of students can be accommodated in a given medical situation, scaling this training type is challenging and costly. As the medical emergencies involved when a student, for instance, accompanies an ambulance cannot be controlled, it is also hard to cover all the critical scenarios required, and the training may not be very efficient. Allowing students to take part in various medical scenarios remotely, will enable them to scale the training in a cost-efficient way and can also help with coverage, as the training scenarios selected for remote participation may be chosen to complement each other.

From a technical viewpoint, the “key” challenges for the above training scenarios are very similar. Multimodal input in video, audio and sensor data must be captured at the medical site, conveyed over the network and turned into an immersive experience for the students at the remote site. The simulated scenario is further challenged by the need to remotely control the manikin’s voice and specific physical reactions. Some of the physical reactions in response to an action need to be immediate and, as the voice represents a face-to-face (F2F) conversation with the manikin, the tolerance to delay is lower as compared to an audio conference.

4.2.3.2 Scenarios Description

While XR-based healthcare education is applicable in multiple learning scenarios, we focus here on remote emergency responder training. In this scenario, we explore the possibility of bringing the training of ambulance nurses to a remote location, such as a classroom, in an immersive way.

For this, medical professionals wear recording equipment. Once on the scene, every first responder’s video camera records a scene viewed by the wearer and streams it to a server on board the ambulance. The microphone captures the voice and streams it to the server. Additionally, ambient sound, as heard by the wearer, is streamed to the server. Sensors are placed on the patients to capture vital signs and other medical data, with the sensor data again streamed to the server. In the simulated scenario, the sensor data is produced by the manikin. The server may collate and forward the streams for remote viewing over a B5G/6G network connection.

An application server receives all the streams and performs any needed pre-processing steps, such as:

- Scene creation: The various video streams are combined to create one cohesive scene that is as close to the original 3D scene within reason. The audio streams are also integrated into the scene in a way consistent with the sounds heard in the original scene. Furthermore, various sensor readings may be embedded into the scene. The person or position being measured may also be labelled with the value.
- AI-based analysis: AI tools that can search the scene may be further utilised to guide learning within the classroom. The AI may, for instance, perform information extraction and augmentation and offer assessment/prediction of the patient’s status by analysing the collected data.

The reconstructed scene is streamed to audio-video peripherals, e.g., monitors or head-mounted displays (HMDs) worn by the students. In the simulated scenario, bidirectional audio communication channels and manikin control are established. While bi-directional audio communication support is also expected for the training in real medical scenarios, communication with the first responders may need to be restricted to avoid intrusion.

4.2.3.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

B5G/6G systems, Edge/Cloud computing and ML/AI are vital for achieving high-quality, immersive and real-time health education. To ensure a high QoS/QoE for the students, we envision XR health education scenarios that demand low-latency transmission of multimodal data flows, some of which have high data rates (e.g., 360-degree video). Before being consumed by the trainees, the multimodal inputs undergo efficient processing, where ML/AI can provide additional functionalities, including information extraction and augmentation, and assessment/prediction of the patient's status by analysing the collected data, to mention a few.

The use case comprises two locations, that is: communication networks and computing platforms. The first location of importance is called the medical site. It is where the healthcare scenario for a specific training session occurs, for example an ambulance where first responders operate in an emergency case. The other location refers to the training site, where the students receive training. A vital feature of this use case is that the trainees experience the remote events at the medical site in a high-quality, immersive and real-time manner. Hence, the training site is where the composite real-time data flow is consumed, after possibly being augmented with additional historical information and pedagogical references that are, for example, retrieved from dedicated databases.

The two end-locations defined above will contain functionality for capture and render, respectively. The communication network and computing platform are expected to be highly distributed and flexibly instantiated along the path. We envision at least the following main components:

- **Multimodal capture and processing:** HW/SW used to collect and process inputs that are typically multimodal and realistically synthesise the scenario at the medical site. Such HW/SW include cameras for collecting high-quality video, microphones for audio input, speakers for audio output (e.g., for bidirectional communication with the training site), heterogeneous sensors for body/environment data collection (e.g., temperature, oxygen level, blood pressure, heartbeats and humidity).
- **Manikin:** The manikin is only used in the simulation scenario. In this scenario, the manikin creates the sensor values mentioned above.
- **Rendering devices:** the training site is equipped with HW/SW that consumes the XR flow, such as audio-video peripherals, e.g., monitors or HMDs.
- **Computing (and storage) node(s):** They form an end-to-end distributed computing platform that provides the functionalities for generating the XR content, by coherently integrating the multimodal inputs collected at the medical site and further non-real-time information. Different nodes may execute different functionalities towards content generation, for example data synchronisation, encoding and augmentation. Depending on each functionality's computing and latency demands, nodes may be deployed at different locations over the Edge-Cloud continuum. For example, nodes that execute heavy ML/AI-based training and inference tasks on the collected/historical data could need to be deployed at the system edges, e.g., near the medical site, to satisfy latency requirements.
- **App server(s):** They provide access to the XR content by end-users. As for the computing nodes, one or several app servers may be deployed at different locations depending on the identified functional requirements (e.g., latency towards the end-users).
- **Communication nodes:** They form the end-to-end communication network between medical and training sites. An end-to-end B5G/6G system will be deployed to achieve stringent QoS/QoE requirements. The system includes end-devices at both locations that can connect to a hybrid RAN and the Core Network (CN) providing the control plane and possibly deployed in a distributed manner (i.e., different CN functions deployed in different nodes). The Edge-Cloud computing platform is instantiated on top of the communication network so that the functionalities are distributed and being flexible.

As described above, the use case comprises a medical site, a training site, communication networks and computing platforms.

The high-level topology of the use case is illustrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: High-level topology for the remote emergency responder training scenario

The nursing science department at KAU is the owner of use case. They have the manikin and the connection to the ambulance services needed for some of the experiments and demonstrations of the use case. The ambulance nursing students will be engaged in the experiments.

Computer Science at KAU is in charge of the 5G testbed used in the experiments and they are responsible for coordinating the technical work to set up the use case in the testbed.

RedZinc has the HW/SW to capture the video at the medical site and distribute it to the training site. The video router from Red Zinc will be deployed in the Edge Cloud at KAU.

4.2.3.4 Requirements

Table 58 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 59 contains the performance requirements.

Table 58: Use Case UC-EDU-3 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Audio/video capture	Capturing video and audio streams at the medical site.
FR2	Data capture	Capturing of medical and other sensor data at the medical site.
FR3	Manikin control	Remote control of the manikin (only for simulated scenarios).
FR4	Communication	Communication of multimodal data between the medical site and the training site.
FR5	Edged deployment	Edged deployment with data and AI processing to create the XR content.
FR6	XR environment	XR environment for students engaged in immersive learning.

Table 59: Use Case UC-EDU-3 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Uplink capacity	High uplink capacity for upload of video and other types of streams.
PR2	Packet loss rate	Low packet-loss to avoid interference in real-time streaming.
PR3	Latency	Low latency is needed to provide an interactive immersive experience and allow control of the manikin.

4.2.3.5 Validation

4.2.3.5.1 Test Cases

The use case will be built stepwise to establish the different components involved and gradually increase the complexity, as outlined in Table 60. TC1 and TC2 are used to establish parts of the technical infrastructure needed to realise the use case and will include functional and performance validation. TC3 to TC5 involve all components needed for a complete simulated or real medical scenario and will also involve validation tests with teachers and/or students in addition to functional and performance validations. Table 60 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 60 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 60: Use Case UC-EDU-3 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Video capture	This test case will integrate the BlueEye camera from RedZinc ⁶⁸ in the 5G testbed at KAU to validate that the device is compatible with the testbed and that the video can be captured and rendered on an audio-video peripheral at a remote location.
TC2: Video capture with Edge deployment	This test case will extend TC1 by integrating the video router from RedZinc within the KAU Edge infrastructure.
TC3a: Manikin integration	This test case will integrate the manikin control in the scenario described above, using an independent channel. This aims to validate that the manikin can be integrated with the 5G network. This test case applies to the simulated scenario described above.
TC3b: Sensor kit integration	This test case will integrate the RedZinc GreenBox sensor kit ⁶⁹ into the scenario created in TC2. This test case applies to the actual medical scenario described above, but tests will use volunteers rather than patients.

⁶⁸ For further information regarding the RedZinc BlueEye camera, also see: <https://redzinc.net/>

⁶⁹ Also see, *inter-alia*: <https://redzinc.net/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/BlueEye-Virtual-Ward-brochure-Nov-2023.pdf>

TC4: 360-degree video integration	This test case adds the capture of 360-degree video to TC3 above, allowing students to experience a richer context for the medical scenario.
TC5: HMD rendering	This test case integrates HMDs on the training site, providing a different viewing experience for the students than the audio-video peripheral used in TC3 and TC4.

4.2.3.5.2 Validation Tools

Three scales will be used to evaluate the medical scenarios: the Ambulance Nurse Competence Scale (ANCS), the Paramedic Global Rating Scale (PRGS) and the System Usability Scale (SUS). These three scales are developed for purposes relevant to the use case. The ANCS scale is a tool for measuring the competencies of specialist ambulance nurses; the PRGS is a tool for assessing technical skills in emergency simulation for education and training purposes, and; the SUS is recommended for measuring the perceived usability of technology. To “deepen” the understanding of using simulation scenarios with digital technology to increase authenticity and realism, enhance the sense of participation and enable learning in paramedic nursing, interviews will be conducted with participating students.

In addition, standard tools such as iPerf and Ping will be used to establish the performance of the underlying communication infrastructure.

4.2.3.5.3 KPIs and KVIs

Tables 61 and 62 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 61: Use Case UC-EDU-3 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Uplink capacity	High uplink capacity for upload of video and other types of streams.	> 20 Mbps
Packet loss rate	Low packet-loss to avoid interference in real-time streaming.	<=1% (frame loss rate)
Latency	Low latency is needed to provide an interactive, immersive experience and allow control of the manikin.	< 20 ms, extended to 50 ms if object detection is done at the Edge and head movement is tracked at the HMDs. 30 - 50 ms for the manikin feedback.

Table 62: Use Case UC-EDU-3 KVIs description

KVI	Description	Objective
Increased realism	Fraction of students that feel the solutions	PGRS (>=3), SUS (>=68)

	contribute to increased training realism.	
Increased engagement	Fraction of students that feel the solutions improved their engagement in the training.	PGRS (>=3), SUS (>=68)
Technology acceptance	Fraction of students that feel 5G/6G and XR bring a positive benefit for the training.	SUS (>=68)

4.2.3.6 Expected Outcomes

6G requirements: The planned use case evaluations will contribute a further understanding of the requirements of immersive healthcare education and how they relate to network KPIs, serving as important input for refining 6G requirements in the context of immersive experiences.

Health education: The developed use case is expected to contribute to enhanced competence and sense of authenticity in students within health education in the specialist nurse ambulance program. For simulated training scenarios, immersive technologies and 5G/6G will bring increased flexibility and allow more realistic training scenarios to be constructed, thereby addressing a key pain point in current practices. For the real medical training scenario, the ability remotely to take part in such scenarios in an immersive fashion will reduce the heavy load on the very few scenarios with real-life patients demanding physical in-person participation and instead increase the possibility of remotely participating in different scenarios, thereby improving scalability and reducing the cost of training, addressing key pain points in the scenario. While the benefits of the simulated scenario are directly realisable, the benefits of the real specialist nurse training scenario require regulatory support.

Business impact: The activities associated with the use case will demonstrate the benefits of B5G/6G and XR technologies in health education. The use case will connect health education actors with actors in the B5G/6G domain, industries and SMEs developing XR technologies. Such connections will foster the uptake of advanced communication and XR solutions within health education and the healthcare sector in general, leading to new business opportunities. Training students using B5G/6G and XR technologies will increase the awareness of the potential of such technologies for eHealth among medical professionals, further supporting future uptake.

4.2.3.7 Risk Assessment

Table 63 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 63: Use Case UC-EDU-3 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Failure to integrate the manikin with the 5G infrastructure.	M	L	The capabilities of the manikin and its potential integration in the use case will be established early in the project. Should this not be feasible, focus can be put on the actual medical scenario instead.

R2	Failure to integrate software and architectural components needed for the use case.	L	M	The system will be developed agilely, with continuous integration of different components, allowing simplifications in some parts of the system if needed. Standardised and open-source solutions will be used as much as possible.
R3	Video capturing, AI processing or VR rendering may be too slow, leading to an unsatisfactory user experience even if the B5G/6G connectivity is sufficient.	M	M	The system will be developed agilely, with continuous testing of different components. If needed, less complex content and processing can be used.
R4	Failure to meet eHealth education use case requirements.	L	H	Health education teaching staff will directly contribute to the use case specification, and the learning environment will be developed in an agile fashion; multiple small-scale user tests will provide feedback on the design.

4.3 Health

4.3.1 UC-HEALTH-1 – 3D hydrogel patches

This use case aims to validate and evaluate an innovative approach to provide a higher level of patient care for patients with chronic wounds in need of customised patches. This use case leverages a new 5G/6G-enabled medical service for remote areas, relying on nomadic micro-networks that provide reliable and secure connectivity in the patient's area when and where needed. A nurse will be visiting patients at home or care facilities and bringing dedicated devices for the execution of the specialised diagnostics for correct wound assessment, stereo 3D model of the wound (high-resolution multidimensional observation data), the printing of tailored hydrogel patches, and teleconference. These operations will be supported by expert personnel and doctors via remote communication from the hospital to ensure proper handling of the equipment, diagnostics, and instructions for applying the required patches and treatment. The nomadic micro-network will be deployed from the nurse's vehicle, acting as an extension of the hospital's campus network. The nomadic micro-network can sense the local environment and select appropriate unused frequencies to avoid disturbing existing communication. It can discover and choose the most appropriate backhaul at the given location (terrestrial or satellite) to connect with the central hospital campus network.

4.3.1.1 Motivation

The success of wound therapy is based on the one hand on the identification and treatment of the underlying disease that causes the symptom wound and, on the other hand, on the correct wound assessment, which is the prerequisite for adequate wound therapy appropriate to the stage. The dynamic course requires a continuous adaptation of the therapy depending on the current wound condition. Considering the current situation it becomes evident that the currently available technology cannot produce the necessary image quality for telemedical "real-time" care, requiring that patients visit hospital premises. Alternatively, telemedical wound therapy would drastically reduce patients' need to be transported to hospitals, significantly reducing the cost of health services. A high-resolution, multimodal sensor approach is necessary to enable a valid assessment of the wound. Some examples are: The still-applied dressing already gives an initial indication of e.g., the moist nature of the wound; an infected wound shows, e.g., coloured coatings depending on the bacteria; certain bacteria show an intrinsic fluorescence under UV-near light (450nm) and thus allow conclusions to be drawn about the species, from which a targeted anti-infective therapy can be derived. The wound environment, wound margin and wound bed must be assessed to determine the appropriate therapy and the interval until the next wound treatment. Multiple studies show that telemedicine interventions can significantly help improve wound healing, control blood glucose and blood pressure and reduce the need for hospital visits or surgical interventions (amputations) [29], [30], [31], [32]. However, distributing such dedicated devices to each patient does not represent a solution due to the high production costs. A solution where telemedicine is provided while access to high-quality medical equipment is needed.

Key Pain Points

- Lack of connectivity for field nurses in remote areas.
- Lack of secure and reliable connectivity, private connectivity for devices in remote areas.
- Integrated connectivity (NPN like) for hospital owned devices with the hospital network (public internet is not a choice due to the very high privacy requirements).
- Difficult objective tracking of wound status.
- Difficult computing of wound depth, volume and radius.

- Lack of a decision support system for patches regarding caring materials to use and their amount, e.g., in the context of a 3D hydrogel patch.

4.3.1.2 Scenarios Description

A nursing professional visits multiple patients with chronic wounds during the day. At the location of each of the patients, the nurse parks the vehicle in front of the patient's premises, takes the specific medical equipment to the patient's premises and executes the wound treatment while using the network placed in the vehicle as a local radio network provider and as a relay to the hospital premises across multiple backhauls. With this system, the nursing professional can use wireless connectivity to perform different tasks, and the on-vehicle-placed Edge network has storage to answer specific privacy requirements. As the nurse moves between the multiple target locations, there is no need for a continuous network in space or time. Instead, a small local network is deployed when and where needed.

Scenario 1: Digital documenting

The nurse uses the Nurse Care App on the smartphone connected to the Edge network to assess the wound via a questionnaire and takes wound 2D pictures and 3D scans. The information is sent to the medical services headquarters, where further data processing.

Scenario 2: OTT Multimedia services

Using OTT apps, the nurse can contact the wound expert at the medical services headquarters and develop a treatment solution. This is when the 3D model of the patch is generated based on the wound expert's requirements (e.g., material).

Scenario 3: Patch printing

The printer is also connected to the Edge network via a hardware and software adapter (e.g., based on Raspberry Pie). The Nurse Care App notifies the nurse when the 3D model is available. The nurse can then request the printer to print the hydrogel patch.

4.3.1.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

The high-level topology of the use case includes the following off-the-self hardware components:

- 3D Scanner: The partners have validated the Seal 3D Scanner, which was considered easier to integrate because it supports multiple operating systems, including Android. One can also mount it on a handheld support with a mobile phone. During validation on laptops, it ran ok, producing the 3D model estimated to take several minutes, and creating a 3D model of around 50 MB. However, the process became complicated when combined with the mobile phone. One still needs a laptop to build the model, and a transfer between the mobile phone app and the laptop must occur, after which the 3D model is built on the laptop. Further, using an application that creates 3D models and runs on mobile phones was validated for scanning objects and is currently considered a more user-friendly approach.
- 3D (bio) printer: The integration of the 3D bioprinter will come in the second version of the prototype. Due to the high purchase price, the Creality Ender 3D printer⁷⁰ was selected as a non-bio 3D printer that can be modified into a bio-printer.

⁷⁰ For further details also see, *inter-alia*: <https://www.creality.com/products/ender-3-3d-printer>

- Customer premises entity (CPE)/mobile phone – a device for each 3D scanner device (when used with a laptop, it will be replaced by a 5G-dongle) and 3D (bio) printer to enable the communication of the devices across the NPN network (from the Edge to central node)
- 5G RAN equipment – a small form factor 5G RAN suitable for deployment as part of the nurse’s vehicle.
- Transport networks – subscriptions to 4G/5G mobile network operators and/or too low earth orbit satellite operators, including the devices needed to transport the data across these third-party networks.

Figure 19 depicts the high-level topology of the UC.

Figure 19: UC-HEALTH-1 high-level topology

Beyond 5G Network

- Packet Core: Control plane (in the Headquarter NPN): AMF, SMF, PCF, AUSF, UDM, NRF, NEF (towards Apps) – enabling the centralised authentication, authorisation, mobility and QoS control of the devices. A centralised solution allows a significant privacy as well as efficient processing for the reduced number of devices.
- Transport Control: A new Edge router component enabling the secure connectivity of the remote Edge networks across multiple transport networks (e.g., satellite networks or public 4G/5G networks). We expect that the Edge router will become a significant component of the 6G networks as it controls the security and reliability of the link.
- Local RAN: It is the radio equipment enabling the nomadic node radio network. The prototype would be implemented with 5G RAN to showcase the advantages of the technology for use. This should be replaced with a 6G RAN with dynamic features in the next release.
- UEs: Modems connected to the specific devices which would connect to the nomadic network. As the RAN, they will be implemented using 5G in the project showcasing the use case. They can be later replaced with 6G UEs when available.
- Packet Core UPF: user plane functions that are deployed both at the edge and at the central location. Both UPFs would include a reduced functionality compared to 5G, adapted to the specific privacy and security requirements of communication while simultaneously removing the overhead of charging and lawful interception. Furthermore, UPFs would not be involved in handover procedures as transport control would ensure mobility.

Nurse Care App

- Wound documentation, 3D model upload, 3D patch printing, check indicated caring materials.
- (interface to or separate) OTT Multimedia Client.

Admin & Care Portal

- Wound documentation visualisation, 3D patch adjustment, select appropriate caring materials.
- (interface to or separate) OTT Multimedia Client.

Patient Data Storage Server

- Based on the HL7 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standard [33] and together with its database, it stores the patient records related to the nurse visits.

Data Access Control Server

- Provides access control service enabling access for the patient and the medical personnel to the Patient Data Storage Server using role-based policies and patient-specific information (e.g., caring doctor).

4.3.1.4 Requirements

Table 64 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 65 contains the performance requirements.

Table 64: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Connectivity Availability	5-nines (dependent on the available transport networks at the location).
FR2	Audio-Video Call Reliability	Dependent on the available transport networks at the location and the application software.
FR3	Transport network availability	At least two transport networks (e.g., terrestrial or satellite) will be included.
FR4	Secure communication	Centralised authentication and authorisation at the hospital premises.
FR5	Secure backhaul communication	Additional securing of the backhaul communication over the transport network.
FR6	Network coverage	Additional securing of the backhaul communication over the transport network.
FR7	Device connectivity	The specific devices should be able to connect to the local NPN Network.

Table 65: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Number of connected devices	The hospital enterprise network should be able to connect 10.000 devices, encompassing all the devices that nurses use during home visits.
PR2	Number of connected local networks	The network should be capable connecting 100 Edge networks representing the number of on-premise visiting nurses.
PR3	Network capacity	The local, as well as the transport network, should be appropriately dimensioned to cover the capacity requirements of the use case > 2Mbps.
PR4	End-to-end delay	The end-to-end delay should remain in the expected use case requirements <1s.

4.3.1.5 Validation

4.3.1.5.1 Test Cases

Table 66 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 66: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Establishment of backhaul	Checking if the backhaul can be established over the selected transport networks.
TC2: Establishment of secure backhaul	Checking if the backhaul can be secured with available security mechanisms (e.g., WireGuard ⁷¹).
TC3: Establishment of end-to-end network	Checking if the nomadic RAN can execute the specific NG-AP operations with the hospital core network.
TC4: Establishment of the data path network	Checking if local and home-to-hospital routed networks are functioning.
TC5: Establishment of the end-to-end connectivity	Checking the UE registration, session establishment, session termination and UE deregistration. Checking the establishment of an end-to-end data path.
TC6: RAN capable 3D Scanner	Checking the extension of the 3D scanner with UE capabilities. Checking the end-to-end data path connectivity.
TC7: RAN capable 3D (bio)printer	Checking the extension of the 3D (bio) printer with UE capabilities. Checking the end-to-end data path connectivity.
TC8: End-to-end use case performance	Checking if the nurse use case has the appropriate <1s delay and

⁷¹ For more details also see: <https://www.wireguard.com/>

the >2Mbps capacity.

4.3.1.5.2 Validation Tools

- End-to-End Testing: ping for testing connectivity establishment and iPerf for testing the connectivity throughput of a device to the central node and Postman for testing access to the eHealth backend services. The benchmarking tool of the Open5GCore for workload generation.
- Laboratory Testing: The size of the wound dressing is measured to assess the suitability of the dressing for the scanned wound. In a laboratory setting, the sterility of the dressing is evaluated through the use of a Petri dish⁷².
- Usability Testing: Nurses are engaged in usability testing to evaluate the solution's user interface, ease of use and overall user experience.
- Survey after field trials: Questionnaires with opinionated questions on a 5-point-Likert-Scale⁷³ will be used to collect feedback from stakeholders to the KVs.

4.3.1.5.3 KPIs and KVs

Tables 67 and 68 define the KPIs and KVs for this use case.

Table 67: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Edge connectivity	Establishment of the connectivity between the Edge and the central network over third party backhuls.	<5s for all transport networks
End-to-end connectivity establishment	Establishment of the connectivity for the UEs	<2s for the establishment of the end-to-end connectivity
End-to-end data path	End-to-end data path.	<200ms end-to-end data path
Number of devices	The number of devices that can connect and exchange the end-to-end data.	10.000 devices each with its data bearer
The fit of wound dressing	Suitability of patch dimensions and texture.	> 95% accuracy in fit of dimensions
Sterility of wound dressing	Confirmation of the sterility of the hydrogel patch through microbiological tests (rule outgrowth of bacteria or fungi).	No growth after > 72h of incubation

⁷² A Petri dish (alternatively known as a Petri plate or cell-culture dish) is a shallow transparent lidded dish that biologists use to hold growth medium in which cells can be cultured, originally, cells of bacteria, fungi and small mosses.

⁷³ A 5-point Likert Scale offers five different options for the respondents to choose from. The options include two extremes, two intermediate, and one neutral opinion. This scale can be used for measuring agreement, likelihood, frequency, importance, quality and a lot more. For further information also see, *inter-alia*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Likert_scale

Duration of intervention	Average time from wound scan, analysis and printing to final application of hydrogel patch.	< 4h
Wound healing rate*	Improvement in wound healing over a set period using the customised hydrogel patch compared to standard wound dressing.	Increase healing rate by 10% over baseline
Infection rate post application*	Percentage of patients developing infections post application of the customised patch compared to standard wound dressing.	Reduce infection by 10%0
Correctness of wound scan and analysis	Accuracy in capturing and analysing wound dimensions, healing stages, complications and characteristics.	Achieve 95% accuracy in scan and analysis

* cannot be evaluated due to lack of clinical trial setting and project scope

Table 68: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 KVis description

KVI	Description	Objective
Public health	Providing a better health service to the patients' by visiting patients (reducing the number of missed hospital visits) while at the same time serving multiple patients with a reduced number of highly trained personal.	Use the same devices and a single doctor in the hospital for a high number of distributed patients who do not leave their premises.
Enhanced Care Quality	Improvement in accessibility and quality of wound care for patients.	Increase the number of successfully treated wounds.
Reduction in healing time	Comparing the duration of wound healing between conventional dressings and customised 3D-printed patches.	Reduce average healing time with customised patches.
Complication Rate Decrease	Reduction in the rate of complications (e.g. infections, delayed healing) using the customised patches compared to standard dressings.	Decrease of complication rate.
Increasing quality of life	Reduction in visits to the doctor and hospital stays due to therapy of chronic wounds and possible nosocomial infections.	Decrease of visits to the doctor / hospital stays.
Societal Upgrade	Better adoption of the eHealth services through reducing the need for travelling of chronic patients.	Use nomadic networks which can visit multiple patients on the same day.
Societal Acceptability	Providing a basis for home health services.	Commodity services at patients' home.
Sustainability	Reduce the number of travels of patients in hospitals.	Use a single nurse's travel plan to cover multiple patients.

Privacy	Extending the privacy of the hospital data to the nurses' vehicle.	Include patients' data into the hospital-owned vehicles and secure its exchange across third-party transport networks.
Environmental impact / waste reduction	Reduction in waste generated through packaging and disposal compared to traditional wound care products.	Achieve a reduction in waste related to conventional wound care dressings.
Cost Reduction	Lower costs of customised wound dressings in the long term at a higher scaling rate.	Achieve less cost compared to conventional wound dressings.

4.3.1.6 Expected Outcomes

- Usable setup for providing connectivity for field nurses.
- Accurate wound scans and analysis with its characteristics (matching in diagnostics criteria and dimensions).
- Decrease healing time and complication rate.
- Contribution to public health and societal well-being.
- High precision and real-time communication with doctors or outpatient wound clinics due to the use of 5G/6G --> Agreement on efficient and appropriate wound care.
- Long-term cost reduction by reducing complication rate.

4.3.1.7 Risk Assessment

Table 69 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 69: Use Case UC-HEALTH-1 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Not an integrated market of devices	H	L	Integrating the communication technologies available in the device with 5G connectivity devices (e.g., phones or CPEs).
R2	Incompatibility of functionality on the mobile device (5G, 3D scanner)	M	M	Replace the mobile phone with a laptop, and replace the 3D scanner with a mobile App. The mobile App might not have the same scanning accuracy.
R3	Limitation of availability from Public MNO and/or satellite	M	H	Design a connectivity map where the nurses' car could be parked (not in the

				scope of the initial use case deployment where selected places will be used for demonstrations where connectivity was priorly tested).
R4	A small number of patients in the trial	M	H	Splitting the use case into different care units (Physician assistant and hospital, maybe elderly homes).
R5	Poor scan quality	L	H	The wound scanner has already been tested.
R6	Non-sterile wound dressings in incubation tests	M	M	Suitable sterilisation methods have been examined.

4.3.2 UC-HEALTH-2 – Elderly monitoring

This use case aims to validate and evaluate an innovative approach to provide more elderly monitoring and care. This use case relies on 5G-/6G-enabled networks to provide continuous monitoring of elderly through wearable devices and other non-invasive monitoring tools, which require real-time data analysis and processing to increase elderly security and increase their quality of life. The devices' real-time transmission of gathered data, assistant features and assisted workouts, through novel AI-powered data analysis, enables advanced automatic pre- and post-diagnostics and threat assessment that can “trigger” immediate intervention (emergency responders or care providers) and improve healthcare provider decision-making through better-informed data.

This use case aims to deploy an integrated monitoring tool in a set of controlled elderly populations with the following set of wearables, sensors and devices:

- Smartwatch with a multitude of sensors, advanced fall detection coupled with an analytics application analysing the patient data and assessing the risk of falls.
- Pain detection algorithm for smart wearable devices.
- 3D Body Tracking Sensor running the myReha Coaching App⁷⁴ acting as workout diary and training assistant.
- Telehealth platform for storing patient records and OTT multimedia services for regular teleconferencing between the elderly and their hospital doctors.

Besides the state-of-the-art sensors and knowledge gathered by these sensors, this use case aims to assess the feasibility and benefits of the usage of advanced sensors (such as pain detection, integrated sensors that include glucose measurement and in- and outdoor air quality) with Edge and Core data processing through AI-powered algorithms that can in real-time provide enhanced knowledge for the patient or residents and medical staff, but also input to the smart virtual assistant that can provide enhanced feedback and support to the elderly person. Some of the AI-powered algorithms to be used are: anomaly/threat detection (intelligent correlation of factors); advanced fall detection; pain assessment during workouts; several health indicators like HRV, skin temperature, atrial fibrillation detection, pain intensity; stress detection; sleep analysis; detect different gasses and smells.

4.3.2.1 Motivation

“We are getting older” is a good thing, but it also increases the risk of falling ill and being dependent on medical and nursing care. Moreover, almost every European country is facing challenges due to demographic changes and the shortage of health professionals. Different sensors “address” different aspects of the geriatric syndrome that the elderly must “face” when they age. Decreased mobility, cognitive impairment and continence problems, may lead to serious health problems that reduce quality of life (like falls, pressure ulcers, loss of orientation, skin irritation). Continuous monitoring of activity/mobility in wearable watches is an effective prevention and allows rapid intervention if needed; for example, prevention of pressure ulcers if a bedridden individual did not move for 2 hours, information on the location of individuals with dementia who lost their orientation. Besides an increase of patient safety, there is an enormous increase in quality of life – not only for the care-dependent individual but even more for the caregiver. Studies have shown that informal caregivers experience enormous stress, since they often do not understand the needs of their care dependent. Sensor-based information combined with an AI-driven recommendation on individual-based intervention are hugely beneficial.

Since this information is highly sensitive and private, a secure 6G Data transmission is prerequisite.

After the 60th living years, every individual faces a decrease in muscle tissue, resulting in sarcopenia in older age. This often leads to less activity and mobility, thus resulting in even more muscle tissue loss. To break this vicious

⁷⁴ For further details also see, *for example*: <https://www.nyra.health/en-us/app>

circle, it is crucial to perform exercises to maintain the “fitness” of the elderly. International guidelines recommend older adults should preferably do at least 150 min per week of moderate-intensity endurance-oriented exercise (e.g., 5 times 30 min/week) or perform at least 75 min/week of higher-intensity endurance exercise. Moreover, older adults should perform muscle-strengthening physical activities at least 2 days per week and perform balance exercises at least 3 days a week for fall prevention. Multimodal sensors may provide feedback about the success of the performed workouts and exercises and may improve the motivation to “keep on going” with this form of intervention. Healthcare professionals may control the exercise, and help therapists and trainers choose the best individual adequate exercise form. These interventions can provide life-long activity and mobility, which are prerequisites for participation and autonomy, and lead to a much higher quality of life. Regular exercise and continuous monitoring can provide multiple quality-of-life improvements for elderly people. Physical activity can improve cardiovascular health, increase strength and flexibility, and reduce the risk of chronic conditions. Maintaining physical independence is possible by engaging in workouts, which may minimise dependence on family members or caregivers. Furthermore, exercise has a positive impact on mental health, reducing symptoms of anxiety and depression and improving overall mood and cognitive function. Participating in workout groups and fitness classes can also foster social interaction, while smartwatches can provide additional motivation, accountability, and tracking of progress towards goals. Combining regular exercise and smartwatch usage can improve sleep quality, increase motivation, and provide several other quality-of-life benefits for elderly individuals.

Key Pain Points

- Lack of reliable and secure home network with continuity of security across a public network.
- Video of exercises sent to the therapist using 6G secure wireless transmission.
- Encouraging activity (mobility) in older people.
- Recognising changes in patients’ conditions or emergencies.
- Difficult objective tracking of mobility status of elderly people.
- Predict the risk of falls.

4.3.2.2 Scenarios Description

A patient is executing physical rehabilitation exercises at home using secure and reliable connectivity provided by her home 3GPP technologies-based network. The network is safe and reliable and connected over 3rd party backhauls to the central rehabilitation centre, where the data is processed centrally.

A patient is transparently monitored using a 5G smartwatch at home or in a nursing home. A secure connectivity is established at the rehabilitation centre where the data is gathered and processed to detect if there was a fall, if the health state has decreased, or if the risk of falling has increased.

4.3.2.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

The high-level topology of the use case is depicted in Figure 20, includes the following off-the-self hardware components:

- 3D Body Tracking Sensor – A device that runs an Android operating system on which myReha Coaching App is deployed. The device can be used with the associated SDK to create a representation of the patient’s skeleton.

- Customer Premises Entity (CPE)/mobile phone – A device for each 3D Body Tracking device to enable the communication of the devices across the NPN network (Edge to central).
- 5G RAN equipment – A small form factor 5G RAN suitable for deployment as part of the nurse’s vehicle.
- Transport networks – Subscriptions to 4G/5G mobile network operators and/or low earth orbit satellite operators, including the devices needed to transport the data across these third-party networks.

Beyond 5G Network:

- Packet Core: Control plane (in the Headquarter NPN): AMF, SMF, PCF, AUSF, UDM, NRF, NEF (towards Apps) – enabling the centralised authentication, authorisation, mobility and QoS control of the devices. A centralised solution allows significant privacy as well as efficient processing for the reduced number of devices.
- Transport Control: A new Edge router component enabling the secure connectivity of the remote Edge networks across multiple transport networks (e.g., satellite networks or public 4G/5G networks). We expect that the Edge router will become a significant component of the 6G networks as it controls the security and reliability of the link.
- Local RAN: This is the radio equipment enabling the nomadic node radio network. The prototype would be implemented with 5G RAN to showcase the advantages of the technology for use. This should be replaced with a 6G RAN with dynamic features in the next release.
- UEs: Modems connected to the specific devices which would connect to the nomadic network. As the RAN, they will be implemented using 5G in the project, showcasing the use case. They can be later replaced with 6G UEs when available
- Packet Core UPF: User plane functions deployed at the Edge and central locations. Both UPFs would include a reduced functionality compared to 5G, adapted to the specific privacy and security requirements of communication while simultaneously removing the overhead of charging and lawful interception. Furthermore, UPFs would not be involved in handover procedures as transport control would ensure mobility.
- Management Interface: For administrative tasks like provisioning the identities of the Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) cards used on the end devices.

Admin and Care Portal

- Web Application used to register patients for the study and visualise the patient records from applications like myReha Admin Server and Patient Data Analytics. The portal implements the Barthel Index questionnaire [34] for assessing the independence of the patient in daily life.

MCS Smart Watch

- Collects raw and pre-processed health and motion data from the patients and sends them via Bluetooth to a smartphone app or the eHealth Gateway. The pre-processed data is also shown on the watch. The smartwatch is configurable via the app or the watch to improve the results of the pre-processed data.

Smartphone / eHealth Gateway

- Collects the data from one or more watches and sends them via 5G to the backend, where different algorithms can run. The smartphone can only connect to one smartwatch and shows the patient’s live data. The eHealth gateway collects data from multiple watches and only sends them to the backend. The eHealth gateway has no display.

myReha Admin Server

- Web Application for interfacing with the therapist. Here the therapist can set the patient training programme and visualise statistical information on the quality of the exercise from the training sessions and video recordings.

myReha Coaching App

- App running on the 3D Body Tracking Sensor for interfacing with the patient during the training sessions. The app authenticates the patient using a QR code generated while the patient is provided access to the Admin and Care Portal. By connecting to a display, the App gives the patient visual hints on the accuracy of the exercise. Using a Borg Scala questionnaire [35], the patient is enquired on his well-being (tiredness) before and after the training session, and the exercises can be adjusted by the elderly, e.g. increase or decrease the number of times to perform an exercise and selecting the exercise to train and its order from the available exercises from the training program.

Figure 20: UC-HEALTH-2 High-Level Topology

Patient Data Storage Server

- Based on the HL7 FHIR standard and its database, it stores the patient records related to the nurse visits.

Data Access Control Server

- Provides access control service enabling access for the patient and the medical personnel to the Patient Data Storage Server using role-based policies and patient specific information (e.g. caring doctor).

MCS Patient App

- Collects the data from the smartphone or the gateway. The data is sent to the backend using 5G. The data is stored locally on the device if no connection can be established. The data can be seen in a Grafana dashboard.

MCS Patient Data Analytics

- Takes the received raw data and runs its algorithms like fall detection or stress level detection to provide the nurses with additional information and warnings in case something unexpected happens to the patient. The number of algorithms will be increased during the project run time.

4.3.2.4 Requirements

Table 70 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 71 contains the performance requirements.

Table 70: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Connectivity Availability	5-nines (dependent on the available transport networks at the location).
FR2	Audio-Video Call Reliability	Dependent on the available transport networks at the location and the application software.
FR3	Transport network availability	At least two transport networks (e.g. terrestrial or satellite) would be included.
FR4	Secure communication	Centralised authentication and authorisation at the hospital premises.
FR5	Secure backhaul communication	Additional securing of the backhaul communication over the transport network.
FR6	Network coverage	The network in the vehicle should cover the patient's premises.
FR7	Connectivity of the 3D Body Tracking Sensor for myReha	The specific devices can connect to the NPN Network.
FR8	Smart Watch connectivity	The specific devices are able to connect to the NPN Network via a mobile or an eHealth gateway.
FR9	Wearable connectivity in public network	The specific device should be able to connect to a public network and transparently transfer the data via a secure transmission to the caretaker headquarters.

Table 71: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Number of connected devices	The hospital enterprise network should be able to connect 10.000 devices, including all the elderly monitored devices.
PR2	Number of connected local networks	The network should be capable of connecting 100 Edge networks, representing the number of rehabilitation networks.
PR3	Network capacity	The local and transport network should be appropriately dimensioned to cover the capacity requirements of the use case > 2Mbps.
PR4	End-to-end delay	The end-to-end delay should remain in the expected use case requirements <1s.

4.3.2.5 Validation

4.3.2.5.1 Test Cases

Table 72 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 72: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 test cases description

Title	Description
TC1: Establishment of backhaul	Checking if the backhaul can be established over the selected transport networks.
TC2: Establishment of secure backhaul	Checking if the backhaul can be secured with available security mechanisms (e.g. Wireguard).
TC3: Establishment of end-to-end network	Checking if the nomadic RAN can execute the specific NG-AP operations with the hospital core network.
TC4: Establishment of the data path network	Checking if local and home-to-hospital routed networks are functioning.
TC5: Establishment of the end-to-end connectivity	Checking the UE registration, session establishment, session termination and UE deregistration. Checking establishing an end-to-end data path between the end device, the Edge network Edge, the central node network and eHealth backend services.
TC6: 3D Body Tracking Sensor	Checking the sensor extension running the 3D Body Coaching App with UE capabilities. Checking the end-to-end data path connectivity.
TC7: Smart Watch connectivity	Checking the extension of the wearable device with UE capabilities (mobile phone or eHealth gateway). Checking the end-to-end data path connectivity.
TC8: Smart Watch 3rd party connectivity	Checking the end-to-end data path connectivity of the wearable devices using the 3rd party network.

4.3.2.5.2 Validation Tools

To validate the use case prototype solutions, from a technical point of view, . test devices (mobile phones, laptops) will be used to test the end-to-end network connectivity establishment using ping and throughput using iPerf. The access to the eHealth backend services will be tested using Postman and the Admin and Care Portal.

The benchmarking tool of the Open5GCore will be used to simulate the workload generation.

To evaluate the impact of the applications on the elderly, the Barthel Index for Self Care⁷⁵ and a fall risk assessment will be collected at the beginning and the end of the study. Also, the NRS Scale for Pain⁷⁶ and the Borg Scale⁷⁷ were used. The Borg Scale allows individuals to subjectively rate their level of exertion before or after exercising.

Questionnaires targeted at medical personnel participating in the study will evaluate non-technical KPIs, such as public health and social impact, as well as user-friendliness.

The App will check if the watches are connected and charged. If the watches are not connected via Bluetooth or the battery is too low, a warning is sent to the backend to inform the nurse or caretaker to take the necessary steps.

4.3.2.5.3 KPIs and KVI

Tables 73 and 74 define the KPIs and KVIs for this use case.

Table 73: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Edge connectivity	Establishment of the connectivity between the Edge and the central network over third party backhauls.	<5s for all transport networks
End-to-end connectivity establishment	Establishment of the connectivity for the UEs.	<2s for the establishment of the end-to-end connectivity
End-to-end data path	End-to-end data path.	<200ms end-to-end data path in local and in 3rd party network
Number of devices	The number of devices which can connect and exchange the end-to-end data.	10.000 devices each with its data bearer

⁷⁵ For further details also see, *inter-alia*: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/medicine-and-dentistry/barthel-index>

⁷⁶ The numeric rating scale (NRS) is a pain screening tool, commonly used to assess pain severity at that moment in time using a 0–10 scale, with zero meaning “no pain” and 10 meaning “the worst pain imaginable”. For further details also see, *among others*: https://www.physio-pedia.com/Numeric_Pain_Rating_Scale

⁷⁷ The Borg Rating of Perceived Exertion (RPE) scale, developed by Swedish researcher Gunnar Borg, is a tool for measuring an individual's effort and exertion, breathlessness and fatigue during physical work and so is highly relevant for occupational health and safety practice. For more detailed information also see, *among others*: <https://academic.oup.com/occmed/article-abstract/67/5/404/3975235?redirectedFrom=fulltext>

Table 74: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 KVIs description

KVI	Description	Objective
Public health	Providing a better health service to patients' through using privacy centric patient tracking.	Use devices to track and customise the patients' exercises to the specific needs.
Societal Upgrade	Better adoption of the elderly care services through digital communication.	Provide an integrated wireless system across public and private network domains.
Societal Acceptability	Self- elderly care.	Provide digital elderly care services without having individually reserved physiotherapy personnel.
Technology Adoption	Providing secure and reliable small nomadic networks designed for eHealth.	Showcase a use case for rehabilitation exercises.
Sustainability	Reduce the number of travels of the physiotherapy.	Use home digital services to cover a very large number of patients.
Cost Reduction	Use case cost reduction.	Provide the rehabilitation use case with a reduced number of trained personnel.
Privacy	Extending the privacy of the hospital data to the home network (only specific patient data).	Include own data into patients' homes and devices and secure its exchange across third-party transport networks.
Medical	Patient side: movement to reduce the risk of falling or to ensure that the fall can be detected quickly.	Showcase a use case for rehabilitation exercises.

4.3.2.6 Expected Outcomes

- Providing reliable and secure connectivity for the eHealth communication of the applications running on the 3D Body Tracking Sensor as well as the wearables.
- Enabling data transmission integrity for video file transmission as well as sensor data from the wearables.
- Multimodal analysis allows differentiating between physiologic and non-physiologic medical algorithms.
- Encouraging and improvement of mobility in older people.
- Improve the well-being and sense of security of elderly people through monitoring and detection of potentially critical conditions.

4.3.2.7 Risk Assessment

Table 75 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 75: Use Case UC-HEALTH-2 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Not an integrated market of devices	H	L	Integrating the communication technologies available in the device with 5G connectivity devices (e.g., phones or CPEs).
R2	Limitation of availability from Public MNO and/or satellite	M	L	Design a connectivity map where the nurses' car could be parked (not in the scope of the initial use case deployment where selected places will be used for demonstrations where connectivity was priorly tested).
R3	Incompatibility of the new body tracking library and the Orbbec Persee 3D sensor⁷⁸	M	M	Use an older version of the Persee sensor and the SDK that was previously validated.
R4	A small number of elderly people taking part in the stud	M	H	Splitting the use case into different settings (daycare and nursing home).
R5	Acute change in condition by elderly people while exercising	M	H	Nursing professionals are continuously involved when elderly people engaged in the programme.
R6	Number of available caregivers to accompany the exercises is insufficient	M	M	Support from research assistants so that the elderly people can do the exercises.
R7	Problems producing the eHealth Gateway due to unforeseen supply shortage	L	L	Choose different components and order them as soon as possible.

⁷⁸ Also see, for example: <https://www.orbbec.com/products/camera-computer/persee-2/>

4.4 Smart Cities

4.4.1 UC-CITIES-1 – Connected and sensing city

This use case relies on a smart city platform, consisting of different types of vehicles (some of them being autonomous), people and sensors around the city, such as environmental and mobility sensors (e.g., video cameras, radars and lidars) all being connected and sending real-time information. This platform will serve as a “base” for the subset of scenarios that are further detailed next.

In a use case of high-distribution video on the move, we consider the scenario where people travel around while watching high-quality videos. The video coding and video distribution services are proactively orchestrated in the new points of access of the people before they arrive, so no video disruption is foreseen. The data on vehicles, people, city infrastructure and networks will give information on the prediction of both mobility and network quality, providing a prediction of the needs of the services in terms of quality and location, to travel with their users.

In a use case of traffic avoidance, we consider the scenario with autonomous vehicles and people, bicycles and motorcycles on the roads. Vehicles, communicating with other vehicles and with the Edge, sense their environment; the Edge, through their sensors, also senses the environment. This data aggregation and processing can be performed in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, integrating AI-network and Edge processing, providing latency-critical services, advanced resource allocation, (re-)distribution of Edge computing resources, and federated learning and computing in a continuum environment. The information on the environment will be made available to all the citizens and automation, allowing for the appropriate choice of paths to flow through areas with improved traffic performance. In a use case of enhanced city services, AI is used to provide better services to citizens, such as detecting stolen cars, badly parked vehicles, cars parked in the carriageway and control of shared areas, to improve the quality of life in the urban spaces.

4.4.1.1 Motivation

A sizeable majority of the population in today’s world lives in highly crowded metropolitan regions. This concentration of population strains city services and poses a challenge to local governments seeking to improve the quality of life for their residents, while still engaging in a responsible allocation of resources. The concept of smart cities can provide solutions to this predicament by employing information and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies and systems. By continuously collecting and storing today’s life data, these systems can deliver pertinent information to assist local governments in the improvement of city services [36].

With the growing adoption of the concept of Smart Cities, obtaining the city’s current status is becoming simpler. Data such as the average number of users in each location, the average number of vehicles per second on a street every day, or even the velocity of the vehicles and their path, which until now were unreliable and inconsistent, now become available and viable for study. Namely, patterns can be analysed and acquired from this data to produce new metrics or predict future behaviours/states of the city [37].

In this sense, there is an opportunity for innovation here with the exploration of a strategy that can help beyond 5G Networks to “meet” the high requirements of different critical scenarios in the city, from IoT to content distribution and autonomous vehicles, involving the consumption of city’s state metrics to increase the effectiveness of the application of Network Slices to the improvement of the QoS. The network slices can be dynamically configured and instantiated, considering the prediction of the mobility paths, and the prediction of their quality, to instantiate a slice in the equipment closest to the service needs and its following path. Simultaneously, the network is ready to support all the AI required for IoT applications in the city, without the interference between the different services running in a 6G network.

Key Pain Points

- Smart City Platform: A network of vehicles (autonomous and non-autonomous), people and city-wide sensors (environmental, mobility) connected in real-time.
- High-Distribution Video on the Move: Seamless high-quality video streaming for users on the move, using predictive orchestration of video services based on mobility and network quality data to prevent disruptions.
- Traffic Avoidance: Autonomous vehicles, bicycles and motorcycles interact with the city infrastructure and sensors via Edge processing and AI to optimise traffic flow, prevent congestion and enhance mobility choices for citizens.
- Cloud-Edge-IoT Continuum: AI-powered data aggregation across Cloud-Edge-IoT systems enables latency-critical services, advanced resource allocation and federated learning to optimise urban operations.
- Enhanced City Services: AI enhances city safety and quality of life by detecting issues like stolen vehicles and parking violations, and controlling shared urban areas for better public management.

4.4.1.2 Scenarios Description

The scenario, depicted in Figure 21, consists of vehicles (some of them being autonomous), from different types, people and sensors around, such as environment and mobility sensors (video cameras, radars and lidars as examples) all being connected and sending real-time information between the sensors, roads and the infrastructure. This overall scenario will be used for the following sub-scenarios in a complemented approach.

Scenario A – High-distribution video on the move

In a use case of high-distribution video on the move, we consider the scenario where people travel around while watching high-quality videos. The video coding and video distribution services are proactively orchestrated in the new points of access of the people before they arrive, so no video disruption is foreseen. The data on vehicles, people, mobility and networks, will give information on the prediction of both mobility and network quality, providing a prediction of the needs of the services, in terms of quality and location, to travel with their users.

Scenario B – Enhanced city services

We consider the scenario where an autonomous vehicle is moving around with other vehicles, requiring several services in the infrastructure for dynamic object detection, data fusion and online maps with dynamic objects on the road. These services are distributed through the new locations of the vehicle for seamless autonomous driving services while on the move. In a similar way as in the previous sub-scenario, the data on vehicles, people, mobility and networks will give information on the prediction of both mobility and network quality, providing a prediction of the needs of the autonomous mobility services, in terms of quality and location, to make sure that all will be ready while on the need when the autonomous vehicles arrive. AI is also used to provide better services to citizens, such as detecting stolen cars, badly parked vehicles and cars parked in the carriageway as well as controlling shared areas to improve the quality of life in urban spaces.

Scenario C – Traffic avoidance

In a use case of traffic avoidance, we consider the scenario with autonomous vehicles and people, bicycles and motorcycles on the roads. Vehicles, communicating with other vehicles and with the Edge, sense their environment; the Edge, through their sensors, also senses the environment. This data aggregation and processing can be performed in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, integrating AI-network and Edge processing, providing latency-critical services, advanced resource allocation, (re-)distribution of Edge computing resources and federated learning and computing in a continuum environment. The information on the environment can be

chosen to flow through areas with improved traffic performance. A digital twin platform is also used to facilitate traffic simulations, helping make decisions based on real-time information and simulated events presenting data in 2D and 3D formats.

4.4.1.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

The architecture of the system, coupled with the overall scenario, is depicted next. We consider a multi-technology AI-engineered, with 5G, mmWave, ITS-G5⁷⁹ and WiFi technologies. The data aggregation and processing are performed in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, integrating AI-network and Edge processing, for obstacle detection, road world perception and network performance. The Edge and Cloud based services are integrated with SDN (Software-Defined Networking), advanced resource allocation, (re-)distribution of Edge network slicing and computing resources, and federated learning and computing in a continuum environment. This will provide massive IoT data as well as latency-critical services.

The prediction of 5G, mmWave, ITS-G5 and WiFi performance can anticipate coverage problems that can prevent meeting the deterministic behaviour in practical scenarios. This can be integrated into an Edge re-location/orchestration of services and computing to improve seamless connectivity for the users on the move and provide them with a complete service wherever they are.

⁷⁹ See: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_en/302600_302699/302663/01.02.00_20/en_302663v010200a.pdf

Figure 21: UC-CITIES-1 High-Level Topology

To support the use cases, most of the capabilities of the ATCLL testbed will be utilised, including:

- Multi-technology communications (5G, ITS-G5, etc.).
- Sensors and Edge computing.
- Mobility metadata and network utilisation metrics.
- Resource allocation and service migration with Edge computing.
- Autonomous vehicles and connected vehicles and people.
- UEs and wearable devices on pedestrians.
- Mobility and environment sensors on bikes and buses, through IoT.

Most importantly, to utilise IT and Altice Labs 5G Core and MEC infrastructures, both entities will deploy roaming between cores and coordinate and intelligent service migration between MECs, to support all the use cases.

4.4.1.4 Requirements

Table 76 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 77 contains the performance requirements.

Table 76: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Low-latency Communication	The platform shall provide low-latency and reliable communication channels between the sensors, road, vehicles and people. It shall allow communication in real-time with low latency and high reliability.
FR2	Reliability	The platform shall be highly reliable to ensure that the communication channels are always available, can change between networks or technologies, or can even be used simultaneously.
FR3	Interoperability	The platform shall be able to integrate with other partners in a 3rd party and an integrated approach.
FR4	QoS	The platform shall provide different levels of QoS, through network slicing, to ensure IoT and latency-critical communications.
FR5	Scalability	The platform shall be able to scale to accommodate a large number of users and to support the growth of the smart city infrastructure over time. It shall also be able to accommodate new technologies in the path to 6G.

Table 77: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Low Latency	The communication platform should have low latency to ensure that the mobility of services is performed in real-time.
PR2	High Reliability	The platform should be highly reliable and always available, with low latency and high availability, choosing the best connection and technology for specific services and their requirements.
PR3	High Bandwidth	The communication platform should support high bandwidth to transfer large amounts of data, such as the perception of the environment.
PR4	Scalability	The platform should be scalable to support an increasing number of users and devices.
PR5	Interoperability	The platform should be able to integrate with different types of communication technologies and devices.
PR6	Security	The platform should have high security to prevent unauthorised access, data breaches and cyber-attacks.
PR7	Redundancy	The platform should have redundancy to ensure that the communication remains operational through the Edge computing approach and the use of different communication technologies.

4.4.1.5 Validation

4.4.1.5.1 Test Cases

We envision different scenarios considering the mobility and the connectivity in the roads, mainly on the mobility of the service through the network nodes, accompanying the mobility of the users travelling by walking or in vehicles, and mobility of services that are needed for the autonomous mobility of the vehicles. Here are some examples shown in Table 78 for this use case.

Table 78: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: High-distribution video on the move	We consider a scenario where people are travelling around while watching high-quality videos. The video coding and video distribution services are proactively orchestrated in the new points of access of the people before they arrive, so no video disruption is foreseen.
TC2: Coordinated and controlled mobility	We consider a scenario where an autonomous vehicle is moving around with other vehicles, requiring several services in the infrastructure for dynamic object detection, data fusion and online maps with dynamic objects on the road. These services are distributed through the new locations of the vehicle for seamless autonomous driving services while on the move.
TC3: Multi-technologies AI-engineered	Prediction of 5G, mmWave, ITS-G5 performance to anticipate coverage problems that can prevent meeting the deterministic behaviour in practical scenarios. This can be integrated into an Edge re-location/orchestration of services and computing to improve seamless connectivity for users on the move.
TC4: Traffic avoidance	We consider a scenario with autonomous vehicles, people, bicycles and motorcycles on the roads. Vehicles, communicating with other vehicles and with the Edge, sense their environment; the Edge, through their sensors, also senses the environment. This data aggregation and processing can be performed in the Cloud-Edge-IoT continuum, integrating AI-network and Edge processing, providing latency-critical services, advanced resource allocation, (re-)distribution of Edge computing resources, and federated learning and computing in a continuum environment. The information on the environment can be chosen to flow through areas with improved traffic performance.

4.4.1.5.2 Validation Tools

A dashboard using the ELK⁸⁰ (Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana) stack is available to monitor the deployment of the use cases. This dashboard features a map displaying the health checks of the city, showing all running services and indicating which ones are up or down. Additionally, it tracks whether containers are down. All logs are sent to this stack, making viewing logs with warnings or errors easy. The dashboard also monitors the percentage of used file space on each device.

The 5G systems are heterogeneous and present a high diversity of equipment and technologies. As such, monitoring the status of this system requires dealing with various information formats and different ways to access this information. Monitoring 5G systems for all the scenarios leverages the following:

- 5G Core monitoring: A couple of Open5GS Core network functions include an HTTP server that exposes metrics regarding the status of those network functions. With an additional Prometheus server, these metrics can be scraped and stored in a Prometheus time-series database, to be later accessed for analytics, complex processing or visualised with other software applications (e.g., Grafana).
- RAN monitoring: Aveiro's cellular infrastructure includes two technologies that implement the gNBs⁸¹: CableFree and srsRAN. These solutions expose a couple of metrics regarding their performance, but they are gathered differently. As such, the solution consists of creating two metrics servers responsible for collecting the metrics from these gNB technologies and then publishing them in the data platform with the appropriate data format. Both servers are implemented as docker containers with a simple Python script to fetch the metrics.

All the metrics persist in a Kafka Cluster⁸² so that other entities (such as ELCM) can subscribe to the brokers associated with this cluster and get real-time information updates about the platform's status. The second approach consists of persisting the RAN data in a Mongo Database cluster⁸³ so that other services can take advantage of a larger data set to perform some complex analysis of historical data. This was accomplished with a Kafka Sink connector that persists the data of specific Kafka topic in the Mongo Cluster.

4.4.1.5.3 KPIs and KVs

Tables 79 and 80 define the KPIs and KVs for this use case.

Table 79: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Safety	Improve road safety and user mobility (20%) (baseline: no AI supporting mechanisms).	20%
Accuracy and interpretability	Inferencing accuracy and interpretability, AI-models accuracy (and additional AI metrics) when it comes to predicting better decisions and the usage of explainable AI techniques to achieve performance	5%

⁸⁰ Also see, *among others*: <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack>

⁸¹ A gNB (gNodeB) is a node in a cellular network that provides connectivity between user equipment (UE) and the evolved packet core (EPC).

⁸² Kafka clusters are a group of interconnected Kafka brokers that work together to manage the data streams entering and leaving a Kafka system. Each broker operates as an independent process on a distinct machine, communicating with other brokers via a reliable and high-speed network. Also see, *among others*: <https://www.boltic.io/blog/kafka-clusters>

⁸³ A MongoDB cluster allows a MongoDB database to either horizontally scale across many servers with sharding or to replicate data ensuring high availability. For further informative details also see, *for example*: <https://www.mongodb.com/resources/products/fundamentals/clusters>

	improvement (5%) when compared with state-of-the-art algorithms and the no AI benchmark.	
Network performance (QoS)	Improve network performance (10%) using differentiated network slicing and other QoS techniques.	10%
Network performance (deterministic)	Improve network performance (10%) using deterministic network mechanisms and protocols.	10%
AAA mechanisms	Number of AAA mechanisms (at least 3) and third-party applications integrated and evaluated in trials.	3

Table 80: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 KVis description

KVI	Description	Objective
Integration and Interoperability	Seamless integration and interoperability between systems, devices and technologies within the smart city infrastructure.	Linking heterogeneous devices, over different networks and Edge computer nodes to provide seamless services while on the move.
Prediction Accuracy	Accuracy of AI predictions for mobility paths, network quality, and service needs enhances proactive service orchestration efficiency.	To achieve high levels of performance of ML models created to support enhanced city services.
Resource Utilisation	Efficient use of computational and network resources, ensuring that the services are delivered with optimal performance.	The objective is to ensure the exchange of network or computational infrastructure to support the overall efficiency of the service.
Faster Emergency Services	Improved response times for emergency services due to real-time data and advanced analytics.	Use AI models to allow combining mobility and network information allowing faster emergency services.
Reduced Congestion	Less traffic congestion and smoother travel experiences lead to reduced stress and improved mental well-being due to data analysis.	Use Digital Twins to simulate congestion patterns to improve the traffic flow in cities.
Enhanced City Services	Better management of urban spaces and services, such as parking and public safety, through AI and real-time data.	To combine different AI services to enrich the city platform.

4.4.1.6 Expected Outcomes

The expected outcomes from this use case are as follows:

- Enhanced Safety on the roads: Through better control of traffic and better control of the mobility.
- Better Decision-Making: AI detection and data fusion will provide the means to improve any decision system.
- Increased Efficiency: The mobility of proactive services and the ability to share information in real-time will increase the deployed services' efficiency and effectiveness.
- Better Resource Management: The AI network slice-based resource management will improve the management of network and computing resources more effectively, providing independence between services.

4.4.1.7 Risk Assessment

Table 81 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 81: Use Case UC-CITIES-1 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Data sensitivity	L	L	Risks related to data management can be mitigated through the Edge processing of sensitive data, which precludes the transmission of streaming data, for example, through the network.
R2	Difficulty in training AI models	L	L	AI detection and prediction risks can also be avoided by supporting Edge-based intelligence and federated learning.
R3	Autonomous mobility on city roads	L	L	Risks associated with autonomous mobility can be addressed using private lanes already in place in the ATCLL infrastructure in Aveiro, Portugal.
R4	Security risks for 3 rd party access to the services deployed in the infrastructure	L	L	Risks associated with the deployments and use of the testbed through 3rd parties may be avoided through VMs for services and secure VPNs to access the platform in a secure, simultaneous, and scalable approach.

4.4.2 UC-CITIES-2 – Automated logistics

The Smart Cities UC-Cities-2 – Automated logistics tackles one of three use cases for this vertical: Interconnected and intelligent cities, automated logistics and security coordination. Specifically, the UC investigates how Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) can improve the production process and employee safety. AGVs will streamline operations by reducing delivery times and eliminating employees needing to transport heavy goods manually, thus minimising the risk of injuries. This will be achieved by exploring and testing the integration of large-scale extreme IoT-Edge- Cloud scenarios, based on a 5G SA testbed.

4.4.2.1 Motivation

The growing demand for increased production, while ensuring employee safety and well-being, is driving the adoption of advanced Industry 5.0 solutions. When applied to smart cities, Industry 5.0 offers significant advantages. It enables the production of goods and services to be more efficient and sustainable, while improving resource and infrastructure management. By integrating Industry 5.0 principles into their manufacturing processes, companies can achieve reduced waste, lower energy consumption and overall productivity.

This UC explores automated logistics processes through an automated sorting system. This system aims to significantly reduce the time needed to organise finished products at the final stage of production, before they are shipped out. Additionally, employees are freed from this manual task, eliminating the risk of injuries, especially when handling bulky or heavy items. Advanced communication networks, beyond even 5G and reaching towards 6G, will be crucial for enhancing the performance of this solution.

Key Pain Points

- High network reliability and availability are essential for maintaining constant remote control of the AGV by a human operator.
- High throughput since video streaming should be sent to the remote operator.
- High device density must be supported, so that the AGV sensors can detect other objects or people and estimate their distance to avoid accidents, in an industrial environment.
- Leveraging heterogeneous data sources is crucial for optimising AGV routes and minimising process time. This includes real-time information on product location, current AGV position and its designated destination.

4.4.2.2 Scenarios Description

Autonomous robots, e.g., AGVs, can transform industrial environments like logistics warehouses. These intelligent machines will take over collecting and distributing goods, freeing up human workers for more strategic roles. This enhances safety by reducing manual handling risks and significantly boosts productivity.

Human oversight remains crucial, with operators monitoring the AGVs and ready to intervene if needed. The robots have advanced sensors and cameras, allowing them to seamlessly communicate with a central control platform. This communication is facilitated by cutting-edge 5G networking, ensuring real-time data exchange and optimal performance.

The future holds even greater possibilities. AI and machine learning (ML) tools are constantly being developed to train these robots further, allowing them to operate with even greater autonomy and reduce processing times even further.

The key players in the Smart Cities eses-2 Automated Logistics scenario will be OTE and ACTA. These organisations will take on the role of AGV warehouse operators.

OTE and ACTA will share the responsibilities of operating the AGVs within the warehouse. These include:

- **Issuing commands:** They will direct the AGVs to perform specific tasks.
- **Emergency intervention:** In an unexpected situation, they will be prepared to take control of the AGVs.
- **Data verification:** They will ensure the reception of sensor and camera data from the AGVs.
- **Network performance evaluation (ACTA only):** ACTA will be responsible for analysing network performance metrics.

UC pre-requisites for the scenarios are:

- The 5G/B5G network must provide robust coverage throughout the designated AGV operating area.
- The designated operating space for the AGV needs to be sufficiently spacious to accommodate its movements freely.
- The AGV should be equipped with sensors and cameras capable of generating significant data.

For consistency in reporting across all 6G-PATH use cases, this UC will present its results in a format aligned with the other UCs.

Third parties involved in an Open Call are expected to provide equipment that requires a 5G network with network KPIs at high limit.

4.4.2.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

The demonstration of this use case will leverage OTE's Athens Lab facilities, which are based on a 5G Standalone (SA) network infrastructure. This infrastructure will be further enhanced to "meet" the specific requirements of the use case.

The 5G network architecture that is planned to be used for this use case is designed to support Industry 4.0 vertical requirements, offering network capabilities such as Network Function Virtualisation Management and Orchestration, network slicing and Slice Management and monitoring of the network KPIs (throughput, latency, packet loss and jitter).

The architecture is separated into three layers: Radio Access Network, where New Radio⁸⁴ (NR) technology based gNBs are used and Edge Computing infrastructure is supported; 5G Core, including network components such as AMF, NSSF UPF; Applications layer, where orchestration, monitoring and slice management take place.

The testbed architecture (Figure 22) is based on 5G SA RAN Rel.16 and 5G Core SA Rel.16. It supports Network Orchestration, Slicing and monitoring of network KPIs and uses Virtualised Infrastructure (OpenStack/K8s). Finally, it could be upgraded by adding Edge computing.

OTE will play a dual role in this use case. Firstly, OTE will provide the necessary 5G/B5G telecommunications network infrastructure and the physical location where the use case will be implemented and executed. Secondly, OTE will also have the role of warehouse operator of the AGV.

⁸⁴ 5G NR (New Radio) is a Radio Access Technology (RAT) developed by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) for the 5G mobile network. It was designed to be the global standard for the air interface of 5G networks. It is based on Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing (OFDM), as is the 4G Long-Term Evolution (LTE) standard. The 3GPP specification 38 series provides the technical details behind 5G NR, the successor of LTE. For more details also see, *for example*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/5G_NR

ACTA will take responsibility for several critical tasks within this use case:

- Adjusting the Network KPI Monitoring & Validation Platform: ACTA will establish the platform that monitors and validates network performance.
- Identifying optimal network probes: Will strategically place probes throughout the network to ensure the most effective monitoring and segmentation.
- Probe and application installation and activation: ACTA will install and activate the network probes and the central application used to gather data.
- Network KPI metric selection and evaluation: Will select the most relevant network performance indicators (KPIs) and the collected data will be analysed to assess network performance.

Figure 22: UC-CITIES-2 High-Level Topology

The current OTE testbed (shown in *Figure 23*) is based on SA Rel.16 architecture, separated into three main parts: RAN, Packet Core and Edge Computing. The testbed supports slicing and allows secured remote access.

Figure 23: OTE Testbed architecture

RAN

The RAN uses NR technology and is integrated with SA Rel.16 5GC, including a Radio Dot, an IRU and a BBU, all provided by Ericsson. With the current installation, the covered area is more than 200 m².

Packet Core

The Packet Core is separated into two main parts: the Control Plane Function (CPF) and the User Plane Function (UPF). Both are implemented as OCI⁸⁵ containers. In the CPF component, four (-4-) Network Functions (NFs) are installed based on the 3GPP standard:

- Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF): The AMF component in the CPF can be accessed by any number of gNBs. Each gNB is assumed to be locally configured to access the AMF.
- Session Management Function (SMF): It can be configured to access any number of UPFs, including the UPF which is co-located. However, a UPF may only be controlled by one SMF. Although a gNB may connect to multiple AMF instances in different instances, each 5GS configuration containing an AMF is an independent 5GS.
- Authentication Server Function (AUSF): It enables the authentication of 3GPP access over NR.
- User Data Management (UDM) Function: It supports the ARPF function, the SIDF function to de-conceal the SUPI from the SUCI, the 5G Authentication Vector Generation, the UE Subscriptions and the Authentication credential Repository and Processing Function (ARPF) to store the USIM long-term keys.

Edge Computing

Edge computing is supported by providing the available resources on OTE's Cloud infrastructure, where an OpenStack Platform is installed. Edge servers allow moving the application hosting from centralised data centres down to the network Edge, closer to consumers and the data generated by applications.

AGVs

⁸⁵ The Open Container Initiative (OCI) is a collaborative project hosted under the Linux Foundation that is designed to establish common standards for container formats and runtimes.

In support of Smart Cities UC2 - Automated Logistics, this Use Case proposes using a robot as a core element for a fully automated logistics solution. The specific robot model under consideration is the RB-THERON⁸⁶, an Autonomous Mobile Robot for transporting loads in indoor environments, which is illustrated in *Figure 24*.

Figure 24: Autonomous Mobile Robot for transporting loads

Several extra components such as cameras, a router and a computer unit will be installed. Cameras will allow the operator to monitor and control the robot, and they will provide data about the environment and the process status. The router will provide connectivity to the 5G/B5G network. At the same time, the computer will handle the 5G/B5G radio communication, collect and process data from the cameras and forward the processed data to the Cloud, making them available to the robot operator.

ACTA KMVaP

ACTA has developed the KPI Monitoring & Validation Platform (KMVaP) leveraging Viavi's Network Integrated Test, Real-time analytics and Optimisation (NITRO) environment [38]. This platform utilises hardware (HW) and software (SW) network probes to gather over 150 metrics from various points within a live network. It enables automated, near real-time collection of user-selected network Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The components that ACTA will use in the UC implementation are the following:

- KMVaP application based on Viavi Nitro.
- Hardware probes JMEPxx Smart SFP⁸⁷.
- Software probes.

The KMVaP is the central management system for the multitude of probes installed in the network and is responsible for collecting data from measurement of network KPIs.

4.4.2.4 Requirements

Table 82 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 83 contains the performance requirements.

⁸⁶ The RB-THERON mobile robot is designed for autonomous transport in even the most confined indoor environments thanks to its compact design. For more details also see: <https://robotnik.eu/products/mobile-robots/rb-theron/>

⁸⁷ Small form-factor pluggable (SFP) transceivers are a core technology in many networks, providing communication between switches and important network components. SFP's are popular due to their small size, versatile connection options (copper or fiber optic), and hot swappable capability.

Table 82: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Video & Data transfer	AGV should be able to send information about the environment using sensors and video cameras.
FR2	Autonomy	AGV should be able to move autonomously, avoiding obstacles and paying extra attention to humans moving in the same area.
FR3	Security	The network will provide authentication of the devices that are registered in the network.

Table 83: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Availability	High availability (99,999%) is required, so that the human AGV operator should be able to reach and control AGV if necessary.
PR2	Reliability	Same as above for availability (99,999%).
PR3	Latency	Low to enhance the perceived quality of service.
PR4	Throughput	High to be able to stream video and transfer sensor data.
PR5	Density	Number of sensors/cameras per sqm.

4.4.2.5 Validation

4.4.2.5.1 Test Cases

Table 84 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 84: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: AGVs simulation run	Autonomous travel of AGVs in simulated conditions.
TC2: AGVs communication simulation	AGVs sending image/data and receiving commands in simulated conditions.
TC3: AGVs in use	The above cases are combined in a testbed (live) environment.

4.4.2.5.2 Validation Tools

This use case will make open access to the following datasets: A subset of training data for the AI/ML models (excluding business critical and IPR data); AAV and AGV communications traces from at least 2 experiments; at least 2 experiments trials or pilots network traces, including sensors.

The OTE network and ACTA probe diagram is shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Indicative probe and monitoring application positions at OTE Lab

Network KPIs will be monitored and validated through the ACTA KMVaP ecosystem. Data collection is an automated process running 24x7, with 1min monitoring granularity and 10 ms sampling granularity. Typical views allow the operator to monitor the progression of the selected KPIs along the selected flows (network segments) in real-time. Certain thresholds can be set to allow for a cockpit view of KPIs in accordance with the designated performance targets.

ACTA will leverage its experience to select a combination of hardware and software probes, both open-source and proprietary, along with the necessary central management software. This comprehensive approach will ensure optimal data collection. Additionally, ACTA will configure the probes to seamlessly integrate with the network interfaces and strategically position them throughout the network. This dual approach aims to achieve two “key” objectives: Comprehensive end-to-end network KPI measurement and detailed analysis of specific network segments.

The Viavi JMEP micro Ethernet probe⁸⁸ for Ethernet and IP performance assurance, is a hardware gigabit Ethernet smart SFP transceiver, available in two varieties, a 1 Gbps JMEP3 and a 10 Gbps JMEP10. Both SFPs can seamlessly be deployed inline into existing network devices. The SFP main capabilities are compatible with standard test methodologies. The Application GUI, probe types and example measurement results GUI are shown in Figure 26.

⁸⁸ For further relevant information see, for example: <https://www.viavisolutions.com/en-us/products/fusion-jmep>

Figure 26: Application GUI, probe types, measurement results GUI

4.4.2.5.3 KPIs and KVis

Tables 85 and 86 define the KPIs and KVis for this use case.

Table 85: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Availability	High availability required, so that the human AGV operator should be able to reach and control AGV if necessary	99,999%
Reliability	Same as above for availability	99,999%.
Latency	Low latency	<5ms
Throughput	High throughput	>3Gbps
Processing time	Reduction in processing time	10%

Table 86 contains the UC KVis descriptions.

Table 86: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 KVis description

KVI	Description	Objective
Route optimisation	Reduction in route optimisation.	10%
QoE	Improvement in QoE perceived due to high-throughput and extreme low latency	10%

	capabilities.	
Safety	Improve employee safety, since the employees will avoid transporting heavy goods, thus preventing from possible injuries.	20%
Service Delivery time	Reduction in overall service delivery time.	15%

4.4.2.6 Expected Outcomes

The UC relates to the effort to setup and evolve the 6G-PATH infrastructure into a B5G/6G experimentation platform.

Expected outcomes are:

- Automated processes are planned to reduce service delivery time. It is expected to be about 15% improvement.
- The employees will avoid transporting heavy goods, avoiding possible injuries.
- Network performance is expected to be advanced, offering low latency (<5%) and high availability (99.999%).
- This project anticipates that the deployed infrastructure will surpass the needs of typical warehouse logistics use cases. It will offer a platform for verticals to implement their use cases and capitalise on the capabilities of B5G/6G solutions and technologies.
- Attains or surpasses all the expected KVis/KPIs.

4.4.2.7 Risk Assessment

Table 87 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 87: Use Case UC-CITIES-2 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	Datasets availability	L	M	New datasets can be delivered.
R2	Testbed availability	M	H	Alignment with other activities is always examined.

4.4.3 UC-CITIES-3 – Security coordination

The police force plays a vital role in cities' daily activities by ensuring the safety and security of individuals in their communities. They are responsible for enforcing the law and maintaining public order, while their presence can significantly reduce crime and improve quality of life. In daily activities, police officers perform various tasks, from responding to emergency calls to patrolling neighbourhoods to prevent crime. They also conduct investigations, gather evidence and make arrests. Their role is both reactive and proactive, as they work to prevent crime by building relationships with community members and implementing crime prevention strategies. Effective police force management is essential for ensuring that police officers can effectively carry out their duties in daily activities. Emergency services communication involves dispatching emergency response teams to different locations in daily activities. Emergency call centres receive calls from individuals who require immediate assistance or rescue, and the call taker must gather all necessary information before dispatching the appropriate emergency services providers. This information includes the nature of the emergency, the location of the incident (i.e., where the call comes from), and any other pertinent details that can be used during the rescue or assistance. Hence, an effective police force is vital to ensure they “meet” their goals.

In our use case, we propose to investigate the usage of different communication technologies to assess the performance and efficiency of security coordination around a given situation. Thus, we aim to improve this coordination by using secure communications, refined geolocation and command and control tools, including situational awareness dashboards and real-time crime mapping information.

4.4.3.1 Motivation

In a traditional emergency response situation, communication between public safety end-users can be slow and unreliable, leading to delays and potentially dangerous situations. To “address” this problem, smart cities leverage advanced communication technologies like 5G and 6G to create more secure, efficient and effective communication platforms for public safety end-users.

Public safety end-users will benefit from on-demand network coverage and resources to enable critical communications, improving situational awareness when needed, coverage, availability, bandwidth, etc. The provided services will then be paid without worrying about maintenance issues. This will lead to the use of cheap and priceless solutions.

Key Pain Points

Our participation in this consortium is guided by the improvements of the current narrowband solution that we bring to the community. Hence, our main objective is to address and fix innovation issues and Pain Points (PP) such as:

- Current PPDR solutions are narrowband, so they are limited in terms of data exchange (specifically, video streams in each scenario). Thus, we need to investigate broadband approaches that will be “addressed” in the 6G-PATH project.
- With the TETRA [39] solution, UE radio profiles should be improved to embrace the New Radio profiles and technologies such B5G/6G NR [40].
- In currently existing PPDR networks, the scalability in terms of number of involved first responders is an issue for MCVideo and MCData and even for MCPTT in the era of 5G and 6G networks. We expect improvements in the agility of the new PPDR solutions to be more efficient, agile and scalable for a growing number of UEs.
- Interoperability between involved UEs in the same scenario is a pain point. Indeed, we expect to investigate 6G-PATH solutions to improve this point.

4.4.3.2 Scenarios Description

We consider and investigate two scenarios to illustrate the impact of new technologies on mission critical communications and applications. Figure 25 illustrates the different components, materials and services solicited in each scenario.

Our first scenario will be based on a situation in which we consider an end-user soliciting emergency services, which will be detailed in the sequel. Thus, the person requiring the rescue or assistance services will communicate some information (nature of emergency, its geolocation, any other relevant information) to the call taker. The latter will dispatch a message soliciting the right players/actors necessary for the identified mission. These PPDR end-users will then use and experiment Mission Critical Services applications based on the following functionalities:

- Individual (or Group) voice calls (PTT, Full Duplex).
- Individual (or Group) messaging.
- Individual (or Group) multimedia messaging, including video.
- Location and map services.

The second scenario of our use case is soliciting and simulating at least two different MCX actors and organisations (police and fire brigade, for instance). We focus on coordinating these actors and how the MCS core system will be adapted to host them adequately. This will help to analyse the situation, make the rationale and make appropriate decisions.

4.4.3.3 Key components and High-Level Topology

The use case is based on the usage of a Mission-Critical Communication Platform [41]. Agnet⁸⁹ notes this platform and essentially provides at least three services, that is: PTT, Video and Data, which will be detailed in the sequel.

The indicated applications are detailed as follows:

- **MCPTT** (Mission Critical Push-To-Talk): It is the most used application in the era of mission-critical networks and communications. It allows involved actors to share simple messages through a Push-To-Talk mechanism to a central controller via the control channel. The involved users and responders in the same mission share a voice channel, available in a pool of frequencies. When this transmission is finished, all radio devices revert to the control channel and the corresponding assigned voice channel is returned to a pool. More details can be found in [42].
- **MCVideo**: This service supports video transmissions for mission-critical organisations with strong security, high availability and reliability. This is allowed by new telecommunications technologies and New Radio (NR), such as 5G and Beyond. Figure 27 illustrates a scenario in which fire responders handle a mission-critical sharing video flow.
- **MC-Data**: This service provides a series of capabilities such as messaging, file distribution and data streaming. Moreover, it allows access to the internet, intranet and event for robot control applications. Figure 27

⁸⁹ Agnet brings secure group communication to smart devices on 3GPP broadband services on a commercial or private 4G/5G platform and support WiFi connectivity. With Agnet, smart device users become part of the professional world – voice, data, video and location services are all at hand with the reliability and security that professional users expect, with a high level of encryption. For more details also see: <https://airbus.com/agnet/>

depicts a case in which the critical mission necessitates to stream data while indicating and locating the position of the considered mission on a map.

Figure 27: Mission Critical Services: Video, Push-To-Talk and Instant Messaging

The illustration and realisation of our use case solicit an important piece of the Airbus MCS platform, represented by the dispatcher. This is described as follows:

The dispatcher plays an important and central role orchestrating the set of involved first responders within a given mission-critical scenario. It allows management of these players to facilitate the orchestration of the necessary steps to be strictly observed during the rescue or intervention operation. It is illustrated in Figure 28.

Figure 28: A high-level view of the Dispatcher in MCX

Moreover, the dispatcher's main role is to help identify the appropriate users for the PPDR case. It will be used for each call, necessitating the "opening" of a rescue session for a given incident or situation.

It is also a tool able to manage the rescue mission regarding the used resources (police, firefighters, etc.) and how to assign them in case of multiple incidents. Hence, it is responsible for coordinating multiple task forces for an efficient rescue operation.

Furthermore, Figure 29 depicts a high-level view of the different actors and tools that we will federate to guarantee secure interoperability and coordination between the various involved actors responding to a given scenario or situation. We will illustrate the impact of the communication technologies (5G, 6G) used to show the use case and assess the performance of the MCX platform. We indeed derive advice and lessons that will be learned from this use case to improve, adjust and finally augment the quality of the proposed MCX services facing new technologies.

Figure 29: Security coordination scenarios: A high-level view

4.4.3.4 Requirements

Table 88 contains the functional requirements of the UC, while Table 89 contains the performance requirements.

Table 88: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 functional requirements

FR	Title	Description
FR1	Low-Latency	It shall allow end-users to communicate in real-time with low latency.
FR2	Reliability and Availability	The platform shall be highly reliable to ensure that the communication channels are always available, even in case of network congestion or other technical issues.
FR3	Quality of service	The platform shall provide different levels of QoS to ensure that the communication channels meet the specific requirements of each end-user group.
FR4	Location-based service	The platform shall provide location-based services to help end-users locate each other and provide real-time situational awareness information.

FR5	Scalable service	The platform shall be able to scale to accommodate many users and to support the growth of the smart city infrastructure over time.
FR6	Security	<p>Verify the identity of each user accessing the system and ensure that only authorised users can access the system.</p> <p>Ensure that the information exchanged is not modified or tampered with during transmission.</p> <p>Ensure that the system is always available for use, and that any downtime is minimised.</p> <p>The system should be designed to withstand attacks or natural disasters and recover quickly.</p> <p>All communication between the users and the system should be encrypted to protect against interception or eavesdropping.</p>

Table 89: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 performance requirements

PR	Title	Description
PR1	Low-Latency	The communication platform should have low latency (less than 75ms for MCPTT use cases) to ensure that users receive real-time data.
PR2	High Reliability and Availability	The platform should be highly reliable and available at all times for all involved end-users.
PR3	High bandwidth	High bandwidth to enable the transfer of large amounts of data such as high-definition videos and images.
PR4	Redundancy	The platform should have redundancy to ensure that the communication channels remain operational in the event of a failure or outage.

4.4.3.5 Validation

4.4.3.5.1 Test Cases

Table 90 contains the test case descriptions for this use case.

Table 90: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 test case description

Title	Description
TC1: Emergency scenario	A policeman on the field is facing a gang attack. He is outnumbered. He needs support. He presses the emergency button implemented on his smartphone. The Emergency call centres receive this call. The call taker will gather all necessary information to dispatch the appropriate emergency services providers. This information includes the nature of the emergency, the location of the incident and the real-time audio and video coming from the smartphone. Then, the call taker will call the nearest forces to request their assistance. He

	will create a new group of communication with the forces involved. He will transmit all the information collected (audio, video, location, etc.) to this new communication group.
TC2: Coordination	A strike is turning into a riot. Fires started in garbage. The police on site need the support of the firefighters. The officer on the field will call on the pre-defined inter-organisation group of communication with the firefighters. One of the firefighters will take the floor with the PTT button and answer.
TC3: Situation awareness	A policeman on the field needs to get information regarding a vehicle's licence plate. He will push a button on its wireless body-worn camera to transmit the video to a computer vision management system. The computer vision will decode the licence plate and will automatically check the validity of this licence plate. The policeman will receive a message on his smartphone with all the information.

4.4.3.5.2 Validation Tools

For Mission Critical Services platform deployment, measuring and assessing the different KPIs is crucial, while ensuring that we meet the objectives described before. Hence, we need some tools to evaluate these KPIs. We can rely on:

- **Network monitoring software:** A tool that can be used to estimate the latency, the necessary time for the Mouth-to-Ear scenario, and the throughput and availability of the network.
- **GPS and location testing tools (such Real Time Kinematic - RTK):** This will be explicitly used to measure the location accuracy for a PPDR scenario.

4.4.3.5.3 KPIs and KVs

Tables 91 and 92 define the KPIs and KVs for this use case.

Table 91: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 KPIs description

KPI	Description	Objective
Mouth-to-ear latency⁹⁰	This is the one-way delay from speech entering the microphone to emanating from the recipient's speaker.	<200 ms
High throughput	Data throughput.	>3Gbps
User density	Total number of connected devices per unit area.	1 000 000/Km2
Positioning/Localisation	Position/localisation accuracy.	<1m (6G-1cm in 3D representation)

⁹⁰ Latency in telephone calls is sometimes referred to as mouth-to-ear delay; the telecommunications industry also uses the term quality of experience (QoE). Voice quality is measured according to the ITU model; measurable quality of a call degrades rapidly where the mouth-to-ear delay latency exceeds 200 milliseconds.

Reliability	Reliability relates to the capability of transmitting a given amount of traffic within a pre-determined time duration with a high success probability.	99,999%
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Table 92: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 KVis description

KVI	Description	Objective
Public Safety and Security	Increase in Public Safety coordination	10%
Response time	Reduction in response times	10%
Decision Making and Resource Optimisation	Better Decision-Making and Resource Management	20%
Cost Saving	Reduce the total cost of the rescue scenario	15%

4.4.3.6 Expected Outcomes

From the described use case and its various considered scenarios, we expect the following as relevant outcomes:

- Rapid backup arrival and deployment of new first responders facing a given PPDR scenario.
- A clear understanding of the situation by first responders and the dispatcher before arrival, thanks to the shared information feeds.
- A better coordination among responding first responders' units thanks to the creation of a dedicated communication group.
- Dispatching of appropriate and only necessary resources based on the severity of our situation.
- Enhance first responders' safety using shared information in real-time.

Hence, leveraging new technologies and coordinated communication systems, our PPDR scenarios will demonstrate the importance of "Modern" MCX solutions and how they can significantly improve first responders' efficacy and deployment.

4.4.3.7 Risk Assessment

Table 93 describes the risks currently identified for this UC and the respective mitigation strategies. These risks are also classified in likelihood (Light/Medium/High) and impact (Light/Medium/High).

Table 93: Use Case UC-CITIES-3 risk assessment

Risk	Description	Likelihood (L / M / H)	Impact (L / M / H)	Mitigation
R1	MCx core deployment compatibility with the platform testbed	L	H	Ensure the testbed is capable of hosting virtual machines.

R2	Security access to the platform	L	L	Ensure access to the platform with a VPN connection and an encrypted key.
R3	A risk linked to a large number of users and to support the growth of the smart city infrastructure over time	L	L	Reinforce the testbed with additional resources (CPU, RAM, etc.). Rely using a load test simulator to cope with this issue.
R4	A risk linked to the unavailability of 5G positioning service	L	L	Ensure the testbed is capable of providing this service.
R5	A risk in measuring the positioning and localisation accuracy	M	M	Rely on using a GPS reception and an RTK network service (if available).

5 Initial Identification of Relevant B5G Technologies and Integration Plan

This section identifies relevant beyond 5G technologies and investigates a potential roadmap for integrating selected technologies into the 6G-PATH architecture.

5.1 Identification of Relevant B5G Technologies

5.1.1 Wireless Radio and Access Technologies

(1) High-Frequency Radio - mmWave, THz

In B5G and 6G networks, the utilisation of ultra-high-frequency electromagnetic waves, specifically in the 30 GHz to 300 GHz range (i.e., mmWaves [43], [44]) and the 100 GHz to 10,000 GHz range (i.e., terahertz waves [45], [46]), will be further enhanced to “meet” the stringent throughput, latency, reliability and sensing accuracy requirements. Operating at these ultra-high frequencies allows B5G and 6G to deliver extensive communication rates and ultra-low latency, facilitating the implementation of emerging applications like XR. Moreover, these frequencies’ short communication distances and high directionality help reduce interference, making them particularly suitable for small-scale, ultra-massive IoT communication. Additionally, the short wavelengths of millimetre and terahertz waves and their unique penetration properties and sensitivity to specific materials enable high-resolution sensing and detection, which will be instrumental in advancing integrated communication and sensing applications in future 6G networks.

(2) Wireless Optical Communication

Wireless Optical Communication (WOC), also known as Free Space Optics (FSO) and Optical wireless communication (OWC) [47], [48], refers to the use of light in the infrared or visible spectrum to transmit data through free space, enabling wireless communication. WOC offers several “key” advantages, including the ability to support extremely high data transmission rates, typically ranging from Gbps to Tbps, and ultra-low communication latency. WOC can effectively mitigate spectrum scarcity, as the spectrum resources in the visible light spectrum are abundant compared to radio frequencies. Meanwhile, WOC operates in unlicensed spectrum bands, which helps reduce operational costs. Light is less susceptible to electromagnetic interference, making WOC particularly suitable for environments where electromagnetic compatibility is crucial. The limited penetration of visible light beams confines communication to specific areas, making interception difficult and enhancing physical layer security. Furthermore, since WOC does not require physical cables, it is an ideal solution in scenarios where traditional cable deployment is impractical or prohibitively expensive. These characteristics “position” WOC as a promising technology for high-speed, secure and flexible communication systems.

(3) Joint Sensing and Communication

Joint Sensing and Communication (JSAC), also known as Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC) [49], [50], typically refers to the integration of wireless communication and radar signal features to simultaneously achieve data transmission and sensing of the environment or target objects, including measurements of distance, speed, shape and material, during the transmission and reception of wireless signals. In addition to leveraging the characteristics of electromagnetic waves (such as THz) [51], ISAC is realised through various methods, including signal processing and analysis, beamforming, multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO), joint waveform design, machine learning, artificial intelligence and cooperative multi-domain information fusion. These technologies work together to integrate wireless communication with environmental sensing, enabling precise detection and localisation of target objects. This supports applications such as intelligent transportation, autonomous driving and smart

cities. As 6G and future networks evolve, this technology will further “drive” innovation and expand its applications across various domains.

(4) Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces

Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) [52], [53] refer to a new technology that reconfigures electromagnetic wave reflections using materials with programmable physical properties. RIS optimises the control of wireless signal transmission channels by adjusting the reflection coefficient, phase, and amplitude. RIS can intelligently manage the propagation paths of electromagnetic waves, significantly enhancing network coverage and signal quality while reducing interference and multipath effects, thus improving spectrum efficiency. This allows RIS to perform exceptionally well in various application scenarios, particularly in complex or challenging environments. Additionally, RIS is typically passive, requiring no additional power supply and using minimal energy to control the state of the reflective elements. Due to its advantages in improving signal transmission and optimising resource utilisation, RIS shows great potential in 6G, particularly in scenarios such as smart buildings, intelligent transportation, industrial IoT, drone communication, augmented reality and virtual reality.

(5) Distributed MIMO

Instead of concentrating antennas on a single facility, Distributed MIMO (D-MIMO) systems distribute antennas across various base stations, access points, or even user devices, thereby forming a virtual MIMO system [54], [55]. The fundamental principle of D-MIMO lies in the coordination of communication and joint signal processing. Each distributed antenna unit cooperates by sharing the same spectrum resources and employing synchronised signal processing techniques, thereby establishing a virtual antenna array [56]. This array dynamically adjusts signal transmission paths and power levels in response to environmental changes, optimising overall network performance. By leveraging advanced signal processing algorithms, D-MIMO effectively mitigates challenges associated with multipath propagation, using reflections and diffractions to enhance signal strength while minimising interference. This significantly expands network coverage, especially in complex environments such as indoor spaces or densely populated urban areas. Furthermore, D-MIMO systems support more concurrent users within the same spectrum resources, substantially increasing network capacity and spectrum efficiency. Its enhanced resistance to interference and signal fading bolsters the reliability and stability of communication. The flexibility in antenna deployment allows D-MIMO to be adaptable to varying network requirements across diverse environments, ranging from urban to rural areas. Moreover, D-MIMO systems dynamically schedule and allocate network resources, adjusting real-time signal transmission to ensure optimal resource utilisation.

(6) Cell-Free

Cell-Free (CF) is a novel extension of D-MIMO technology that departs from traditional cellular architectures by utilising many distributed antennas working in unison to provide seamless, wide-area coverage [57]. Unlike conventional cellular networks, Cell-Free technology does not assign users to specific cellular units [58], [59]. Instead, multiple antennas are distributed over a wide area and simultaneously serve each user. These antennas share the same spectrum resources and synchronise their signal processing techniques, creating a massive virtual antenna array that dynamically adjusts signal transmission paths and power levels based on the user’s location and environmental changes. This architecture eliminates cell boundary effects, ensuring that users do not experience a decline in service quality when moving across different areas. Cell-Free technology employs intelligent beam-forming and joint processing algorithms to maximise the benefits of multi-path propagation in the environment, enhancing signal strength and coverage while minimising interference. Since all antennas work collaboratively, the system can manage interference across a larger area, further improving spectrum efficiency and network capacity.

5.1.2 Network Transmission Technologies

(1) Programmable Optical Networking

Programmable Optical Links represent an advanced communication technology that enables dynamic control over optical transmission parameters, such as wavelength, bandwidth and routing, by making optical links – typically used for fiber optic data transmission – programmable and reconfigurable. This technology leverages the principles of Software-Defined Networking (SDN), allowing network operators to manage and optimise optical network performance in real-time through a centralised software management system. Programmable Optical Links facilitate dynamic bandwidth allocation, adjusting resource utilisation to accommodate changing network demands and ensuring efficient data transmission. The ability to reconfigure optical paths on-the-fly enhances network resilience and reliability, particularly during congestion or network failures. Moreover, the capability for dynamic wavelength routing and switching allows networks to handle large-scale data traffic fluctuations better, reducing congestion and improving overall performance. This technology has broad applications in data centres, telecommunications networks and Cloud computing environments, as well as in B5G and future communication networks. It meets the growing demands for high capacity and low latency, especially for future Edge intelligence applications.

(2) Deterministic Network

A Deterministic Network (DetNet) is an architecture designed to provide highly reliable, low latency and predictable E2E network services [60], making it particularly well-suited for mission-critical areas such as industrial automation, intelligent transportation, aerospace and military communications. By incorporating features such as time sensitivity, bandwidth reservation, redundant paths and strict quality-of-service guarantees, deterministic networking ensures that data is transmitted reliably within a specified time frame [61]. It is widely applied in scenarios that require real-time responsiveness and high stability.

Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) is one of the representative implementation technologies of deterministic networking, developed by the IEEE 802.1 Working Group [62], [63]. TSN enables high-precision, low-latency and deterministic data transmission over standard Ethernet by introducing mechanisms such as time synchronisation, traffic scheduling and resource reservation at the MAC layer to control the timing, priority and path of data frame transmissions, thereby providing low latency, low jitter and high reliability in network services.

Although 5G has established mechanisms for integrating TSN and DetNet standards, the current combination of 5G with TSN and DetNet remains insufficient to “meet” the demands of emerging E2E time-critical applications. This calls for further developing TSN and DetNet technologies in B5G and 6G.

5.1.3 Network Tiers and Segments

(1) Non-Terrestrial Network

Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) technology generally refers to the use of platforms such as satellites, drones and high-altitude balloons to extend the coverage of communication networks [64], [65]. This technology enables communication services in areas where traditional terrestrial networks are inaccessible or difficult to reach, such as remote mountainous regions, oceans, deserts and airspace. By integrating with terrestrial networks, NTN technology provides seamless global connectivity and supports a variety of application scenarios, including the Internet of Things (IoT), disaster emergency communications, aviation communications, and maritime communications [66]. As B5G and future 6G networks evolve, NTN will become a crucial technology for expanding network coverage and improving communication reliability, especially in responding to natural disasters, providing remote education and

delivering healthcare services. Typical satellites used in different NTN constellations include Low Earth Orbit Satellites (LEO, typical altitudes: 500 –2,000 km), Medium Earth Orbit Satellites (MEO, typical altitudes: 8,000–20,000 km), and Geostationary Orbit Satellites (GEO, altitude: 35,786 km). Additionally, NTN systems include High Altitude Platform Systems (HAPS), Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Networks (UAVs), and High-Altitude Long Endurance UAVs (HALE UAVs).

(2) Sub-Network Systems

Sub-network technology refers to the creation of multiple smaller or short-range network segments within a larger network architecture, where each sub-network operates independently and serves specific functions, such as wireless personal/body IoT, home IoT and drone swarms [67], [68]. This approach allows each sub-network to function autonomously within particular application scenarios, providing a high degree of self-governance and enabling dynamic adjustments and optimisations based on local conditions and requirements. Even in the event of a disruption in the connection to the main network, the sub-network can continue to perform its local tasks, ensuring the uninterrupted operation of critical applications. Additionally, sub-network technology supports localised resource optimisation, offering customised services tailored to application scenarios, such as industrial control, smart homes and autonomous driving. This ensures efficient resource utilisation and ultra-low latency. Moreover, sub-networks are equipped with multi-domain integration capabilities, enabling seamless coordination of network resources across various physical domains, including wireless, wired and Cloud computing, thereby facilitating the delivery of cross-domain services.

Integrating across multiple domains allows sub-networks to be flexibly deployed and scaled in complex network environments, rapidly adapting to evolving business needs. Sub-network technology plays a pivotal role in enhancing modern networks' flexibility, adaptability and scalability.

(3) Network and Computation Fabric

Network and Computation Fabric (NCF) [69] represents an innovative architecture designed to integrate network and computational resources for future applications. Its primary objective is to establish a flexible, dynamically optimised infrastructure by merging networking and computing capabilities. This platform not only provides traditional network connectivity but also serves as a computational framework, allocating computing resources in real-time based on the specific demands of applications, particularly those driven by AI or requiring intensive data processing and computation [70]. NCF oversees network transmission with an emphasis on task-oriented computing, facilitating E2E service delivery from Core Cloud infrastructures to Edge nodes. Ultimately, the goal of NCF is to achieve seamless integration of network and computational resources, thereby supporting a wide array of application scenarios, including smart cities, autonomous driving, Industrial IoT (IIoT), and AR/VR. With the deep integration of networking and computing emerging as a key trend in future network architectures, several related technical concepts are being developed with this objective in mind. These concepts, such as computing power networks [71], computing-first networks [72], and in-network computing [73], exhibit a high degree of similarity in their underlying goals and approaches.

5.1.4 Functional Technologies for Enhanced Network Automation

(1) Open Radio Access Network

Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) represents an open, standardised Wireless Access Network (WAN) architecture designed to overcome the proprietary limitations of traditional RAN systems through the use of open interfaces, virtualisation and intelligent features [74], [75]. By introducing open standard interfaces, O-RAN enables interoperability between devices from different vendors and supports the virtualisation and Cloudification of RAN functions, allowing them to operate on general-purpose

hardware. This significantly enhances the network's flexibility and scalability. Furthermore, the O-RAN architecture incorporates the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), which leverages AI and ML to enable automated network optimisation, real-time resource allocation, traffic management and fault prediction, thereby improving network performance and reliability. Through its modular design, O-RAN disaggregates RAN functions into separate modules, allowing operators to flexibly configure and deploy the network based on specific requirements, reducing both deployment and operational costs. This approach is particularly critical for the deployment of B5G and 6G networks [76].

O-RAN is currently experiencing rapid development, with its initial implementation in 5G networks introducing open interfaces, virtualisation and modular design-effectively dismantling the proprietary constraints of traditional RAN systems and laying the foundation for multi-vendor interoperability. However, to fully "unlock" its potential in B5G and 6G networks, further advancements are required in standardisation, enhanced interoperability between devices and systems and accelerated deployment of intelligent control mechanisms, such as AI-driven network optimisation and comprehensive Cloudification.

(2) Edge Intelligence

Edge Intelligence is a broad concept encompassing a set of technologies developed on the foundation of Edge computing, integrating AI technologies to enable AI-driven applications at the network Edge [77], [78]. It leverages the deployment of distributed computing resources within Edge networks and extends intelligent computing capabilities to Edge devices. This approach enables data processing and the execution of various AI algorithms closer to the data source.

By processing data at the network Edge, Edge intelligence supports intelligent services, effectively reduces network transmission load and achieves lower latency, enhanced privacy protection and improved real-time responsiveness. However, the inherent resource limitations of Edge networks pose challenges for running complex and resource-intensive AI models. This has led to the development of a suite of Edge intelligence technologies that address both network and AI-related challenges. "Key" technologies include:

- **Model Compression:** These techniques, such as knowledge distillation [79], model pruning [80], and quantisation [81], compress large AI models into lightweight versions suitable for Edge devices, reducing the demand for computational and storage resources.
- **Model Partitioning [82], [83]:** Involves dividing a deep learning (DL) model into multiple parts, with each part being executed on different devices or nodes, reducing the demand for computational and storage resources of a single device.
- **Federated Learning (FL) [84]:** A distributed machine learning approach that enables multiple Edge devices to collaboratively train a shared model without the need to upload local data to the Cloud, thus preserving data privacy and reducing bandwidth consumption.
- **Collaborative Computing [85]:** These involve processing data or tasks across multiple Edge nodes, distributing the computational load to enhance overall efficiency and enable effective data processing.
- **Heterogeneous Computing Architectures [86]:** Leveraging the strengths of different processing units, such as CPUs, GPUs, and FPGAs, to optimise computational efficiency on Edge devices and meet diverse task requirements.
- **Smart Gateways and Edge Caching:** Smart gateways handle data pre-processing and protocol conversion, while Edge caching stores critical data locally, reducing dependency on the Cloud and improving data access efficiency.

(3) Intent-Driven Networking

Intent-Driven Networking (IDN) or Intent-Based Networking (IBN) [87] is an innovated networking paradigm for upcoming 5G and 6G, designed to achieve highly intelligent and automated network management by mapping the intent of users. Intent can be defined as “a set of operational goals that a network should meet and outcomes that a network is supposed to deliver, defined in a declarative manner without specifying how to achieve or implement them” [87], [88]. Then, IDN leverages AI and ML in combination with SDN and Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV) to translate high-level intents into specific network configurations and operational commands [88]. Network administrators or users only need to specify their desired goals, such as performance requirements, security policies, or Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and the system automatically analyses these intents, dynamically allocates network resources and adjusts in real-time to “meet” the evolving network conditions. The major workflow of Intent-driven networking includes:

- Intent generation/definition: Network administrators or users define their requirements or goals at a high level, typically includes performance requirements, security policies or SLAs.
- Intent parsing and translation: The system parses and translates the high-level intents into specific network configurations and operational commands.
- Intent implementation: Based on the parsed intents, the network controller changes its configuration.
- Monitoring and Adjustment: The system continuously monitors network performance to ensure that it aligns with the defined intents. Meanwhile, the system can automatically adjust configurations in real-time to adapt to changing network conditions.
- Intent Validation and Optimisation: By analysing actual network behaviour, the system validates whether the user’s intents have been met. If discrepancies are found, the system can further optimise configurations and learn new strategies to improve responsiveness and efficiency in similar future scenarios.

(4) Digital Twin Network

A Digital Twin Network (DTN) refers to the creation of accurate digital replicas of physical network elements and their topologies within a digital space, allowing for the emulation of the state and behaviour of physical components [90]. By synchronising the physical and digital systems, DTN enables real-time mapping and precise simulation of network operations, device behaviours and data flows [91]. Additionally, DTN facilitates continuous monitoring of network performance, simulation and optimisation of network configurations in a virtual environment and the prediction of potential failures, thereby allowing for preventive actions that significantly enhance network reliability and stability.

A DTN model can simulate networks of varying scales, ranging from a single device to a regional network or even a metropolitan area network (MAN) [92]. By leveraging the powerful simulation capabilities of DTN, a wide range of network deployments, service developments and management strategies can be validated, accelerating network upgrades, network management and the development of network applications, all without impacting the physical network [93]. Moreover, DTN can generate rich synthetic data for AI model training, addressing challenges related to the high cost of real-world data collection and data scarcity.

(5) Zero-Touch Closed Loop Governance and Coordination

Zero-touch networks represent an advanced paradigm in network management, wherein operational processes are fully automated, minimising or eliminating the need for human intervention [94]. In response to the complex challenges posed by 5G and 6G networks – characterised by dynamic conditions, heterogeneity, increased network scale and the need to support diverse emerging service

demands – zero-touch networks aim to achieve autonomous operation through advanced data-driven methodologies, such as AI technologies. These technologies facilitate “key” network functions, including monitoring, analysis, prediction, maintenance and fault detection.

The Closed Loop (CL) concept constitutes an architectural framework for realising zero-touch management. CLs can be understood as a set of interrelated functions – monitoring, analysis, decision-making and execution – that are virtualised and dynamically orchestrated across various temporal, spatial and domain-specific contexts to enable goal-driven network automation and control [95], [96], [97]. In practice, multiple CLs can be instantiated within a system, each serving distinct objectives, such as ensuring quality of service (QoS) or achieving load balancing.

Closed Loop Governance (CLG) [98] refers to a framework of capabilities designed to manage and configure the behaviour of Closed Loops throughout their lifecycle. CLG provides mechanisms for retrieving critical information, such as the status, health and performance of the Closed Loops. Its core functionalities include lifecycle management of CLs, handling CL models, configuring policies, rules, triggers and priorities, and providing real-time feedback on the status and performance of CL operations.

Closed Loop Coordination (CLC) [98] involves the orchestration and coordination of multiple CLs operating within the zero-touch network architecture. CLs within a system are not necessarily isolated from one another; rather, they may influence each other’s operations. The relationships between interacting CLs can be classified into hierarchical relationships, where one CL is authorised to control specific aspects of another, and peer relationships, where CLs operate independently but influence one another’s behaviour by jointly managing entities or sharing resources. The primary objective of CLC is to enhance CLs’ performance and goal attainment, through various interactions during runtime. These interactions include delegating or escalating objectives, coordinating actions, and sharing information across different stages of CL operations. CLC also addresses conflicts that may arise between CLs, which can adversely affect their operations. Such conflicts often occur when CLs manage the same or different entities, potentially leading to performance degradation.

5.1.5 Network Security

(1) Blockchain-Assisted Security

Blockchain technology is emerging as a popular enabler for building distributed secure networks due to its decentralised nature, immutability and traceability [99]. As a result, blockchain is being integrated into various network systems, such as IoT [100], [101] and vehicular networks [102], where its distributed authentication capabilities improve resource-sharing efficiency and dynamic user access [103], [104]. In future networks with massive devices and cross-domain infrastructures, blockchain can facilitate peer-to-peer data exchanges, reducing costs while enhancing security. It also strengthens trust and privacy in large-scale, heterogeneous networks by supporting cross-segment collaboration without centralised management. Blockchain’s flexibility makes it particularly advantageous for dynamic network deployments, addressing issues related to trust, resource sharing, secure access control and privacy protection. It will further enhance and integrate into upcoming B5G and 6G systems to build trusted communication and network infrastructures.

(2) Zero-Trust Framework

The Zero Trust [105] security model represents a fundamental shift in the field of cybersecurity, emphasising the principle of “never trust, always verify”. Different from traditional security frameworks that rely on implicit trust within internal networks, Zero Trust assumes that both internal and external environments may be compromised. As a result, Zero Trust establishes a user-centred dynamic access

control mechanism, requiring continuous verification of every user, device and application attempting to access organisational resources, regardless of their network location [106].

Core elements of the Zero Trust architecture include the principle of least privilege, ensuring that access for users and devices is restricted to the minimum necessary to perform specific tasks. Continuous authentication is employed to verify identity at every stage of interaction, meaning it does not rely on pre-defined access permissions at the request stage, but instead applies strict verification, scrutiny and authorisation for each access attempt. Additionally, micro-segmentation is implemented to isolate different parts of the network, preventing potential attackers from moving laterally.

Moreover, Zero Trust operates under the assumption that breaches are inevitable, focusing on minimising damage and swiftly mitigating security threats. This model has proven particularly effective in addressing the complexities arising from remote work environments, Cloud-based infrastructures and the increasing proliferation of IoT devices. By reducing implicit trust and rigorously verifying each access attempt, Zero Trust significantly reduces the attack surface, enhances data protection and provides a comprehensive solution for maintaining security in dynamic and distributed network environments. Zero Trust is likely to deeper integration with AI and ML for real-time threat detection, automation of security policies and enhanced scalability across Cloud environments and IoT ecosystems. This evolution aims to “meet” the growing demand for securing increasingly complex and distributed network systems, ensuring continuous verification and granular access control across hybrid, multi-Cloud and Edge infrastructures in the upcoming B5G and 6G networks [107].

(3) Quantum-Powered Security

In the context of B5G and 6G, the increasing complexity of networks and the proliferation of devices present heightened security challenges. Quantum technology is anticipated to play a pivotal role in addressing these challenges, particularly in network security and encrypted communications [108]. One of the “key” applications of quantum technology is Quantum Key Distribution (QKD), which ensures secure data transmission by leveraging the principles of quantum mechanics. Through QKD, encryption keys are exchanged using quantum states and any attempt to intercept these keys can be detected, preventing unauthorised access.

Moreover, Quantum Random Number Generators (QRNGs) offer an additional layer of security by producing truly random cryptographic keys, enhancing resistance to future quantum computing threats. As quantum computers become capable of breaking classical encryption algorithms, quantum cryptography provides a forward-looking solution to safeguard the long-term security of network communications [109].

As quantum networks continue to evolve, the integration of quantum technology into B5G and 6G networks will facilitate the gradual development of a quantum internet, enabling secure quantum communications between devices [110]. This will lay the foundation for quantum-secure communication systems, enhancing network security and efficiency. These advancements will not only improve the overall security of distributed networks but will also ensure the integrity of data across critical infrastructures, such as Cloud computing, IoT systems and Edge computing environments, in the B5G and 6G landscape.

(4) Confidential Computing with TEE

Confidential computing primarily refers to processing sensitive data in a protected environment to ensure data privacy and security during computation [111], [112]. It mainly relies on Trusted Execution Environment (TEE) technology [113]. TEE enables secure computation through hardware-based security in CPUs, allowing sensitive data and applications to be processed in an environment isolated from the rest of the system via memory isolation.

As B5G and 6G networks connect billions of devices, ensuring robust user data privacy becomes crucial. TEE provides a secure environment for processing sensitive information, ensuring data protection even in untrusted environments such as Edge or multi-tenant Cloud environments. Additionally, with the widespread application of AI in B5G and 6G networks, confidential computing through TEE can protect machine learning models and datasets during training and inference [111]. This ensures that AI applications relying on sensitive user data (such as personal health information) can maintain data confidentiality across distributed Edge networks.

Furthermore, the secure execution environment provided by TEE offers a trusted mechanism for executing and operating cross-domain services in B5G and 6G. On the other hand, TEE-based confidential computing can also offer a secure environment for testing and deploying quantum-resistant algorithms and protocols, helping defend against quantum threats.

(5) AI-driven Security

AI-driven security in B5G/6G networks leverages advanced artificial intelligence technologies to address the increasing complexity and threats within next-generation networks. As the number of connected devices surges and distributed architectures become more prevalent, traditional security measures struggle to “meet” these evolving demands. AI-enabled threat detection and prediction provide real-time network traffic monitoring, enabling the identification of anomalous behaviours and potential threats, especially in response to large-scale attacks or malware proliferation [114], [115]. Furthermore, AI assists in optimising encryption algorithms and, when integrated with blockchain technology, helps mitigate the risks associated with quantum computing. This integration also facilitates secure communication between Edge devices and network nodes in distributed systems, thereby enhancing overall network security and operational efficiency.

Moreover, AI plays a critical role in strengthening physical layer security, particularly in wireless dynamic spectrum sharing, which is susceptible to spectrum attacks and interference [116]. AI technologies enable dynamic spectrum and electromagnetic signal monitoring, allowing for the identification of anomalous signals and interference, while facilitating real-time adjustments to spectrum resource allocation. This ensures efficient spectrum utilisation and bolsters system security, which is essential for the robust functioning of B5G and 6G systems.

Additionally, to “address” the privacy and security challenges AI may face, it is crucial to ensure that AI models are robust enough to withstand attacks, generate trustworthy decisions and prevent the malicious use of AI technology that could harm network systems [117], [118]. To achieve this, more resilient AI models must be developed, incorporating techniques such as adversarial training to enhance the model’s stability when confronted with malicious inputs. Regarding data privacy, techniques like federated learning combined with trusted computing can be employed to protect user data privacy. Furthermore, explainable AI ensures that AI systems provide transparent and trustworthy decisions, helping administrators understand the AI system’s rationale and better assess whether its behaviour is reasonable and secure.

5.1.6 Others

(1) Semantic Communication

With the advent of the B5G and 6G eras, the complexity of networks and the volume of data traffic have increased dramatically. Semantic communication is emerging as a core technology capable of breaking the Shannon limit⁹¹ and significantly improving the performance and resource efficiency of

⁹¹ In information theory, the noisy-channel coding theorem (sometimes Shannon's theorem or Shannon's limit), establishes that for any given degree of noise contamination of a communication channel, it is possible (in theory) to communicate

communication systems. Semantic information refers to the meaning or intent behind the data, focusing on the actual context or significance of the information, rather than merely its symbolic or bit-level representation [119], [120]. Unlike traditional data-centric communication approaches, semantic communication transmits only meaningful information relevant to the task or application by understanding the semantic content of the data. This reduces redundant data transmission and optimises bandwidth usage. In semantic communication, not all raw data is transmitted. Instead, the system selects and transmits only the content that is useful for the receiver's task, based on a deep understanding of the data's semantics. This method effectively lowers the volume of transmitted data, thereby enhancing both resource utilisation and transmission efficiency. By focusing on the relevance and meaning of the information being transmitted, semantic communication enables more efficient use of network resources, particularly in environments characterised by high data traffic and complexity, such as future B5G/6G networks.

(2) X-as-Service

In B5G and 6G networks, X-as-a-Service (XaaS) is poised to become an increasingly pivotal service delivery model. In this context, "X" refers to any functionality that can be provided as a service through virtualisation and Cloud-based technologies [121], [122]. This model leverages on-demand provisioning over the internet, eliminating the need for users to purchase or manage physical hardware or infrastructure, thus significantly enhancing the flexibility and scalability of service and resource deployment. As B5G/6G technologies evolve, XaaS will expand beyond traditional services to encompass more complex and dynamic services, such as communication, AI, and Edge computing, further promoting intelligence and scalability. The emerging X-as-service models in upcoming B5G/6G mainly include AI as-a-Service (AIaaS), Security as-a-Service (SECaaS), Data as-a-Service (DaaS) and so on.

discrete data (digital information) nearly error-free up to a computable maximum rate through the channel. For more details see, *for example*: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Noisy-channel_coding_theorem

5.2 Integration Plan for Relevant B5G Technologies

The roadmap for technology integration is shown in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Road-map for technology integration

The 6G-PATH divides the entire integration plan into four phases. In Phase 1, we initially identified the relevant B5G technologies, which has now been completed and is presented in this deliverable. Meanwhile, we also conducted preliminary investigations into the ongoing SNS JU projects to gain an overview of their topics and ambitions. We will continue to “track” their progress, as well as that of other relevant projects. In the subsequent duration of the 6G-PATH, we will advance the activities of Phases 2, Phase 3 and Phase 4.

Phase 2 focuses on clarifying the mapping between use cases and the corresponding identified technologies, as well as identifying the candidate technologies and external groups with which the 6G-PATH can integrate and collaborate. To this end, Phase 2 involves four main tasks.

- Clarify the advantages of the identified relevant technologies: This refers to the specific benefits each identified technology can provide, particularly in relation to the KVIs or requirements outlined in the 6G-PATH. This will help us establish a clear mapping between the identified technologies and the 6G-PATH use cases and platforms.
- Summarise the TRLs of identified technologies in relevant projects: This involves investigating the expected TRLs of the corresponding technologies in related projects, which will help determine whether the outcomes of these projects can be re-utilised for integration into the 6G-PATH.
- Map the identified technologies to 6G-PATH use cases and ambitions: This focuses on determining whether an identified technology can meet the requirements of the 6G-PATH UCs and whether it can contribute to advancing 6G-PATH’s ambitions after integration.

- Identify the candidate technologies for integration: By the end of Phase 2, 6G-PATH will compile a list of technologies based on the activities mentioned above. This list will be used for subsequent communication activities with external groups in Phase 3 and implementation activities in Phase 4.

After Phase 2, 6G-PATH will engage with external groups in Phase 3 to identify the final list of technologies for integration, as well as the corresponding external groups for collaboration on technology integration. Additionally, an initial plan for integrating each technology will be drafted. To achieve these milestones, Phase 3 will carry out the following activities:

- Call and determine the 6G-PATH partner teams for each technology identified in Phase 2. These partner teams will engage in communication activities with relevant external groups to explore potential collaborations for technology integration.
- Call and determine the 6G-PATH partner teams for each technology identified in Phase 2. These partner teams will engage in communication activities with relevant external groups to explore potential collaborations for technology integration.
- Determine the final external groups with which 6G-PATH will collaborate for technology integration. This decision will be based on the technologies that 6G-PATH has selected for integration, as well as the TRL and the willingness of the external groups to collaborate.
- Communication activities with external groups: This process consists of two parts. The first part involves initial communications to determine the technologies to be integrated and the groups to collaborate with. The second part focuses on drafting the initial integration plan for the final technologies selected for integration.

Based on the integration plan developed in Phase 3, the implementation of the integration will take place in Phase 4. In this phase, the primary technology integration will be carried out by the 6G-PATH UC partners and platform owners. Meanwhile, 6G-PATH will monitor the progress of the integration activities as well as the results feedback, allowing for adjustments and modifications to the process as needed. Additionally, 6G-PATH will continue to track updates and developments in the identified technologies and relevant projects, which will serve as a reference for upgrading the 6G-PATH architecture and integration activities.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented, in detail, the reviewed 6G-PATH architecture and its main components, interfaces and workflows, the reviewed blueprints for the various vertical use cases proposed in the project and the selection of potentially applicable beyond 5G technologies. These outcomes serve as the references for the ongoing and subsequent R&D activities in component development, system integration and testing and use case onboarding, testing and evaluation.

A pragmatic approach has been taken in reviewing and refining the 6G-PATH architecture, components and use cases, in line with the schedules of Open Calls for third parties' use cases. The reference architecture builds on the experiences gained from beyond 5G projects, especially 5GENESIS, one of the major platforms for 5G and beyond trials. The main difference lies in the expected advanced features to be offered in 6G-PATH, such as AI as-a-Service, Security as-a-Service, Closed Loop Coordination and different flavours of Network Slice Management, among others. The vast majority of the functional building blocks identified in the reference architecture can be "mapped" to existing components across the various testbeds within the project consortium, although further developments are needed to adapt the existing components to the 6G-PATH architecture. Moreover, additional developments are expected to optimise and further evolve these components in terms of functionality and performance.

The reviewed vertical use cases represent a broad spectrum of real-world businesses that can benefit from the evolution towards 6G, helping test the KPIs and contributing to the KVIs as defined. There are challenges ahead though, for example, in integrating components from partners and potentially from third parties to enhance the capabilities of the existing use case testbeds.

A large number of potentially related beyond 5G technologies are available for the project to further scrutinise to allow justifying the optimal and feasible choices to build a powerful 6G-ready system as envisioned.

Appendices

This section contains more details of specific deployment considerations for the 6G-PATH architecture.

Appendix 1: ELCM details

This appendix provides more details on the implementation of the ELCM.

Workflow

ELCM can be deemed as a scheduler for the execution of test cases. The execution of the test cases is based on tasks mentioned previously. These tasks are performed in three different stages:

- **Pre-Run:** This stage involves experiment registration and configuration, a feasibility check, a wait loop for the necessary resources.
- **Run:** The Run stage varies for each experiment type and involves executing the tasks necessary to run the experiment's test cases on the platform.
- **Post-Run:** During this stage, the resources used by an experiment are released.

Certain values cannot be determined while the platform administrator defines the tasks involved in a test case's execution. Examples include the Execution ID, which depends on the number of previously executed experiments on the platform and the location of an experiment execution's temporary folder, which is created at run-time. Other values may depend on the output from external applications. Therefore, the ELCM provides a set of 'placeholders'. These placeholders follow a predefined format, consisting of a known identifier enclosed in specific characters: a known identifier enclosed in curly or square brackets, preceded by '@', to ease their detection, including ExecutionId, the Unique ID of the experiment execution; TempFolder, the Path to the temporary folder created exclusively for use of the current experiment executor; Application, the contents of the 'Application' field in the Experiment Descriptor, JSONParameters, the complete 'Parameters' dictionary of the Experiment Descriptor, encoded in JSON format; ReservationTime and ReservationTimeSeconds, the value of the 'ReservationTime' field of the Experiment Descriptor; TapFolder and TapResults, the Paths to the folders where the OpenTAP instance and result output reside, as set in the configuration of the ELCM.

It is also possible to expand the values contained in the 'Parameters' dictionary independently, using the following expressions: - @[Params.key]: The value of 'key' in the dictionary, or '<<UNDEFINED>>' if not found; - @[Params.key:default]: The value of 'key' in the dictionary, or 'default' if not found. Additionally, platform administrators have access to Tasks that are able to generate new (key, value) pairs at runtime, either with a fixed value, a value extracted from a file or taken from a previous task. Once a value has been published using either of these methods, it becomes available for variable expansion using the following expressions: - @[key] or @[Publish.key]: Expands to the value of 'key' if defined, '<>' otherwise; - @[key:default] or @[Publish.key:default]: Expands to the value of 'key' if defined, or 'default'.

Administration interface

The Administration Interface is a web application developed using Flask, providing a unified interface for platform administrators. This interface allows them to monitor the execution status of an active experiment and track the usage of physical resources on the platform. Additionally, administrators can cancel an experiment's execution and review the generated execution logs through this interface.

Platform Registry

The Platform Registry defines the functionality and behaviour of a facility and consists of a set of YAML⁹² configuration files distributed across four folders alongside the ELCM files. These folders include **TestCases**: Contains information about the available test cases that can be run in the facility; **UEs**: Contains specific actions required for using and releasing specific equipment of the facility during the execution of test cases; **Resources**: Describes certain facility equipment, particularly those that can only be used by a single experiment at a time; **Scenarios**: Contains additional configuration values that can be set during the deployment of a network configuration.

Test case and UE description

The contents of the 'UEs' and 'TestCases' sub-folders outline the behaviour of the platform when an experiment execution request is received. The ELCM loads the contents of all YAML files in these folders at startup and whenever the 'Reload facility' button on the web dashboard is pressed. The dashboard also displays a validation log ('Facility log'), which helps detect errors in a test case or UE configuration.

The files in both folders share a similar format, containing a main dictionary key that defines the name of the test case or UE. This key includes the set of actions to perform when the UE is in use or the test case is being executed. For test cases, the configuration files contain additional keys to define the type of experiment (standard, custom, public, private, or distributed), the available configuration parameters (for custom experiments), and the contents of the Grafana dashboard. An important field in every task definition is the 'Order' value, used during the composition process to generate the final list of actions to execute.

Resources and scenarios

The files in the Resources folder describe specific physical or logical equipment that cannot be shared among multiple experiments simultaneously. For instance, a UE configuration file for a specific mobile phone is typically linked to one resource file, ensuring that the phone is used by only one experiment at a time. Another example is the use of a particular probe during a specific type of experiment. Resource definition files contain the following keys: **Id**, a unique Resource ID used to identify the resource during test case execution; **Name**, the name of the resource, visible on the ELCM dashboard; **Icon**, the resource icon, also visible on the ELCM dashboard. Required resources are configured per task. When an experiment execution request is received, the ELCM generates a list of all required resources for all tasks in the experiment (either from a test case or UE definition). When an experiment starts, these resources are locked, preventing other experiments with common requirements from executing until the running experiment finishes and the resources are released. In the context of the ELCM, a Scenario is a set of configuration values used to further customise the behaviour of the network. These files contain a dictionary with a single key, defining the Scenario name, and a corresponding dictionary as the value, which contains the collection of values to be customised by the Scenario.

Experiment Registry

The Experiment Registry holds information about each individual experiment execution. This includes logs, additional metadata like start and end-times, the final execution status of each stage and certain files generated

⁹² YAML (Yet Another Markup Language) is a data serialisation language that is consistently listed as one of the most popular programming languages. It is often used as a format for configuration files, but its object serialisation abilities make it a viable replacement for languages like JSON. For more informative details also see, *among others*: <https://www.redhat.com/en/topics/automation/what-is-yaml>

by the executed tasks. The Experiment Registry also supports various endpoints of the Open APIs, such as those enabling the retrieval of experiment logs.

Grafana dashboard generator

The ELCM can request the creation of custom dashboards from a running Grafana instance, allowing experimenters to review the results generated by an experiment. To generate these dashboards, the ELCM uses information from the Facility Registry, where platform administrators can define various Grafana panels. The parameters that can be used to specify the contents and visualisation format of each panel include Type (String) Panel type, available values are 'SingleStat' (gauges, numeric values) and 'Graph' (time series graph); Name (Optional) (String): name of the panel, if not set a default name will be generated from the measurement and field values; Measurement (String): measurement name; Field (String): field name; Unit (Optional) (String): results unit; Size (List[int]) (String): size of the panel (height, width); Position (List[int]): panel position in the dashboard (x,y); Color (List[int]): graph or text colors. For Gauges this is the list of 3 colors, otherwise a single value; Lines (Graph)(Boolean): True to display as line graph, False to display as bars; Percentage (Graph)(Boolean): whether the graph represents a percentage or not; Interval (Graph)(Optional)(String): time interval of the graph. If not set, the default Grafana interval will be used; Dots(Graph)(Boolean): display dots along with the graph or bar; Gauge (SingleStat)(Boolean): True to display as a gauge, false to display as a single numeric value; MaxValue(Optional)(Float): maximum expected value of the gauge, 100 if not set; MinValue(Optional)(Float): minimum expected value of the gauge, 0 if not set.

Appendix 2: Security-as-a-Service details

This appendix provides more details on the implementation of Security-as-a-Service based on OpenCAPIF.

Figure 31 shows the OpenCAPIF architecture⁹³. OpenCAPIF implementation is based in Containers. There is one Container per Service (API) offered. The list of containers exposing services include Invoker Management API: Service to register new Invokers in CAPIF, Provider Management API: Service to register new Providers in CAPIF; Discover API: Service used by Invoker to discover Services registered in CAPIF; Publish API: Service used by APF to publish new Services in CAPIF; Events API: Service used by all Entities of CAPIF to receive notifications (New service Published, Provider removed, etc.); Security API: Service used by Invokers to create security context and manage security authentication between Invokers and Services; Logging/Auditing API: Services to save and consult logs of use when Invoker calls Service; Access Control Policy API: Service used by an API exposing function to obtain the access control policy from the CAPIF core function, and; Routing Info API: Service used by an API exposing function to obtain the API routing information from the CAPIF core function. Services are exposed using NGINX as a reverse proxy supporting mutual TLS negotiation. All CAPIF API requests are coming to NGINX that handles the certificates negotiation for TLS mutual authentication and dispatches the request to the specific service consumed.

Figure 31: OpenCAPIF architecture

⁹³ OpenCAPIF enables experimentation, prototyping and validation for research projects and industry. Find here after research activities using or contributing to OpenCAPIF. The ETSI Software Development Group OpenCAPIF (SDG OCF) is developing an open source Common API Frameworks, as described by 3GPP, allowing to expose and consume APIs in a secure and consistent way. For further details also see: <https://ocf.etsi.org/>

All data persisted in a MongoDB database. This database contains the information about registered Invokers, Providers, Security Contexts issued, Logs, etc. Vault is the Certificate Authority (CA) included in OpenCAPIF. This CA is responsible for expediting all certificates requested by API Invokers and Providers. Redis⁹⁴ is used by OpenCAPIF as a bus for internal communication between services and manages the CAPIF Events triggering. Finally, the Register Service, which is out of the scope of CAPIF Standards, is responsible to provide the following information to API Invokers and Providers, including CAPIF Core Function address: the DNS or IP address of CAPIF Core Function to request Onboarding; CA Root certificate: Root certificate needed to validate Server-side Certificates, and; OAuth 2.0 Token: Token for the Onboarding operation in CCF (CARIF Core Function). This is the only operation which is server-side only TLS and the Token provides the additional security from the Client side. CAPIF Core Function will publish CAPIF APIs following the 3GPP URL specifications. The way 3GPP forms URLs for APIs follows this format: {apiRoot}/api-name/v1. Figure 32 shows the registration process.

Figure 32: OpenCAPIF registration

As noted, CAPIF framework is developed to facilitate secure and standardised access to 5G network services by third-party applications providing a unified API gateway that manages the exposure of network capabilities and ensures secure interactions between the network and external applications. Here are the “key” aspects of how CAPIF manages security:

Authentication: CAPIF employs robust authentication mechanisms to verify the identities of entities (applications, services and users) interacting with the network APIs, including OAuth 2.0: CAPIF uses OAuth 2.0 for token-based authentication. This standard protocol allows third-party applications to obtain limited access to network resources on behalf of the user, ensuring that only authenticated and authorised entities can interact with the APIs; API Keys: CAPIF can also use API keys for simpler authentication needs. Each API key is unique to a specific application and is used to authenticate API requests.

Authorisation: Authorisation ensures that authenticated entities have the appropriate permissions to access specific resources or perform certain actions, including Role-Based Access Control (RBAC): CAPIF supports RBAC, where access permissions are assigned based on the roles of users or applications. This ensures that only authorised entities can access or manipulate certain data or services; OAuth 2.0 Scopes: OAuth 2.0 scopes are used to specify the level of access granted to the token holder. Scopes define the resources that can be accessed and the actions that can be performed, providing fine-grained control over API permissions.

Encryption: CAPIF ensures that data exchanged between the network and external applications is encrypted to protect it from unauthorised access and tampering, including Transport Layer Security (TLS): CAPIF mandates the use of TLS for securing data in transit. TLS encrypts the data transmitted between clients and servers, ensuring confidentiality and integrity; Secure Storage: Sensitive data such as authentication credentials and tokens is stored securely using encryption mechanisms to prevent unauthorised access.

⁹⁴ Redis is an open-source key-value store that can be used as a cache, message broker, and database. Developers choose Redis because it is fast, has a large ecosystem of client libraries, and has been deployed by major enterprises for years. For further information also see, *inter-alia*: <https://redis.io/learn/develop/node/nodecrashcourse/whatisredis>

API Security Gateway: The API Security Gateway is a critical component of CAPIF that enforces security policies and provides a secure interface for API interactions, including Rate Limiting: The gateway implements rate limiting to prevent abuse and ensure fair usage of network resources. This helps protect the network from DoS (Denial of Service) attacks; Throttling: Throttling mechanisms control the rate of API requests, preventing excessive usage and ensuring that resources are available to all authorised users; IP Whitelisting/Blacklisting: The gateway can restrict access to APIs based on IP addresses, allowing only trusted IP addresses to interact with the APIs while blocking malicious or unauthorised IP addresses.

Monitoring and Auditing: CAPIF includes mechanisms for monitoring and auditing API interactions to detect and respond to security incidents, including Logging: All API requests and responses are logged for auditing purposes, and these logs can be analysed to detect suspicious activities or unauthorised access attempts; Anomaly Detection: CAPIF can employ anomaly detection algorithms to identify unusual patterns of behaviour that may indicate a security breach or attack; Audit Trails: Detailed audit trails are maintained to provide a history of all interactions with the APIs. This helps in forensic analysis and compliance with regulatory requirements.

Compliance and Regulatory Adherence: CAPIF ensures compliance with relevant security standards and regulatory requirements to provide a secure and trustworthy framework, including GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) Compliance: CAPIF adheres to data protection regulations such as GDPR to ensure the privacy and security of user data; 3GPP Security Standards: CAPIF follows the security standards and guidelines set by 3GPP, ensuring that it meets the stringent security requirements of the telecommunications industry.

Third-Party Security: CAPIF includes provisions for evaluating and ensuring the security of third-party applications that interact with the network APIs, including Security Certification: Third-party applications may need to undergo a security certification process to verify their compliance with CAPIF security standards before they are allowed to access the network APIs; Continuous Security Assessment: Regular security assessments and penetration testing are conducted to identify and mitigate vulnerabilities in third-party applications.

By incorporating these comprehensive security measures, CAPIF ensures that the interactions between 5G networks and third-party applications are secure, reliable, and compliant with industry standards.

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